

Project acronym: RESISTIRÉ

Project title: "RESponding to outbreaks through co-creaTive sustainable inclusive equality stRatEgies"

Grant agreement number: 101015990

Start date of project: 1 April 2021, Duration: 24 months

RESISTIRÉ

Reducing gendered inequalities
caused by COVID-19 policies

Deliverable 3.1

Summary report on mapping quantitative indicators – cycle 1

Due date of deliverable	30/09/2021
Submission date	30/09/2021
File Name	D3.1 RESISTIRE_Summary report on mappnig quantitative indicators - cycle 1
Organisation Responsible of Deliverable	OBU
Author name(s)	Clare Stovell, Federica Rossetti, Lorenzo Lionello, Alexis Still, Rana Charafeddine, Anne Laure Humbert, Charikleia Tzanakou.
Revision number	01
Status	Final
Dissemination Level	Public

Revision history

Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	18.09.2021	ORU/Sofia Strid	Internal quality check
0.2	24.09.2021	Consortium partners	Comments and suggestions
0.3	25.09.2021	Sciensano	Changes and addressing comments
0.4	29.09.2021	Clare Stovell, Charikleia Tzanakou	Final revision of draft report

Partners

ESF
ORU
YW
OBU
K&I
TUD
SU
UDEUSTO
ISAS
Sciensano

Acknowledgement and Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101015990.

The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of its author and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

List of acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019
EEA	European Economic Area
EC	European Commission
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EU27	European Union (27 countries)
GBV	Gender-based violence
GPG	Gender Pay Gap
HEI	Higher education institution
ILO	International Labour Organization
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPI	Non-pharmaceutical intervention
NR	National researcher
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PPE	Personal protective equipment
PPS	Price parity standard
RAS	Rapid Assessment Surveys
SES	Socioeconomic status
WHO	World Health Organisation

Summary

This report provides an overview of the first cycle mapping of quantitative, comparative information on indicators that allow us to measure and monitor the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19. Two types of mapping have been conducted, which provide us with a) European and b) national insights on the impact of COVID-19. The first mapping (European insights) looks at official secondary data sources at international and EU level, while the second mapping (national insights) concerns Rapid Assessment Surveys (RAS), which are studies conducted on the initiative of lobby groups, scientists or official agencies that provide fast, research-based assessments. The aim of the report is to provide analytical insights before the outbreak to identify baseline levels and compare this with data collected during the pandemic. It also sets the baseline for cycles two and three of the project, which will delve deeper into the issues highlighted in this first review and investigate the evolution of inequalities throughout the COVID-19 pandemic.

In line with the theoretical conceptualisation of the RESISTIRÉ project, the report builds on an intersectional, gender+ approach (Verloo, 2013; Walby et al., 2012) and its theoretical framework focuses on specific domains of gender inequalities¹ (work and the labour market, the economy, the gender pay and pension gap, the gender care gap, gender-based violence, decision-making and politics, human and fundamental rights, and environmental justice), and specific vulnerability grounds (sex and/or gender, sexual orientation, ethnicity, race, nationality, class, age, religion/belief, disability). The European-level data was produced by Sciensano and consists of three tasks: a scoping review of the literature, a compilation of indicators and a descriptive analysis of the data. The national-level data for the report were collated by 30 national researchers (NRs) contracted to map RAS focusing explicitly on the domains and target groups of interest in the EU27 countries (excluding Malta²) along with Iceland, the UK, Serbia, and Turkey, from May to July 2021.

The findings of this first cycle of quantitative mapping describe a complex picture, where women remain significantly disadvantaged across all domains despite the progress in gender equality made in the last decade. While at first glance some gender differences might seem small, a closer look at disaggregated data shows substantial disparities in the standards of living and in the wellbeing between different socio-economic groups, which are posed to deteriorate if governments do not ensure that the most vulnerable are adequately protected and cared for.

¹ These domains are based on the EC Gender Equality Strategy (2020-25) and on the Beijing Platform for Action

² Due to issues arising during data collection, this report does not include contributions from the Maltese NR. The situation in Malta will be considered in subsequent project cycles.

While evidence provided a clear picture of some aspects of inequalities in Europe, a detailed analysis was not possible for all domains due to data availability. In particular, comparable and harmonised data at a European level is needed on the gender pay gap, gender-based violence, decision making and environmental justice. Importantly, existing data is particularly limited for the most marginalised groups in society and current analyses rarely extend beyond differences in socioeconomic status, family structure and education. Non-registered workers, migrants, refugees and the homeless are likely to have been severely affected by COVID-19 and related government restrictions, however little evidence is available to assess these implications across the domains of interest. There is an urgent need for European databases to take varied inequality grounds into consideration to better understand the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19 related policies through a gender+ lens. Local rapid assessment surveys, providing fast, research-based assessments, have proved useful for filling some these gaps and offer an insight into issues at national level. However, further data and/or better integration of existing data is needed, especially at a European level.

Table of Contents

Deliverable 3.1	1
Partners	2
Summary.....	4
Table of Contents.....	6
Introduction.....	8
Methodology.....	13
European Insights Mapping	13
National Insights Mapping	14
Economy/Work and Labour Market.....	19
Summary	19
European-level Insights.....	20
National Insights	26
Gender Pay and Pension Gaps	29
Summary	29
European-level Insights.....	30
National Insights	32
Gender Care Gap	35
Summary	35
European-level Insights.....	36
National Insights	38
Gender-based Violence.....	41
Summary	41
European-level Insights.....	41
National Insights	43
Decision-Making and Politics.....	47
Summary	47
European-level Insights.....	47
National Insights	51
Human Rights	53

Summary	53
European-level Insights.....	54
National Insights	58
Environmental Justice.....	62
Summary	62
European-level Insights.....	63
National Insights	68
Conclusion.....	69
References.....	71
Annex 1 – Pathways and Indicators.....	81
Pathways of inequalities.....	82
Indicators of Inequalities	95
Annex 2 – RAS grid template.....	128
Annex 3 – RAS Country Report Template.....	132
Annex 4 - Mapped RAS	133
Acknowledgements	163

Introduction

The aim of RESISTIRÉ is to understand the unequal impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak and its policy responses on behavioural, social and economic inequalities in 31 countries (EU 27 plus Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey) and to work towards individual and societal resilience. The pandemic has led to the introduction of national policy responses and measures in multiple policy domains to slow infections and prevent deaths (Cibin et al., 2021). This has profoundly changed lives, with physical and social distancing becoming the new norm and, where needed, quarantining and self-isolation. It has radically shifted how society is organised, with increased working from home, home-schooling and intensification of online presence, all with their own specific (un)intended consequences (Bonaccorsi et al., 2020). It has also meant furloughing and job losses, with associated economic hardship and mental health issues, delayed ordinary health treatments, and worse, the loss of life (Nicola et al., 2020; Van Bavel 2020; Lewnard & Lo, 2020).

The impacts of these developments, like those of other crises, are gendered and related to sex, age, disability, ethnicity/race, migration status, religion, social class, and the intersections between these inequalities (Lokot & Avakyan, 2020; Walter & McGregor, 2020; Walby, 2015). They are uneven and unequal, disproportional in their consequences for different groups, and their long-term impacts are uncertain (Cumming et al., 2020). Women have been disproportionately infected by COVID-19 (Sciensano, 2020) and affected by its impact; as front-line workers, as formal or informal caregivers in society. As these positions intersect with social class, ethnicity, age and other inequalities, this proposal opts for a 'gender+' approach. This approach highlights gender relations and gender inequalities, but always considers how it is intersected by other inequalities (Verloo, 2013; Walby et al., 2012). Policy responses to the pandemic also need to consider the gender+ perspective, and how some groups benefit, while others lose out. It is important to understand how different policy responses are having unequal effects, but also how different responses can be put into place to understand and address gender and intersectional inequalities in different policy domains (Lombardo & Kantola, 2019).

To meet these aims, RESISTIRÉ conducts policy analysis, as well as quantitative and qualitative research activities, to inform the design of innovative solutions. In this way, it responds to the outbreak through co-created and inclusive strategies that address old and new, durable and temporary inequality patterns in and across policy domains. The overall methodology of RESISTIRÉ is based on a step-by-step process running in three cycles over 24 months (April 2021/March 2023). All project activities are organised in these three cycles, feeding results into one another.

This report (Deliverable 3.1) builds on the theoretical framework of the RESISTIRE project and aims to collect and analyse quantitative, bottom-up data on the most salient

inequalities that emerged or worsened during COVID-19, including those produced by the outbreak and by its policy and societal responses. Thus, its objective is to provide a picture of how COVID-19 has impacted on inequalities through the lens of quantitative indicators at local, regional, national, European and international level. It derives from an extensive – albeit not exhaustive – mapping of quantitative, comparative information on indicators that allow us to measure and monitor the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19. Two types of mapping have been conducted which provide us with a) European and b) national insights on the impact of COVID-19. The first mapping (European insights) looks at official secondary data sources at international and EU level, such as Eurostat (e.g. Labour Force Survey, Survey on Income and Living Conditions), Eurofound (e.g. European Working Conditions Survey, European Quality of Life Surveys), FRA’s EU-Wide Survey on Violence against Women etc. Wherever possible, microdata sets have been sought, e.g. through Eurostat, Eurofound, FRA, to allow for analysis broken down among as many categories of inequalities as possible (sex; other grounds of diversity such as age or citizenship; member of the Roma community, etc.).

The second mapping (national insights) concerns Rapid Assessment Surveys (RAS), which are studies conducted on the initiative of lobby groups, scientists or official agencies that provide fast, research-based assessments. The purpose of this RAS collection was to map, at national level, RAS that provide evidence on the economic, social and environmental impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic from a gender+ perspective. Most of the RAS involved the analysis of primary data collected since the beginning of the pandemic, although some RAS analysed existing data through a COVID-19 lens. This mapping also enabled us to identify the most promising of these RAS in cycle 1 of the RESISTIRÉ project. This is key in the establishment of links with the bodies that manage these RAS, allowing us to collaborate and exchange data with them in cycles 2 and 3.

Through this double mapping process, the report provides analytical insights before the outbreak to identify baseline levels and compare with data collected during the pandemic. Both mapping processes have been guided by the framework of policy domains drawn from the EC Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 and the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (UN Women, 1995), which is central to the RESISTIRÉ project as a whole. European data sets and national RAS were analysed under these eight key domains, defined in Table 1. The policy domain of gender stereotypes, included in the EC Gender Equality Strategy, is considered in this report as a general, cross-cutting domain, relevant to all other domains and contributing to producing or increasing their impacts in terms of inequalities.

Table 1: Definitions of Key Domains
FROM THE EC GENDER EQUALITY STRATEGY 2020-2025

Economy	As opposed to the previous domain, the domain of the Economy addresses issues at the macro-economic level, rather than based on individual or organisational considerations. "Some women are structurally under-represented in the labour market (EC 2020, p.7). "Women remain under-represented in higher paid professions. More women than men work in low-paid jobs and sectors, and in lower positions" (EC 2020, p. 10). Macro-economic considerations also call into play wider disparities among countries and geopolitical inequality, in turn evoking gender+ intersectional perspectives.
Work/labour market	Many women still experience barriers to joining and remaining in the labour market. Connected topics: "Improving the work-life balance of workers is one of the ways of addressing the gender gaps in the labour market." [...] "Mainstreaming gender in public administration, state budgeting and financial management." [...] "Social and economic policies, taxation and social protection systems should not perpetuate structural gender inequalities based on traditional gender roles in the realm of work" (EC 2020, p. 8).
Gender pay and pension gaps	"Women still earn on average less than men. Accumulated lifetime gender employment and pay gaps result in an even wider pension gap, and consequently older women are more at risk of poverty than men". [...] "Eliminating the gender pay gap requires addressing all of its root causes, including women's lower participation in the labour market, invisible and unpaid work, their higher use of part time work [or alternative forms of work] and career breaks, as well as vertical and horizontal segregation based on gender stereotypes and discrimination" (EC 2020, p. 10-11).

Gender care gap	<p>“Thriving at work while managing care responsibilities at home is a challenge, especially for women. Women often align their decision to work and how to work with their caring responsibilities and with whether and how these duties are shared with a partner. This is a particular challenge for single parents, most of whom are women, and for people living in remote rural areas for whom support solutions are often lacking. Women also carry a disproportionate burden of unpaid work, which constitutes a significant share of economic activity. Some emerging issues: “Sharing of care responsibilities at home is crucial”, “Insufficient access to quality and affordable care services is one of the drivers of gender inequality in the labour market” (EC 2020, p.11).</p>
Gender-based violence	<p>“Violence that is directed against women [or transgender persons] because they are women, or that affects women disproportionately”. Examples include “sexual harassment (also online), abuse of women, female genital mutilation (FGM), forced abortion and forced sterilisation, early and forced marriage, so-called ‘honour-related violence’, trafficking in human beings” (EC 2020, p. 3).</p>
Decision-making and politics	<p>“There are still far too few women in leading positions. Be it in politics or government agencies, at the highest courts or on company boards. This the case even if gender parity exists at the lower levels” (EC 2020, p. 13).</p>

FROM THE BEIJING DECLARATION AND PLATFORM FOR ACTION

Human and fundamental rights	<p>Severe socially restraining measures raise profound concerns about compliance with fundamental rights, e.g., non-discrimination; dignity; justice and equality; work and education; access to health; privacy and data protection, access to digital technologies. Within RESISTIRÉ, the areas of health and education will be particularly considered, particularly in the first research cycle.</p>
Environmental justice	<p>“Women are among the most affected by climate change. Meanwhile, their voices are often ignored in environmental planning. They also have less access to land and productive resources” (UN Women, 1995). Gender+ perspectives are imperative to understand the differential effects of environmental issues, as in the case of mobility patterns, availability of public transportation, commuting distances, availability of and access to green urban areas.</p>

The remainder of this report is structured as follows: to begin with, the methodology explains how the mapping at both European and national levels was undertaken. Next, a summary of the overall findings from both the European and national level mapping is presented. This is followed by seven subsections devoted to analysing findings in the context of the eight policy domains above, from a gender+ lens. The domains of Economy and Work and Labour Market have been combined into one subsection in this report, since the effects of economic and financial crises typically concern all parts of the economy at both macro (Economy domain) and micro levels (Work and Labour Market domain). The report ends with concluding thoughts. Tables of indicators and RAS are included in the annex.

Methodology

European Insights Mapping

The first mapping of quantitative indicators focused on providing European insights and consisted of three tasks: a scoping review of the literature, a compilation of indicators and a descriptive analysis of the data. To begin with, a scoping review was conducted of the eight key policy domains to assess the research evidence available at a European level. We focused on reviewing the relevant literature in order to define each topic, identify the inequalities present and assess the potential social and economic impacts that the COVID-19 pandemic might have had on the population. This review set the scene and provided key points for each domain, but was not exhaustive, given the time constraints.

We then developed a tool that can be used to map indicators of inequalities potentially caused or accentuated by COVID-19. First, relevant data sources were identified that contained comparable and harmonised data at the European level. Then, we identified the possible indicators within each data source that would allow us to assess inequalities for each domain using the search tools of the databases (e.g. Eurostat) or through scanning existing survey questionnaires (e.g. Eurobarometer). The most relevant and available indicators have been compiled into tables (see Annex 1 for specific information on each of the indicators). Finally, secondary data analyses were undertaken. Publicly available harmonised data were downloaded from the official sources' websites (e.g. country-level data available on Eurostat), while requests were made to access micro-level data (e.g. Eurofound *Living, Working and COVID-19* survey). For this first cycle, we focused mainly on descriptive analyses of selected indicators, which provide an overview of the current situation as well as baseline figures of previous years. These figures are useful for giving a snapshot of the situation prior to the pandemic and, where possible, will be updated in subsequent cycles when new data are released.

To better grasp the ways in which the public health emergency could affect women's and men's social and economic status, as well as overall inequalities, part of this analysis included identifying and defining specific pathways through which COVID-19 has contributed to create – or exacerbate – gender inequalities in each identified domain, following the ideas developed in the WHO document on population health monitoring (World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe, 2021). While reviewing evidence and literature for each domain, direct and indirect effects for each of the pathways were identified and defined. These differentiated between impacts directly related to the policies described and those likely to arise due to subsequent social and economic developments. These pathways were necessary to derive the indicators used within the results section and will be used as point of reference in subsequent iterations of the project, as a way of tracking the future developments of the crisis (see Annex 1 for tables of pathways and indicators). The list of pathways is not exhaustive and will be developed throughout the next cycles.

National Insights Mapping

The second mapping aimed to provide insights at a national level, based on the Rapid Assessment Survey (RAS) analysis generated by 30 National Researchers (NRs). These researchers represented all EU27 countries (except Malta, since no data was returned at the time of writing), along with Iceland, the UK, Serbia, and Turkey. They consist of researchers and experts in gender studies and inequality studies who were contracted to map the situation in their countries. Nine of the NRs are part of the project's partner teams, while the others were identified through a network of professional connections among members of the consortium. NRs received training through written guidelines and two 1.5-hour online briefing sessions, which outlined their role and the tasks they needed to complete. In addition to the data produced for this report, NRs were also asked to collect information on national COVID-19 policies and societal responses relating to the domains and target groups of interest (for Work Package 2) and to interview experts on the topic and people in precarious and disadvantaged groups (for Work Package 4). These activities will all be repeated in cycles 2 and 3 of the project.

For Work Package 3, the NRs were requested to deliver two types of output: 1) identify ten local RAS that focus explicitly on the domains and target groups of interest³ and 2) summarise which inequalities and domains have been addressed or omitted at a national level. NRs were asked to complete a 'RAS grid' of 17 questions (a combination of closed and open-ended) for each of the 10 RAS they identified. These provided information on authors of the RAS, methodology, respondents, key findings and which domains and inequalities were addressed (Annex 2). NRs were asked to map RAS that identify, measure and monitor the economic, social and/or environmental impacts of COVID-19-related policies, with a particular focus on the target groups within the eight domains identified above. If many RAS were identified, NRs were advised to focus on RAS that they deemed novel. These RAS could be based on primary data collection, or alternatively provide an analysis of existing (secondary) datasets, although NRs were asked to prioritise those using primary data. It should be stressed that the RAS mapping for this first cycle was exploratory to understand which kinds of RAS had been conducted in relation to COVID-19 in each country within the scope of this project. It was not intended to provide an exhaustive list of all available RAS.

Once RAS grids had been filled out, the NRs completed a country report (Annex 3), which guided them in summarising the inequalities, target groups and domains that were addressed by the mapped RAS and identifying which were missing. This report also

³ It should be noted that some RAS included more than one country, however the analysis here focuses on national level results.

required NRs to select the three RAS that they deemed most important or promising for contributing towards a gender+ inclusive COVID-19 recovery.

Between May-July 2021, the NRs produced 291 RAS grids and 29 country reports (a country report for Estonia was not completed). Although 10 RAS from each country were requested, and in most cases were delivered, some NRs delivered more and others less (ranging from 3-13). A full table of the 291 mapped RAS is included in Annex 4 and can be used to cross-reference the RAS identifiers that are used in the rest of this report (e.g. AT01). Frequency tables and graphs were created from closed-end questions to provide an overall picture of the RAS that had been mapped.

The vast majority of the 291 RAS consisted of primary datasets and only 34 were reported that used existing data. Most were one-off studies, although 93 were identified as having longitudinal dimensions. Most RAS were produced by higher education institutions and NGOs (Figure 1), while other author types identified by the NRs included independent research organisations, trade unions, management consultancies, businesses, banks or financial institutions, market research organisations, international agencies (e.g. UN, EU etc.) and the police.

Figure 1: Number of RAS according to author type

The RAS mapping involved identifying whether different forms of inequality were captured in the surveys. The most common inequality grounds identified in the RAS were sex/gender, age and socio-economic status (Figure 2). However, although sex and/or

gender were included as a variable in the majority of RAS, this did not necessarily mean that findings were examined through a gender+ lens and gendered analysis was often lacking. When other inequality grounds were reported, these were often related to migration background, which often overlaps indirectly with race/ethnicity, nationality and religion.

Figure 2: Number of RAS addressing different inequality grounds

**Some versions of the RAS reporting form did not include Nationality among the listed inequality grounds and so the frequency of this form of inequality is likely to be underestimated.*

In total, 47 out of the 291 RAS were identified by NRs as addressing stereotypes. These related to women having primary responsibility for caregiving and domestic chores, stigma towards COVID-19 sufferers, gender as a binary, racial stereotypes, and who should be considered as ‘vulnerable’ or ‘at risk’ (particularly in relation to age). However, it was often reported that these stereotypes were not addressed directly or explicitly in the RAS.

A central part of the RAS mapping exercise was identifying which of the eight key domains the surveys addressed. Figure 3 shows how often each domain was represented and indicates that Work and Labour Market and Human Rights were the two most common domains covered by the RAS. When ‘other’ was selected as a domain type, responses

included attitudes and values, mental health, access to education and access to technology, suggesting overlap with the Human Rights domain. When considering these figures, it is important to note that the connection between a RAS and the domains was sometimes limited or implicit. RAS which focused specifically on each domain are identified in the following sections.

Figure 3: Number of RAS addressing key domains

NRs were also required to highlight three key RAS which they deemed to be the best examples within their country. Factors taken into account when identifying these specific RAS as promising varied from the nature of the research design to the analysis and findings. Longitudinal studies were often identified by NRs as particularly promising RAS, since the repeated data collection points allowed for changes across the waves of the pandemic to be analysed (e.g. BE02, ES05, LV03, SK04). Several studies were deemed exemplar due to their consideration of gender and gender+ approaches from the outset. This included focusing on how women were affected in specific domains (IT09), employing feminist methodologies (TR02), considering the needs of vulnerable groups (ES08) and incorporating a gender+ approach into developing research questions (BE04). Studies that had already made a tangible impact, for example on policy making, were also reported as promising. NRs indicated that the potential for impact increased when RAS included short cycles and regular reporting; questions that were adapted to changing circumstances allowing for fast feedback on the behaviour of people; and a large sample size, which gave credibility (e.g. BE09). Many of the RAS identified as promising were broad in scope, covering many domains and enabling both a more cohesive view of the

economic, social or political situation of the country and an exploration into topics that might otherwise have been missed in more focused surveys (AT10, BE07). These 'promising' RAS are highlighted in grey in the RAS table in Annex 4.

Further analyses of the RAS were then completed at a domain level (see Table 1), focusing on open-ended questions on target group, main topics and findings. The RAS were read thoroughly by two researchers from the analysis group to identify commonalities and key studies. These two researchers also coded open-ended questions from country summary reports thematically under the categories of 'prominence of gender'; 'inclusion of intersectionality'; 'which inequalities'; 'which domains' and 'what's missing'. Country reports were divided up among the researchers and the material identified under each code was discussed and analysed collaboratively to identify commonalities and discrepancies.

Having set out the methodology of mapping exercises at both European and national levels, we now provide detailed findings of the insights generated across the eight domains first presented in the introduction. Each subsection starts with a summary of key points and goes on to provide European-level insights that have emerged from analysis of secondary data sources, comparing different European countries before and after COVID-19, where possible. Then, national insights from RAS are presented to understand what smaller-scale but fast data collection and assessment revealed about the impact of COVID-19 on inequalities.

Economy/Work and Labour Market

Summary

Although important from a public health perspective, the severe measures imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic have had dramatic negative economic and social consequences, triggering an economic crisis that is expected to be one of the worst since the Great Depression (OECD, 2020). Since economic and financial crises typically have trickle down effects which end up affecting all parts of the economy at both macro (economy domain) and micro levels (work and labour market domain), this section combines the analysis of these two policy domains.

The structure of modern global economies has been inherently defined by exponential economic and technological development, which have lifted many out of poverty and improved the lives of all, but has done so at the price of staggering socioeconomic inequalities (Deaton, 2013). The equality gap has represented a constant division in modern society since the industrial revolution, and has developed today into health, wealth, and wellbeing differences across all social and economic status gradients (Deaton, 2013). While the crisis seems to have hit all countries irrespective of their economic conditions, we observe that, within each country, some socioeconomic groups have suffered more serious consequences than others in terms of employment.

Amongst the social groups who have been historically most disenfranchised by the economy are women, who have tended to be more exploited, less protected, and more likely to be treated unequally across all demographic, socioeconomic and ethnic groups. A gap in the employment and unemployment rates of women and men was already observable across all European countries before the COVID-19 pandemic. Structural sexism is inherent to modern capitalism, which often requires women to be more prepared and qualified while enduring worse treatment, less pay, and rarer promotions to managerial or decision-making positions (Biletta, Isabella et al., 2018).

Key Points

- Women have a markedly lower participation in the labour market during the pandemic, and unemployment tends to be clustered around sectors of the economy which were particularly hit by the restrictive measures taken by governments to stop the spread of COVID-19.
- The largest differences in both employment and unemployment rates are related to educational level (rather than gender). Lower rates of employment have also been reported in the RAS by younger, less educated and foreign-born workers.
- According to the various RAS reviewed, among those who were employed, women were more likely to work from home than men. However, it is still not clear whether teleworking has had positive or negative impacts on productivity. More research is

also needed on whether the increased presence of fathers at home – because of telework – might affect gender-role attitudes, making them more egalitarian.

- An important gap in the field of work and labour market is the effects of the pandemic on the conditions of those who are in non-formal employment or atypical employment. Despite the support provided by governments through various welfare schemes (e.g. furlough), more attention should be paid to those who could not benefit from these schemes, for instance because they were not formally employed.

European-level Insights

The worst effects of an economic crisis have the greatest impact on the most vulnerable parts of society, as they suffer the indirect effects of rising prices, stagnating labour markets, higher taxes, and worse market bargaining power (Mazzucato, 2018; Whitehead et al., 2021). Extensive literature has concretely shown that women consistently pay a higher price in periods of recession (Eydoux, 2014), and European-level data suggests that this is also the case in the context of the current public health emergency (Bambra et al., 2020). While men have been more affected by the disease in terms of health, women have experienced more serious social and economic consequences (Cook and Grimshaw, 2021; Wenham et al., 2020).

Firstly, employment loss as a result of the pandemic has been recorded as higher for women than men globally: 5% in 2020 versus 3.9% for men according to the ILO (International Labour Organization, 2021). These figures are even starker in some countries, such as Italy where a comparison between the second trimester of 2019 and 2020 finds that 470,000 employed women lost their job, a drop of 4.7%, compared to the 2.7% drop for men (371,000 thousand employed) (Fondazione Studi Consulenti del Lavoro, 2020). Figure 4 shows that in all countries across Europe, men have higher employment rates than women, in both 2019 and 2020. In countries with the highest levels of unemployment in Europe – Greece, Spain and Turkey – the gap between women and men is more pronounced.

Figure 4. Employment rates (%) across Europe by sex
2019Q4 and 2020Q4, age group 15-64

Source: Eurostat Labour Force Survey, online data code: LFSI_EMP_Q

Educational level appears to play an important role as a determinant of employment, as for example women with lower levels of education have experienced more work interruptions and longer periods of absence from work than men (Brugiavini et al., 2021). Figure 5 illustrates that women and men with tertiary education have the highest employment rates in 2019 and 2020. The gap between those with a tertiary education and those with less than secondary education is especially large for women (around 45 percentage points in both years), and less pronounced for men (around 35 percentage points).

Figure 5. Employment rates (%) in EU27 by sex and educational level
2019 and 2020, age group 15-64

Source: Eurostat Labour Force Survey, online data code: LFSI_EDUC_A

While the pandemic did not impact unemployment rates drastically, as most countries adopted some form of social security net to avoid mass layoffs, a closer look at the most vulnerable workers highlights a drop in temporary contracts, which make up a larger share of women's total employment contracts than those of men in all countries analysed (Figure 6). Some countries have seen a gradual recovery in these contracts, but overall, the general level has remained below pre-pandemic times. The uncertain development of the pandemic creates a stressful climate for those who have lost a job or are struggling to find one (Bambra et al., 2020; OECD, 2021a). Importantly, while recovery from financial and economic crisis tend to often bring prosperity and a general improvement in overall life, recovery tends to be slower the further down the income scale, with the most affected often finding themselves in a worse economic situation in the long run (Mazzucato, 2018).

Figure 6: Temporary contracts (as percentage of total employment contracts) by sex in various European countries
2019-2021 monthly time series, age group 20-64 included

Source: Eurostat, online data code: LFSI_PT_Q

Widespread measures implemented in almost all European countries to stop the spread of COVID-19 required many jobs to transition almost overnight to home working so that physical contact in workplaces was minimised. This assumed that everyone could afford to have adequate space and means to work at home properly (e.g. a stable internet connection). However, this was not always the case and several issues related to remote working and occupational health emerged, such as how to guarantee the safety of home working environments (Bouziri et al., 2020). The consequences of these changes for working practices remain unclear and there is no consensus in the literature about the effect of telework on productivity. This may be due to features of teleworking having the potential to be both advantageous and harmful for productivity and worker satisfaction, depending on circumstances (such as whether children are present). On the one hand, working from home implies increased social isolation, lack of daily face-to-face interactions with colleagues and blurred boundaries between personal and work life (Samek Lodovici et al., 2021). On the other hand, it can also provide reduced commuting time, fewer interruptions from colleagues and greater flexibility in working hours (Ipsen et al., 2021;

Samek Lodovici et al., 2021).

Given increases in remote working, men, who tend to work longer hours, may have experienced an increase in the amount of time spent at home. This change, in addition to school and nursery closures, has potential for increasing men's – and especially fathers' – awareness of the realities of unpaid domestic responsibilities (Mangiavacchi et al., 2021). The household division of paid and unpaid work is strongly shaped by gender ideologies around how tasks ought to be divided between women and men (Davis and Greenstein, 2009, p. 87). Following the pandemic, it remains to be seen to what degree the transformations to working patterns will persist and whether gender ideologies will adjust to changing family and employment circumstances (Reichelt et al., 2021). This is a topic that is covered in greater detail in the analysis of the gender care gap domain.

Sectors unable to shift to home working - such as retail, tourism, care, and hospitality - were some of the most affected by the pandemic. Some, such as tourism and hospitality, were brought to an almost complete halt for the majority of 2020, while others, such as supermarkets and care providers, faced increased demand. Workers in these sectors were exposed to higher risks of infection because basic protection measures were not respected or due to the higher number of close contacts. Eighty-four percent of all women's employment is in the care, services, and tourism sectors, in which they are consistently employed more than men, while they present a smaller fraction in the information and communication sector (which swiftly transitioned to remote work) across Europe (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Employees (in thousands) by specific economic sectors and sex 2019, most complete data series available for all countries

Source: Eurostat, online data code: LFSQ_EGAN2

The process of recovery and exit from the pandemic remains unclear (European Commission, 2021a, 2021b), with predictions remaining especially uncertain due to the possibility of new variants of COVID-19 emerging. There is, however, a very real prospect of economic recession due to the halt of economic and social life during much of 2020 and 2021 (Ferrer, 2021). It is envisaged that women will face the longest negative effects - including lower wages, decreased working hours, and less accessible job markets - and will therefore have to rely more heavily on welfare support of governments. The observations presented above constitute a partial picture of the inequities experienced by women in the overall economy. The gap in employment, pay, care, and occupational status requires a detailed examination of a variety of country-specific indicators, outside of the scope of this report. Focusing on only one indicator can, as previously shown in the literature, bring governments to underestimate these differences (International Labour Organization, 2018).

National Insights

In the Work and Labour Market domain, 169 relevant RAS were identified. For the Economy, the total was 96, however only 14 RAS were identified as pertaining to the Economy domain and not to Work and Labour Market (resulting in a total of 183 for both domains). These domains were some of the most common among the RAS, however it should be noted that many RAS did not include gendered analysis or have work or the economy as a central focus. Exceptions were **FR10**, **HR01**, **IT07**, **PL02** and **SE03**, which were identified as key RAS for this domain.

Common Findings

Echoing the European insights above, most RAS indicated that women's employment rate had declined during the pandemic at a greater rate than men's and they also reported more absences (BE02, ES06, FI03, GER03, IE05, PL06, SER07, TR04). Furthermore, women were more likely to express concerns about keeping or finding a job during the pandemic (BE10, ES10, HU06, PL05), which was found to contribute to them reporting poorer mental health (e.g. RO01). Some RAS reported that men had faced similar or greater levels of unemployment in the early stages of the pandemic, but in most cases these trends had reversed over time (ES07, CZ03, IE04, SER09, SK10). Government schemes were reported as important in mitigating the effects of the pandemic on unemployment rates (e.g. CZ06).

For those who were employed, many RAS found that women were more likely to work from home than men, or to have the opportunity to do so (ES02, ES06, ES07, HU09, IS02, IT03, PL06, SER07, SK09, TR04). However, studies demonstrated that working from home increased the number of hours in paid work (ES02, IS02). While women were more likely to report poor or worsening work-life balance during the pandemic than men (e.g. ES03), they seemed to appreciate home working more (e.g. GR05) and reported that their productivity increased (e.g. SK09), although in alignment with the debate about the effect of teleworking on productivity discussed above, some studies reported the reverse (e.g. RO02).

As with European-level analysis, sector was identified as an important factor in explaining gender differences in the consequences of the pandemic on the economy, work and the labour market. Since women make up the majority of those employed and engaged in the areas of health care, education and social protection, they appear to have been the ones most affected by the crisis, especially those with lower education working in low paying jobs (SER02).

Specific examples:

- A RAS conducted by the United Nations in Serbia (SER09) noted that businesses dismissed mostly men as an immediate reaction to the crisis (58,400 men lost their jobs nationally during March 2020 compared to 2,500 women), however by the

second quarter of 2020, the opposite was observed (34,700 women lost their job compared to an increase of 1,500 more jobs for men).

- According to a nationally representative RAS from Poland (PL06), 10% of women lost their jobs during the pandemic, which is two times higher than among men. More women reported working remotely from home (14%) compared to men (9%), while fewer women (66%) than men (79%) reported working outside the home. Another Polish RAS (PL02) found that 32% of the women surveyed had lost the possibility of career development or joining a new project due to the pandemic.
- Understanding Society, a UK longitudinal household panel survey (UK04), reported that among those who were furloughed, women had more negative experiences than men. In July 2020, 31% of women who had been furloughed at any point during the pandemic had worked zero hours since March, compared with 20% of men. Among those with experience of furlough, women were also more likely to express concerns about losing their job.
- A French RAS (FR10) conducted among a representative sample of 2002 salaried office workers found that women were 1.3 times less likely than men to have an isolated space to work (62% compared to 71% of men) and 1.5 times more likely to be frequently interrupted when teleworking (28% compared to 19% for men).
- A Swedish survey of academics (SE03) found that men reported receiving more support at work and were more likely to get the resources they asked for. The majority (71%) of women claimed they were satisfied with the support from their immediate manager in handling COVID-19, although this was even higher for men (77%).

Gender+ Dimensions

As well as cross-national and gender differences, analysis of the RAS revealed that the impacts of the pandemic on work varied according to other demographics. Unsurprisingly, the most protected workers, with permanent contracts and the ability to move to home or agile working, were the most satisfied with their current working conditions and work-life balance. Many RAS indicate that the self-employed had higher rates of unemployment or were more at risk of unemployment (AT08, BG01). Having a low income prior to the pandemic was also related to higher levels of unemployment (ES05). Younger (AT08, BE02, ES06, PL06,,), less educated (BE02, PL06, PT04) and foreign born (BE02, AT08, ES05, IE05, TR07) workers exhibited a lower rate of employment during the pandemic. According to a Spanish RAS (ES05), the situation improved over time for young people but not for foreign born individuals. Location within a country was also an important factor for determining unemployment risk, with RAS indicating that rural populations were more affected than urban populations, and that this was particularly the case for rural women (e.g. SER06). The RAS further indicated that parenthood and couple status were important

for understanding experiences of gender inequality during the pandemic, since single women without children faced less severe consequences (AT08, GER07, GR03, GER03, SK09). The situation was particularly difficult for single parents, who perceived an uncertain future and had most difficulty combining paid work and childcare (e.g. UK01).

Specific examples:

- A Slovakian RAS on homeworking (SK09) found that people with a higher socio-economic status were more likely to work from home in the first wave of the pandemic – 54% compared to 15% of those with the lowest socio-economic status. It also observed that the number of days parents worked from home was higher when they had younger children.
- In the UK, a RAS among a random sample of adults (UK01) reported that 50% of employed BAME women and 43% employed white women were worried about their job or promotion prospects due to the pandemic, compared with 35% of employed white men.
- According to a RAS from the Czech Republic (CZ03), which has released regular reports on national unemployment rates during the pandemic, the highest year-on-year growth rate of unemployment among men was observed in the age categories 20–24 and 45–49. Women showed the highest growth rates around retirement age.
- A longitudinal German RAS of self-employed workers (GER07) observed that coupled women were less likely to be working than coupled men, whereas the opposite was true for single women and men (GER07).
- A RAS from Spain (ES05) used anonymised bank records from the working population (excluding the self-employed) to track income inequality over the pandemic. It found a rise in inequality during lockdown months, which gradually weakened following the reopening of the economy. The effect was especially pronounced among immigrants and in regions more dependent on sectors that were heavily affected by the restrictions put in place to limit the spread of the virus, such as tourism. Government transfers and furlough schemes were very effective in mitigating the rise in inequality, and at providing a much-needed safety net to the most affected segments of the population.

Gender Pay and Pension Gaps

Summary

The gender pay gap describes a difference in mean or median earnings between women and men. Ample evidence, spanning several decades, has clearly shown that women are systematically paid less than men (Arulampalam et al., 2007; Fortin, 2005; Rubery, 1992; Rubery et al., 2005). This is despite women's level of education having not only caught up but exceeded that of men's among new graduates. The pay gap is an indicator of deeper social and structural inequalities faced by women in the job market, in accessing benefits, and in advancing their career. Over the life course, the gender pay gap compounds into a much wider gender pension gap (Barigozzi et al., 2021; Burkevica et al., 2015). The gender pay and associated pension gaps remain important social and economic hurdles, which European countries are slowly working toward narrowing. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound effect on the economy of Europe, however the impacts on pay and pension gaps may still be too early to quantify or predict.

Key Points

- Women in the European Union are employed less than men and earn less, despite having on average a higher educational attainment. However, hourly gross earnings remain similar across Europe for the same educational levels. This suggests that the gender pay gap is primarily driven by structural factors, such as women being more likely to work part-time, rather than by differences in hourly wages.
- According to various RAS, public opinions about the gender pay gap and its policy priorities remain divided across Europe, and not all respondents agreed that women were more at economic risk than men in the pandemic.
- The greatest impact on women's income and employment were primarily linked to women's increased caring duties due to offices and schools closing. This increase was steeper among lone parents, but also applied to families with both parents at home.
- Government emergency welfare schemes, such as furlough and increased extraordinary childcare leave, were important to help mitigate the worst effects on incomes.

European-level Insights

The unadjusted gender pay gap, or the mean difference in hourly gross earnings between women and men, was 14% for workers in the EU with the same qualifications in 2019, with little change observed over the last five years (Figure 8). The gap in remuneration remains a substantial problem common to all countries despite various cultural, social, and economic contexts (Leythienne and Ronkowski, 2018). While it remains too early to predict the impact which the pandemic will have on the gender pay gap in Europe, women with low skills or educational attainment are more likely to be employed in precarious or informal working conditions (EIGE, 2017; ILO, 2018), putting them more at risk of losing their job or, in some cases, not being able to access welfare policies made available by governments to mitigate the impacts of the pandemic, which may require specific employment criteria for eligibility (International Labour Organization, 2020).

Figure 8: Unadjusted gender pay gap (GPG) across Europe by year
(% of average gross hourly earnings of male employees)

The unadjusted gender wage gap is the difference between average gross hourly earnings of male paid employees and of female paid employees

Source: Eurostat, online data code: SDG_05_20

Moreover, inequalities in pay increase if we disaggregate them by educational attainment. Figure 9 shows that women with the lowest educational attainment likely fall in some of the most vulnerable social categories during an economic crisis, as their earnings are persistently almost half those of the highest educational level, women and men alike. Across all countries, the greatest gender pay gap between men and women seems to be primarily observed at the highest educational level, but the starkest differences are found between educational attainment levels, regardless of sex. In the European Union (EU27) women with a tertiary education earned on average 40 percentage points more yearly than those with the lowest level of education, and 10 percentage points less than of men with the same educational level.

Figure 9. Mean annual income (in PPS) by sex, country, and educational level in various European countries 2019, most complete data series available

Source: Eurostat, online data code: *ilc_di08*

While the gender pay gap is described through a difference in remunerations, it is driven

by a wide array of social and economic factors, reflected (amongst other things) by an unequal participation in the labour market by women. Fewer hours of paid work are undertaken by women than by men in Europe, due to a mix of a generally higher unemployment rate for women in the labour market (Leythienne and Ronkowski, 2018) and a shorter number of hours worked by women (139 average monthly paid working hours compared to 162 for men), in part due to a higher proportion of women employed in part-time positions (Leythienne and Ronkowski, 2018). Because of the increased caring responsibilities stereotypically attributed to women as prime caretakers of the house and family, the sudden burden of care created by school closures due to the pandemic seems to have fallen more often on women than men, likely pushing more women out of employment and widening both the pay and unemployment gap in Europe (Cook and Grimshaw, 2021; Joint Research Centre (European Commission) et al., 2020). The consequences of the pandemic for the gender care gap are explored in more detail in the following section.

National Insights

In total, 33 RAS were identified as pertaining to the gender pay and pension gaps, however many of these focused on the consequences of the pandemic for women's work and employment situation and did not specifically measure the impact on pay and pensions. These studies are considered in the earlier section on the domains of Economy and Work and Labour Market. Other RAS did focus on the effects of the pandemic on income, but failed to explicitly include gendered analysis or consider gender inequalities. In some countries (e.g. UK) gender pay gap reporting requirements were suspended during the pandemic, which have had consequences for the availability of data. This means that insights are limited for this domain, however, one key RAS from Ireland was identified that focused specifically on the gender pay and pension gaps (IE04).

Common Findings

The effect of the pandemic on women and men's employment rates and hours in work has been complex, changing across the duration of the pandemic and varying by sector and country. However, studies indicate that overall, the effect was stronger for women than men (e.g. ES05, GER03, PL06) and there are fears that this will result in a widening of existing gender pay and pension gaps during and beyond the pandemic (e.g. GER02). Nevertheless, government schemes, such as furlough and childcare leave, were found to be important for mitigating the worst effects on income (ES05, FR09).

Echoing the results of European-level analysis, the gendered impact of the pandemic on income and employment was linked in the RAS to mothers taking on more childcare and home-schooling than fathers (GER02) and women being more likely to work in sectors most affected by the pandemic (BE01). The relationship between gender gaps in care and pay also appears to be reciprocal, with couples' relative income levels providing some (but by no means a full) explanation for gender inequalities in the division of childcare and

home-schooling during the pandemic (GER02).

Specific examples:

- According to an Irish RAS exploring the effect of the pandemic on income (IE04), average wages decreased more among women than men during the first wave of the pandemic, but gender differences were less apparent in subsequent waves. Prior to the pandemic, occupational segregation contributed to the gender income gap, but this study finds that the structure of job and earnings loss during the pandemic has reversed this and women's occupation and industry structure have provided them with an earnings advantage. The RAS also finds that men benefitted more than women from welfare measures, due to higher employment losses and the flat, non-means tested nature of new supports.
- According to a nationally representative RAS from Poland (PL06), men's wages increased more often during the pandemic than women's. Another Polish RAS (PL05) found that, while 28% of mothers in Warsaw earned less than before the pandemic, 13% declared their pensions had increased.
- A longitudinal RAS of UK households (UK04) reported in July 2020 that women who had been placed on furlough had worse projected financial security than furloughed men. Among workers who had ever been furloughed, women were 12 percentage points more likely to believe they would experience difficulty paying their usual bills. However, among workers in general there was no gender difference.
- A French RAS on poverty levels (FR09) found that women and young people were the two groups that were most likely to restrict the amount and quality of food they eat as a result of income loss.

Gender+ Dimensions

Parental status appears to be an important factor for the consequences of the pandemic on the gender pay gap. Women with children were found to be the most affected because of the increased childcare responsibilities that came with school closures (GER02, GER03, HR01). Couple status was also important: in Germany, women living with a partner or spouse were less likely to be working, whereas the opposite was true for single women (GER07). In contrast, a Slovenian RAS (SI05) reports that women were more at risk of poverty if living alone.

Reflecting the observations from European-level data, educational attainment also appears to be important, with higher levels associated with higher levels of income and employment (BE01, HR01). For example, in Germany (GER05), higher educated individuals perceived their financial situation more favourably during the pandemic and were better

able to cope with financial shocks. In Croatia, only 25 percent of women with less than an upper-secondary education were active in the labour market in June 2020 and women with low levels of education and those living in remote rural areas were less likely to be able to economically cope with the lockdown (HR01). Finally, the nature of employment appears important with regards to the consequences of the pandemic, since self-employed individuals reported higher financial and psychological stress (GER05).

Gender Care Gap

Summary

Care work can be broadly defined as the activity of providing personal services to meet the physical, psychological, emotional needs of one or more other persons (EIGE, 2021a; ILO, 2007). Care recipients can be both adults and children, frail or able-bodied. Those who are generally identified as more in need are new-borns, babies, school-age children, sick people, those with a disability, and the elderly (ILO, 2007). Care work comprises two overlapping activities: direct care activities (e.g. feeding a baby) and indirect care activities (e.g. cooking, cleaning) (ILO, 2018). Care work can be done visibly – institutionalised as paid employment – or invisibly, in the home (ILO, 2007). Our attention focuses on the latter, given that the visibility of unpaid care work performed in the home increased exponentially during the pandemic crisis (Rubery and Tavora, 2020). Care and childbearing are two of the major constraints to women’s participation in the labour market. Even when women do not have children – whether by choice or not – they are still affected by caring expectations linked to gender stereotypes. Working mothers suffer from the so-called ‘motherhood penalty’, namely their hourly remuneration is lower than non-mothers (Budig and England, 2001). While childcare policies in some countries have tried to even the work between both partners, the responsibility for care remains deeply unbalanced towards women and policies tend to assume that children are born within a two-parent heterosexual family unit.

Key Points

- There appears to be a link between the burden of childcare and a decrease in working hours during the pandemic. In most of the countries mapped here, a higher share of working women living with children under 18 reported that their working hours had decreased substantially, compared to working women without dependent children, and compared to men living with children of the same age.
- Across all European countries, even before the pandemic, there was a higher share of women who opted working part-time because they needed to care for children or adults requiring care.
- Further research should investigate whether increased teleworking among fathers has had positive effects on norms and gendered division of labour. National level RAS showed that fathers increased their contribution to childcare during the pandemic as a result of working from home.
- Governments should focus more on the needs of working mothers as they appear to be the most affected group of workers. Many of the reviewed RAS indicated that women took on the majority of care responsibilities and were particularly

burdened with home-schooling. The burden of childcare seems to be associated with negative consequences on women's performance at work, work-life balance and mental health.

European-level Insights

Despite observing a reduction of the gender gap in time spent on care since 2005, women and men are still far from sharing unpaid work equally, given that men have not taken on care work in the home to the same extent as women have moved into the labour market (EIGE, 2021a). The 'stay-at-home' COVID-19 policies, which imposed or strongly recommended telework along with school and nursery closures, have increased the unpaid workload for households (Adams-Prassl et al., 2020; Del Boca et al., 2020, 2020; Rubery and Tavora, 2020; Sevilla and Smith, 2020). Currently, there are no comparable data at the European level on time spent on housework and childcare pre- and post-pandemic, however the analysis of national RAS that follows indicates that women have taken up more of the additional unpaid work and childcare than men, thus exacerbating existing gender inequalities.

The increased burden of childcare also appears to have consequences for paid working hours. In Figure 10 we observe that women were more likely to report that their hours had decreased substantially between April and June 2020 in most of the EU27 countries⁴. Greater differences are seen when we compare working women and working men with children under 18 living in the household, although the presence of children does not *per se* explain gender differences, and the country context might play a more crucial role. For example, working women with children under 18 in Belgium, Estonia, Finland, or Poland, reported that their working hours have decreased significantly compared to men with co-habiting children of the same age.

Decreased working hours may take the form of part-time working. Women and men work part-time for different reasons, not least because of care responsibilities (Figure 11). Across Europe, there is a higher share of women who opt for working part-time because they need to care for dependent adults or children, with little change between 2018 and 2020.

A steep rise in home working during the pandemic is likely to have increased the opportunities for fathers to be involved in childcare, with possible lasting effects on norms and gender division of labour (Alon et al., 2020; Andrew et al., 2020). Men's increased exposure to the domestic sphere could lead to more egalitarian attitudes, however there

⁴ The question was part of both Round 1 (April-June 2020) and Round 2 (June-July 2020) of the online survey *Living, working and Covid-19* of Eurofound (here in Figure 10 only the results from Round 1 are reported). The question asked whether during the COVID-19 pandemic respondent's working hours have changed (5-item scale from 'decreased a lot' to 'increased a lot').

could also be a shift towards more traditional attitudes as a result of women reducing engagement with paid work to take on an increased childcare load (Reichelt et al., 2021).

Figure 10. Percentage of employees and self-employed who have reported that working hours have decreased a lot by sex and presence of children in the household, 2020

Source: Living, working and COVID-19 dataset, Eurofound – Round 1

Figure 11. Percentage of part-time workers reporting that caring for adults or children is the main reason for part-time employment
2018-2020, age group 15-64

Source: Eurostat Labour Force Survey, online data code: LFSA_EPGAR

National Insights

In total, 87 RAS were identified that pertained to this domain in some way. Among them, nine key RAS focused specifically on the gender care gap (GER09, HU03, IE06, IS02, IT10, NL02, SK02, TR05, UK09). Others included analysis on the gender care gap but did not have it as the primary focus (e.g. AT01, ES02, CZ02), while some focused specifically on the effects of the pandemic on family life but failed to explicitly include gendered analysis or consider the care gap (e.g. FI06, FI07, IT06, LV02, LV09).

Common Findings

The RAS indicated that care responsibilities increased during the pandemic due to school closures and the loss of formal and informal support, such as support services for disabled people, homecare for older adults and childcare offered by grandparents and friends (IE06, LV02). Many RAS show that fathers increased their contribution to childcare during the pandemic as a result of working from home, which led to greater flexibility in work hours and reduced commute times (e.g. ES02, GER03, HU03, IS02, LU01, NL02, TR05, TR06). However, the RAS overwhelmingly indicate that women took on the majority of care responsibilities and were particularly burdened with home-schooling.

The greater time spent on caring for dependent children and older adults by women during the pandemic (gender care gap) and a lack of associated support appear to have

had negative consequences for women's performance at work (ES02), time for recreation (AT01, NL02), work-life balance (CZ02, ES10), income (CZ02, GER02), and possibilities of accepting a job (ES10). There have also been consequences for women's wellbeing. Studies find that the pandemic had a greater impact on women's mental health than men's (RO01, CZ02, SK01) and that, compared to men, women felt more overwhelmed, exhausted and stressed (AT01, GER09, GER11) and less satisfied with work, family life and life in general (GER03). Several studies suggest that women's poorer mental health outcomes are directly linked to the gender care gap and mothers in particular were found to suffer (CZ02).

Specific examples:

- In a Czech study on the effects of the pandemic on mental health, (CZ02), it was reported that women more often than men switched to *ošetřovné* (a care allowance leave) during the pandemic to look after a family member. For example, in mid-April 2020, 20% of working women with children under 18 said they had spent some time on the care allowance leave during the past month, compared to only 8% of men. This was a longitudinal RAS analysing the mental health of respondents at regular intervals in the pandemic compared to a pre-pandemic baseline.
- According to a RAS from France examining housing issues (FR01), 39% of women share their workspace with their children or other household members, compared to 24% of men.
- A Hungarian RAS exploring the gendered division of childcare and work (HU03) found that, on average, men have increased their contributions to childcare at roughly the same rate as women (35%). However, given that women had been doing considerably more childcare before the pandemic, in absolute terms, women's contributions grew significantly more than men's and the gap between women and men increased in absolute terms.
- A longitudinal panel study organised by three Dutch universities with households in the Netherlands (NL02) found that the proportion of fathers reporting greater involvement in childcare increased between April (22%) and June 2020 (31%), however by September of the same year it had decreased to 23% and in November it reduced further still (18%).
- However, data from Poland in a nationwide, representative sample (PL06) indicates that caution should be taken when findings rely on respondents' self-reports of care divisions since men more often than women reported that the involvement of both parents in distance learning was equal, while women were more likely to report that they did a larger share of home-schooling. The same observation was made concerning respondents' opinions on divisions of childcare.

Gender+ Dimensions

A number of RAS pointed to additional childcare and home-schooling responsibilities being more of a struggle for single-parent families, families with several children, families on low income and families where parents had lower levels of education (e.g. AT08, GER02, CZ07, IE06). Some RAS (e.g. HR01) indicated that less-educated women were disproportionately hit by the unequal division of household chores and faced mutually reinforcing barriers (low labour force participation, limited social protection coverage, and more stringent traditional gender norms). However, contrasting findings were observed in research from Hungary (HU03), which found that a gender care gap was particularly observed among middle class, highly educated city-dwelling women. Analysis on intersections between the gender care gap and inequalities relating to race/ethnicity, nationality, sexuality and gender identity were not reflected in the RAS.

Gender-based Violence

Summary

Gender-based violence is defined as violence directed against a person (or persons) because of their gender, or violence that affects persons of a particular gender disproportionately (European Commission, 2021c). The term 'gender-based violence' (and its abbreviation GBV) is used to capture all forms of violence - physical, sexual, psychological, economic - in both online and offline contexts (European Commission, 2021c). In relation to the pandemic, the concern is particularly focused on domestic abuse – also called domestic violence. Domestic violence (DV) is a broad term and usually includes intimate partner violence (IPV), which is defined as “a pattern of behaviour in any relationship that is used to gain or maintain power and control over an intimate partner. Abuse is physical, sexual, emotional, economic or psychological actions or threats of actions that influence another person. This includes any behaviours that frighten, intimidate, terrorize, manipulate, hurt, humiliate, blame, injure, or wound someone” (United Nations, 2021). Domestic violence also includes elder abuse and child abuse (Boserup et al., 2020).

Key Points

- Before the pandemic, one in five women (18-74 years old) living in EU member states who were or had been in a couple relationship, had experienced physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence (IPV).
- IPV against women and girls, including both physical and psychological violence, has reportedly increased globally during the pandemic, as witnessed by a rise in emergency calls in several countries and as reported in some of the RAS analysed.
- Emerging evidence seems to also signal a rise in femicides by an intimate partner in some of the countries most affected by COVID-19.
- Many studies show that women are reluctant to inform others about their experiences of gender-based violence. Some actions have been taken by governments to encourage women to report incidents, however it is still unknown whether these actions have brought positive consequences. More research is needed on the effects of initiatives to increase rates of gender-based violence reporting.

European-level Insights

According to the 2012 EU FRA survey on Gender-Based Violence Against Women, among women aged 18-74 years old living in the EU member states who have been involved in a couple relationship, one in five has experienced physical and/or sexual intimate partner violence (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2014). Almost everywhere in Europe, people think that domestic violence – both physical and psychological – is a

serious issue (Figure 13). Yet, across countries a non-negligible proportion of the population do not hold this view. Psychological violence, in particular, is less likely to be regarded as a very serious issue. A gender difference is also noted, with women across Europe more likely than men to regard violence against women as a very serious issue.

Figure 13. Share of respondents thinking that domestic violence against women is a very serious issue across Europe by sex, 2010

Data are obtained from EIGE

Source: Eurobarometer 73.2

Gender-based violence has been found to increase during periods of crisis, and this appears to be the case during the COVID-19 pandemic (Bradbury-Jones and Isham, 2020; European Commission, 2020a; Mittal and Singh, 2020). In the midst of measures confining people to their homes to avoid the spread of the virus, violence against women has been a particular area of concern and an increase in violence against women and girls has been reported (Bradbury-Jones and Isham, 2020; Mittal and Singh, 2020). According to a UN Women report, since March 2020 the increase in incidents of domestic violence in France was 30% and in Cyprus, a 30% increase in calls to helplines was observed in the week after the first confirmed case of COVID-19 on the island (Graham-Harrison et al., 2020; UN Women, 2020). As a result, issues around gender-based violence have gained more visibility in public debates, although greater awareness is still needed and data allowing a comparison of rates of gender-based violence before and after the beginning of the pandemic is limited (Shreeves and Prpic, 2020).

Despite a lack of data, analysis suggests that lockdowns have prevented women from 'escaping' their perpetrators, accessing support services, or making calls to emergency services because the abusive partner is likely to always be at home or in the room (EIGE, 2020; Fielding, 2020; June and Morgan, 2020). An additional problem created by the pandemic is that victims of violence might refuse to go to hospital because they are concerned about the risk of infection with COVID-19 (Fielding, 2020). Given the economic consequences of the pandemic already outlined in this report, women may also be more financially dependent on their partners, further constraining their ability to leave an abusive situation (Mittal and Singh, 2020). Increased financial stress and work-related problems may also contribute to increased cases of intimate partner violence since difficulty coping with multiple pressures and resulting substance abuse are risk factors for abusive behaviour towards family members (Capaldi et al., 2012; Fielding, 2020; Piquero et al., 2020).

There are concerns that other forms of violence will increase in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2019, the International Labour Conference adopted the ILO Violence and Harassment Convention No. 190, providing a plan for the prevention of violence and harassment in the world of work (ILO, 2020). The Convention is important for the COVID-19 response and recovery because, among other things, it helps to protect everyone in and beyond the physical workplace, to prevent GBV and harassment, to lessen the impact of domestic violence on the world of work, to prevent and address cyberbullying (which might arise as a consequence of the increased teleworking arrangements) and to protect those who are more at risk of violence in certain occupation sectors (ILO, 2020). In response to concerns about a rise in cases of violence during the pandemic, many governments have tried to take actions to counteract this phenomenon (Mittal and Singh, 2020). For instance, France and Spain have adopted a system whereby women can report to the local pharmacy if they are victims of domestic violence, so that the pharmacist can inform the police (Guenfoud, 2020). More research is needed to collect cross-national data on gender-based violence – in all its forms, for instance on online violence – and on femicides during the pandemic.

National Insights

Out of the 291 mapped RAS, a total of 43 were identified as covering the domain of gender-based violence (GBV) in some respect. The majority of RAS that explore the domain of gender-based violence do not explore the topic as their central focus, but rather engage with broader topics such as the overall experience of women during the pandemic, psychological and behavioural aspects of the crisis and the effects of COVID-19 upon vulnerable members of the population, such as women with disabilities or those with caring responsibilities. More often, the surveys targeted the general population with only 13 out of the 43 surveys having gender-based violence as their central focus (AT04, BE04, ES08, FR02, GER10, IE03, LT08, LV01, PT06, SER10, SI01, SK07, TR03).

Common Findings

In alignment with the European-level data, the RAS analysed for this report were also found to corroborate concerns that gender-based violence would increase during the COVID-19 pandemic. Violence was found to be especially significant if women were in quarantine; the family was struggling financially; one of the partners had employment difficulties; or family members suffered anxiety or depression. Some studies however show a mixed picture as different effects were felt in different waves of the pandemic. A Spanish study on violence and COVID-19 (ES08) from the University of Zaragoza found that, while the number of women killed decreased during the first pandemic wave, the number of femicides subsequently increased, with 17 women killed from July to October 2020.

In terms of help seeking, many studies showed that women would not inform anyone of their experiences of gender-based violence. Additionally, a Belgian study (BE04) noted that victims would rather seek psychological care from their GPs rather than seek assistance from the police, meaning they may receive less support and access to resources. Studies that explored the availability and provision of services for those experiencing gender-based violence (IE03, SK07, SER10) demonstrated that due to the increased need for assistance, pressure was placed upon shelters and charitable organisations that far exceeded their capability. This was explained by various reasons including a lack of funding; COVID-19 restrictions meaning those in need could not access services; reduced availability of shelters for their protection; and difficulties in retaining and supporting staff. The reliance of most services on external funding significantly undermined the resilience of these organisations to sudden crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. This meant that these organisations are likely to continue to suffer post-pandemic, as they will be left without reserve funds.

Specific examples:

- A German representative online survey with households across the country (GER10) explored the impact of the pandemic on violence against women and children and reported that 3.1% of women had experienced at least one physical conflict, 3.8% felt threatened by their partner and 2.2% were not allowed to leave the home without permission from their partner.
- According to a Turkish RAS exploring violence against women and children during lockdown (TR03), 23.7% of respondents reported that they had experienced psychological violence, 10.3% economic violence, 4.8% digital violence, 1.7% physical violence, 1.4% sexual violence, and 1.1% stalking. In total, 32% of respondents said they were not aware of emergency help and report lines to report incidences of violence, suggesting the issue is likely much worse than reported.
- According to a French study administered by the NGO Fédération Nationale Solidarité Femmes on marital violence (FR02), one in ten women experienced domestic violence during the first lockdown and a third of these were new cases.

Half of respondents who reported to have experienced violence expressed that they would not tell a relative and only one in ten intended to file a complaint.

- The Slovakian survey on 'Mapping of needs of women surviving intimate partner violence (IPV) during the pandemic' (SK07) engaged with service providers and reported an increase in the number of women surviving intimate partner violence that contacted services for assistance. This increase in demand coincided with limited accessibility to shelter services due to the unavailability of free testing, a requirement for admission.
- A Slovenian RAS on COVID-19 and wellbeing (SI03) found that while almost 90% of respondents agreed that domestic violence is not discussed enough, 34.7% of men and 18% of women did not agree with the statement that violence is the sole responsibility of the perpetrator. They also found that 30% of respondents think that women should calm conflicts, situations and relations in the time of crisis instead of exposing their own problems while 15% of women stated that COVID-19 further increased their dependence on their partner.

Gender+ Dimensions

The RAS that explored gender-based violence engaged with a variety of other socio-demographic characteristics, including disability, LGBTQ+ identities and socioeconomic background. The findings illustrate how multiple vulnerabilities intersect to compound risk factors during the pandemic.

Specific examples:

- Austrian analysis from the Ministry of the Interior on domestic violence (AT04) found that reports to the police during March/April 2020 increased more in larger cities (26%) compared to Jan/Feb 2020 than in less densely populated areas (9%). This study combined survey analysis with data from the Federal Criminal Police Office.
- A Turkish study exploring rights violations of disabled Turkish women during COVID-19 (TR01) found that 33.4% of women with disabilities were exposed to violence prior to the pandemic but this rose to 39.6% during the pandemic. Specifically, these women were exposed to physical, verbal and financial violence.
- A longitudinal Irish survey of LGBTQ+ youth (IE07), found that nearly all respondents (97%) had struggled with mental health issues and felt confined to an unsupportive home environment in which they may experience violence during the pandemic.
- A Spanish study on violence against women and LGBTQI+ individuals during COVID-19 (ES08) reported that 43.2% of the total number of active cases of gender-based violence registered by the police in September 2020 (1,583 cases) corresponded to victims born abroad, showing that nationality and migration may have an impact on gender-based violence that needs to be further explored.

- The VD@COVID19 study undertaken by Higher Education Institutions in Portugal and the Netherlands on the topic of domestic violence (PT06) explored the educational and economic backgrounds of participants, and demonstrated that incidents of domestic violence were prevalent among younger and less qualified women. However, many new cases were from people with high education and no economic problems, suggesting that issues of gender-based rose among all sectors of society during the pandemic.

Decision-Making and Politics

Summary

Women are underrepresented within decision-making processes and in leading positions, be it in politics, government agencies, the judicial system or on company boards. This was recognised in the Beijing Platform for Action (in 1995) as one of the areas of concern for women's advancement. During the pandemic, while many women have been working mainly behind the scenes – as nurses, medical doctors and so on – the public domain is disproportionately occupied by men, who are responsible for the important decisions affecting citizens' everyday lives (EIGE, 2020). This imbalanced situation implies that women are excluded from shaping the decisions affecting their own lives (EIGE, 2020). Experience from past outbreaks shows that it is important to integrate a gender analysis into preparedness and response efforts, to promote gender and health equity goals as well as to improve the effectiveness of health interventions (Wenham et al., 2020).

Key Points

- In the second quarter of 2020, women were underrepresented in the European Parliament and among the members of the European Committees of all EU countries (except for Finland, France and Sweden).
- Likewise, there is an underrepresentation of women at the regional and municipal level across all European countries.
- Results from the reviewed RAS regarding individual decision-making indicate that respondents may be losing trust in government and mass media as sources of information on the virus.
- An important issue that governments should address in the near future is to include women and representatives from other vulnerable communities (such as the LGBTQ+ community) in decision-making bodies for COVID-19 response. These groups should be valued as an important resource to encourage more innovative and appropriate solutions to global challenges.

European-level Insights

Across the countries of the European Union, women are underrepresented in decision-making positions, both in political and economic institutions. For instance, within the labour market, women are underrepresented in management and in senior positions in many fields, although they constituted more than half (57.6%) of all graduates in 2015 within the EU-28 (EPP Group in the European Parliament, 2019).

Underrepresentation is an issue throughout the institutions and bodies of the EU, both at local and at higher levels of decision making. According to the United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women, women's political participation is an

essential prerequisite for gender equality and genuine democracy (Apap et al., 2019). In countries where special measures apply, such as quotas, women’s representation in parliaments has significantly increased (Apap et al., 2019). During the second quarter of 2020 – at the time of the beginning of pandemic – the proportion of members in the European Parliament who were women was below 50% in the majority of countries (Figure 17). For Denmark, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta and Slovenia, women constituted the half of the parliamentarians. Only for two countries – Finland and Sweden – women were more than 50% of the parliamentarians.

Figure 17. Members of the European Parliament (2020Q2).

Source: EIGE

In the same period (second quarter of 2020), the share of women in the European Commission was 44.4 (EIGE, 2021b). Looking at the composition of specific bodies, women are generally underrepresented both in the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC) and in the Committee of the Regions (CoR) (Figure 18). While the former represents the various economic and social components of organised civil society, and enables the represented organisations to participate in the Community decision-making process, the CoR is the political assembly providing local and regional authorities with a voice at the centre of the European Union (EIGE, 2021c). The CoR can be consulted by the European Commission, Council and the Parliament, if they see relevant regional or local implications to a proposal (EIGE, 2021c). In all but two countries (France and Sweden), men are greatly over-represented in both the EESC and the CoR.

Figure 18. Distribution of the members of the European Committees across Europe by sex, 2021Q2.

Source: EIGE

At regional and municipal levels of decision-making, women are also underrepresented (Figures 19 and 20), although there are examples of a higher share of women executives (e.g. regional executives in France and the UK).

Pandemic policy responses have been developed by decision-making and advisory committees dominated by men in most European countries (Cibin et al., 2021). According to data from Operation 50/50 compiled by Women in Global Health, women make up only 20% of the WHO Emergency Committee on COVID-19, while they represent 70% of the global health workforce on the frontline fighting the pandemic (Women in Global Health, 2021). Despite women’s underrepresentation at every level of decision-making processes, public health metrics measuring the spread of the virus seem to have been more positive worldwide in countries led by women compared to countries with leaders who are men (Purkayastha et al., 2020). Although it is not possible to claim a causal relationship between the two phenomena, it has been proposed that including women in decision-making bodies for COVID-19 responses – together with representatives from other vulnerable communities, such as low and middle-income countries and the LGBTQ+ community – will help to limit groupthink, stimulate problem solving and encourage more innovative and appropriate solutions to global challenges (Bali et al., 2020).

Figure 19. Distribution of the members of the regional executives across Europe by sex, 2021.

Source: EIGE

Figure 20. Distribution of the members of the municipal council (or equivalent) across Europe by sex, 2020

Source: EIGE

National Insights

Out of the 291 RAS, 34 RAS were identified as falling within the domain of decision making. These RAS focused on individuals' decision making in relation to social, economic and political consequences of the pandemic. For example, studies looked at the degree to which individuals adhered to COVID-19 restrictions and took up the vaccine. Some RAS explored the degree to which the general public had trust in the government and key institutions such as emergency services, healthcare and the military, and the degree to which this affected individual behaviour. However further links were not made between this individual-level decision making and wider political discussions or the role of women within the decision-making space. Only 12 out of the 34 surveys had decision making and politics as their central focus (CY09, EE01, EE10, FI02, GER04, IS01, IS03, IS06, IS08, LT03, PT02, SI07). Of these 12, only two RAS explicitly explored gendered inequalities (GER04, SI07).

Common Findings

The findings regarding trust in government and politics were mixed, likely reflecting the diverse nature and success of national COVID-19 policy responses. For example, a study (CY09) on psychological resilience, hope and adaptability in Greek and Cypriot society found that, although people complied with social isolation restrictions, they did not trust relevant state policies. Studies from Iceland noted more positive results, with one (IS06) finding that nine out of ten respondents trusted public defence and health authorities and two out of three trusted media coverage. Another (IS08) found that almost all respondents trusted the Director of Health, the Chief Epidemiologist and the Chief Superintendent of the Civil Defence. Many studies identified that their participants were moving away from government and mass media sources as a means to attain information on the virus. Respondents in a Cypriot study (CY09) were found to rely on sources other than mass media for pandemic information and an Estonian study (EE01) reported that 69% of respondents found information about COVID-19 on the internet.

In regards to gender, RAS indicated that expert advice tended to come from men. A German study exploring the gender distribution in COVID-19 media reporting (GER04) found that 94% of interviewees on the topic of epidemiology or infection research were men and representations of female medical experts in the media were limited, particularly in comparison to the representation of women with other forms of expertise such as education or in other forms of media such as talk shows.

Gender+ Dimensions

Very few intersectional aspects were considered within the RAS addressing decision making and politics. Many studies did not control for demographics of participants and therefore did not report how views differentiated by gender, age, socioeconomic status etc. Age was considered in some of the studies alongside gender, with a longitudinal Icelandic study (IS01) finding that women were more worried about the pandemic than

men and this was especially pronounced in the oldest age group (60+ years). A Portuguese study on the social impact of the pandemic (PT02) found that the younger the respondents, the lower the percentage of people that had confidence in the pandemic response. This study also found that difficulties with dealing with restrictions were most prevalent among women and those aged 16-24 years old. One study from Estonia (EE10) investigated the experiences of Russian speaking people during the pandemic, exploring how nationality and language barriers affected adherence to coronavirus restrictions.

Human Rights

Summary

According to the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action (see Table 1), fundamental human rights include non-discrimination; dignity; justice and equality; work and education; access to health; privacy and data protection, access to digital technologies. Within RESISTIRÉ, and this first research cycle in particular, the areas of health and education are given priority. Rights to healthcare and education were put under particular stress throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting and exacerbating inequalities that existed prior to the crisis. Access to education was clearly impacted by widespread closures to institutions such as schools, nurseries, universities and libraries. The public health emergency has strained hospitals, reduced the availability of healthcare workers and resulted in the deferral of non-urgent care (OECD, 2021b). Furthermore, although most countries in Europe have achieved some form of universal health coverage, there are great variations in terms of the type of procedures covered, and the share of expenses waived for citizens. These costs can be significant for people, especially those in the lowest income quintile (European Commission, 2020b).

Key Points

- Europe offers relatively good access to healthcare, but inequalities were persistent prior to the pandemic across socioeconomic status, with those in the lowest income quintile consistently reporting a higher unmet need. Among those with the lowest income levels we also observed the greatest gender gaps in self-reported health.
- The COVID-19 pandemic severely stressed hospitals and healthcare systems around Europe and often forced to postpone most non-urgent care (OECD, 2021b), decreasing access to quality care especially for the most disadvantaged groups.
- Issues around unemployment, uncertainties about the future, and work-life balance have increased during the pandemic. These events can have important impacts on the mental wellbeing of people. The mental health impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the European population is likely underestimated by both a lack of data and an already high unmet need in mental wellbeing support in the region.
- The health and wellbeing of those living outside of the healthcare system, which represent the most vulnerable group with regards to the right to access healthcare, remains largely unobserved, and their unmet need is likely grossly underestimated due to a lack of data.
- The key issues identified from national-level RAS were take-up of vaccinations, mental health and psychosocial support, and issues surrounding education and home-schooling.
- Overall, the RAS indicated that health and wellbeing had declined during the COVID-19 pandemic, aligning with broader findings regarding reduced access to health

services as a result of increased pressure on healthcare systems and the negative consequences of isolation on mental wellbeing.

- When exploring specific factors that affected physical and mental wellbeing, the restrictive measures that were imposed upon education, work and movement outside of the home were found to be significant in negatively impacting upon individuals in the RAS. Financial issues that exacerbated psychological stress were also important

European-level Insights

The domain of human rights covers a breadth of issues too wide to cover comprehensively in this short document. Instead, the European-level analysis of the impact of the pandemic on the domain of human rights opts to focus on access to healthcare. This recognises that the "the highest attainable standard of health [is] a fundamental right of every human being", as included in the WHO Constitution (1946) (World Health Organization and United Nations, 1946), and that access to essential health services ought to be a universal human right rather than the preserve of those able to access or afford it.

The coverage and inclusiveness of a healthcare system can be defined across three aspects: affordability, availability, and use of services (European Commission, 2020b). The overwhelming majority of expenses in health across Europe are funded through general taxation or some form of compulsory health insurance schemes, and few procedures are paid out of pocket or at the time of service (Baeten et al., 2018). While countries across Europe can generally provide an equal access and standard of care for all people (Arts and Gelissen, 2002; EIGE, 2015), health inequalities between countries and across socioeconomic groups are evident, and seem to be related to the inability of systems to protect the most vulnerable groups (European Commission, 2020b; Timon Forster et al., 2018). Good access is dependent on how much governments spend on their healthcare systems (Timon Forster et al., 2018), and research has shown that public health expenditure tends to severely decrease following economic crises (Baeten et al., 2018; Megan Carney and Bayla Ostrach, 2020). In Italy, for example, austerity policies enacted following the 2008 economic crises led to a severe decrease in funding, which ultimately created a less prepared healthcare system for responding to the pandemic (Buzelli and Boyce, 2021). Even if the COVID-19 crisis has centred on the importance of strong and resilient health systems, it is unlikely that governments will respond with an increase in spending in the coming years. Decreased spending inevitably means decreased access, and contributes to a possible increase in the privatisation of healthcare providers (Buzelli and Boyce, 2021; Maarse, 2006). This has the potential of furthering the divide between those who can afford better, more expensive care in private institutions and those that cannot. Public health defunding is a dangerous burden, both on the health of the population and on the governments that need to protect it.

The proportion of citizens reporting unmet medical needs prior to the pandemic remained generally low in the European Union, however eastern European countries reported much

higher rates of unmet need due to cost or distance than countries in western and central Europe (Figure 14). Stark differences are also clear between income groups: respondents in the richest income quintile in almost all countries reported an unmet need that is much lower than those in the poorest income quintile, even in cases where unmet need is close to zero. While no significant differences are reported between women and men, the former report a slightly higher rate of unmet need, but no significant differences are observed.

Figure 14: Percentage of respondents reporting an unmet need for medical examination by sex and income quintile in various European countries 2019, latest and most complete data series available

Source: Eurostat, online data code: HLTH_SILC_08

Disentangling all the factors that affect good health and good care is complex, but self-perceived health can help us understand the overall state of personal wellbeing within each country. Before the pandemic, most respondents in Europe reported a good or very good level of health, although women were less likely to do so than men (Figure 15), a finding in line with previous literature, which has found that women report worse health

regardless of SES, educational level, or ethnicity (Boerma et al., 2016; Caroli and Weber-Baghdigian, 2016; Grosse Frie et al., 2010). Significant differences remained cross-nationally, especially when looking at sex, income, and their intersection. Those with a lower income, especially women, reported markedly worse health than their men counterparts in most countries.

Figure 15: Percentage of female and male respondents reporting “good” or “very good” health in the highest and lowest income quintiles in various European countries 2019, most recent and complete data series available

Source: Eurostat, online data code HLTH_SILC_10

The gender gap in self-reported health presents a recurring problem in the healthcare systems across Europe: while there are many reasons behind these differences, gender stereotypes, social norms, and a male-centred medical practice all contribute to worse wellbeing outcomes for women, rooted deeply within the gender divide that persists in Europe (Caroli and Weber-Baghdigian, 2016; Teunissen et al., 2016).

Access to healthcare tends to decrease during periods of economic recession (Baeten et al., 2018) and, due to the public health emergency which strained hospitals and healthcare

workers, people were less likely to go to the doctor and non-urgent care was deferred (OECD, 2021b). Recent Eurofound (2021) results have already recorded a significant rise in unmet need across all European Union countries both in summer 2020 (Figure 16) and spring 2021. Looking at Figure 16, based on the Eurofound sample from June-July 2020, a much higher percentage of women than men reported a rise in unmet in health care since the start of the pandemic in the EU.

Figure 16. Percentage of respondents reporting an increase in unmet medical needs since the beginning of the pandemic in European Union countries (EU27)

Respondents to the Eurofound survey “Living, working, and COVID-19”: wave 2 (June-July 2020)

Source: Eurofound microdata from Wave 2 of the “Living, working, and COVID-19” European Union survey.

The toll of the pandemic on mental health and wellbeing is still hard to quantify, but its side effects could outlive the emergency (Kontoangelos et al., 2020; Public Health Wales, 2020). There is a notoriously high level of unmet need for mental health support in Europe (Alonso et al., 2007), and this will inevitably increase as a result of the pandemic, especially for the most vulnerable, such as those with a lower socioeconomic status, who are also often suffering the worst mental health outcomes (Eurofound, 2021). Unemployment, uncertainties about the future and work-life balance have become consistently harder to bear, with recent Eurofound results showing an increase in depression across all age groups between summer 2020 and spring 2021, and an increase in the percentage of women feeling tense, lonely, and depressed in the same period (Eurofound, 2021).

Vaccination campaigns against COVID-19 rolled out across Europe in early 2021 and the region did not present particular differences in access, largely due to the provision of free jabs in all countries. As a result, by August 2021, 70% of the adult population in the European Union had been fully vaccinated (European Commission, 2021d). However, data are generally unavailable to assess socioeconomic inequalities in vaccination rates at the European level (Caspi et al., 2021). In England, evidence shows a lower vaccination rate for people with lower SES, poor English proficiency, and non-white ethnicity in the 50 and 70 plus age groups (Office for National Statistics, 2021, 2021). Hesitancy in vaccination was found to be associated with lower socioeconomic status and education in England and Portugal, but results have shown associations in both directions (Murphy et al., 2021; Soares et al., 2021). With most European countries continuing to experience new outbreaks, it is still unclear how access to healthcare will be affected in the future, or if governments will find an effective way of meeting these needs.

National Insights

Human rights was the second largest domain represented across the RAS mapping, covering 158 out of the 291 RAS identified. This is to be expected due to the pandemic affecting key aspects of life such as healthcare, education and work, as well as the increased infringement upon the rights of already vulnerable groups such as migrants, people with disabilities and those from poorer socioeconomic backgrounds. While some studies were very broad in scope and sought to explore experiences of the pandemic through social, economic and political lenses simultaneously in one RAS, all surveys mapped intersected with the domain of human rights in one way or another due to the restrictions imposed on individual lives that affected their education, livelihoods and social interactions. Due to this intersectionality, summarising all the findings from such a large domain would prove to be out of the scope of this document. Therefore, in order to cover as much of this domain as possible, and to reflect the data mapped at national level, this section will touch upon issues related to healthcare and wellbeing, and focus on the impacts of access to education.

Many of the RAS exploring human rights specifically had access to healthcare and experiences of illness as a key focus. There were a total of 75 surveys which explored physical and mental health of individuals during the pandemic, of which 46 specifically focused on mental health, psychological wellbeing and psychosocial support. The majority of RAS exploring human rights and COVID-19 were broad in scope and covered multiple domains, however 25 studies had gender and/or women's experiences as a key focus of their study (ES10, GER10, HR03, IE03, IE06, IT04, IT08, IT09, IT10, NL09, PL05, PL06, PL13, PT06, RO03, RO07, SE01, SE02, SE03, SER06, TR01, TR02, TR03, TR04, TR10).

Common Findings

The key issues identified from the RAS in relation to human rights were take up of vaccinations, mental health and psychosocial support, and issues surrounding education and home-schooling. Several studies examined the degree to which respondents would adhere to restrictions such as mask-wearing and social distancing, and 10 studies examined whether individuals would consider taking up the vaccine (BE03, BE09, BG03, FR05, GER01, HU08, IE02, IT02, LT03, LT10). Some RAS indicated that being a woman was associated with less inclination to get vaccinated against COVID-19 (BE09), and that older age (BE09) and higher levels of education (HU08) were factors that increased the likelihood of being inclined to take the vaccine.

Overall, the RAS indicated that health and wellbeing had declined during the COVID-19 pandemic, aligning with broader findings regarding reduced access to health services as a result of increased pressure on healthcare systems and the negative consequences of isolation on mental wellbeing. In line with European insights on the increase of mental health needs, the RAS reported that mental health deteriorated considerably over the course of the pandemic (BE08, CY04, CY09, CZ02, DK08, DK09, DK10, ES04, FR05, IE02, IS09, IT04, LT05, LT06, PT08, RO10, SI06). When exploring specific factors that affected physical and mental wellbeing, the restrictive measures that were imposed upon education, work and movement outside of the home were found to be significant in negatively impacting upon individuals (BE08, CY07). Financial issues that exacerbated psychological stress were also important (BE08, FR05), especially among those unemployed or with low income (PT08). Some studies specifically focused on how restrictions had increased isolation and loneliness, therefore reducing overall wellbeing both physically and mentally (CY06, CY07, CY08, HR06, NL06). In terms of mediating factors, activity and exercise was found to be a way to improve general mental health (CY06, CY08) with psychological resiliency reported to increase with age and higher educational attainment (CY09).

Gender differences in the effects of the pandemic on mental health were found to be associated with employment. Sectors such as social work (RO08) and healthcare (TR10) – where women are often over-represented – saw a particular deterioration in mental health due to overwhelming work pressure. Women were found in several studies to experience higher levels of anxiety and stress (CY04, CZ02, ES04, IE02, IS09, IT04, PT08, RO10) and insomnia symptoms (CY07).

Specific examples:

- A Lithuanian study of the general population exploring the implications on COVID-19 on human security (LT03) found that 44% of men would get the vaccine if it became available compared to 28% of women.
- A longitudinal RAS from the Czech Republic focusing on the implication of the pandemic on mental health (CZ02) concluded that the effect has been more severe

for women, even though women and men's mental health was on a similar level pre-pandemic.

- According to primary school teachers taking part in a RAS from Slovakia investigating distance education in the school year 2020/21 (SK08), only 81% of students regularly participated in distance education and 10% did not participate at all. The majority of teachers (84.5%) estimated that the students gained less knowledge through distance education and 25% of students needed additional support after the re-opening of schools. During the pandemic, 41% of teachers experienced worsening of their mental health and one third of their physical health.

Gender+ Dimensions

The domain of human rights had numerous RAS that were intersectional in nature and explored how groups with specific vulnerabilities had struggled during the pandemic. For example, gender differences in the effects of the pandemic on mental health were associated with parenthood status. Pregnancy and motherhood were the key focus of several RAS (SE02, PL05, NL09, HR03) that reported an increase in stress and anxiety amongst upcoming and new mothers and the reduction of social and psychological support available to them compared to pre-pandemic times. Furthermore, while the presence or absence of children in the household did not affect men's mental health, it emerged as an important variable when it came to women's mental health (CZ02, FR05). This was linked to the higher demand in child-caring responsibilities following school and nursery closures, which tended to fall on women's shoulders.

The closure of educational establishments also had consequences for the wellbeing of children and young people, with RAS indicating that the most damaging effects on mental health were felt by those under the age of 35 (FR05, IE02, PT08). Findings included observations that children's wellbeing had decreased over the school year 2020/2021 (SK08), that students missed physical interaction with peers and teachers (AT03) and that they had not received sufficient support (FI08). The degree to which children and young people could engage with home-schooling seemed to vary greatly depending on socioeconomic and resource inequalities as well as familial support (AT03, AT11, BG06, CZ01, DK09, FI08, SE04, SI02, SK08). Inequalities in accessing resources, such as WIFI and laptops, associated with financial disadvantage also played a significant role in whether children were able to access education during periods of home-schooling (AT11, BG06, BG08, IE10).

Issues around access to support were identified among LGBTQ+ individuals in numerous studies (TR08, PT08, PL01, IE07) due to a lack of awareness of resources and difficulty connecting to peers for emotional support during periods of lockdown. Respondents also discussed how, due to stay at home measures, they feared an increase in discrimination from family members (IE07, PL01) and their mental health suffered as a result of this

isolation (PL01, PT07). Difficulty accessing support was also identified as an issue for those with disabilities, with studies finding that disabled women's physical health had deteriorated (FR08) and many felt isolated and without support (ES10, TR01). Rights to housing and homelessness were also discussed in two studies (HU08, HR08), finding that conditions had worsened, with many unable to receive vaccines as they could not register for healthcare. Five studies looked at the experiences of migrants, refugees and asylum seekers (UK19, TR09, NL04, IT01, AT06) and reported that their situation had worsened during the pandemic in terms of their socioeconomic disadvantage and mental health.

Specific examples:

- A study from Lithuania (LT09) investigated the effects on the pandemic on education through surveying parents/guardians of schoolchildren and teachers. The study found that girls spent more time on computer screens for learning purposes, while boys spent more screen time on entertainment. Both boys and girls were found to have negative health consequences from home-schooling, however these differed as girls were found to experience headaches whereas boys were more likely to be overweight. Parents also noted a significant reduction in children's emotional state during home-schooling compared to in-person teaching
- A Croatian study among school students from the Department of Psychology at University of Zagreb (HR07) corroborated these gendered differences in the negative effects of home-schooling in both primary and secondary school students, as the mental health of girls was found to be worse than the mental health of boys. The mental health of older children was also found to be worse than the mental health of younger children.
- Two RAS from Sweden exploring the effects of the pandemic on high school students found that half of high school students were worried about the future and many felt lonely and bored (SE04) and girls felt their mood had deteriorated as a result of distance learning more than that of boys (SE01).
- In 10% of schools surveyed in a Bulgarian RAS (BG08), over 75% of students did not have devices to participate in online learning, and many other families could not afford appropriate internet plans to support home-schooling. This study specifically aimed to explore whether distance learning would deepen educational inequalities.
- An Irish study exploring digital inequalities in higher education students (IE10) similarly reported issues with internet coverage, as one in six students came from areas with poor broadband facilities. These students were also more likely to be socioeconomically disadvantaged.

Environmental Justice

Summary

Environmental justice aims for the achievement of a healthy environment for all, as well as equal access to environmental goods and equal protection from environmental harms. This includes within its domain the work and living environment of people (Bell, 2016). Furthermore, we can define environmental inequalities as the unequal distribution of the consequences (positive or negative) of society's interaction with the natural environment (Ganzleben and Kazmierczak, 2020). Linked closely to the previous domain, more recent literature has also expanded the discourse toward equal representation and participation in environmental decision-making (Ganzleben and Kazmierczak, 2020; WHO European Office, 2019, 2010). Housing inequalities represent a significant aspect of environmental injustice within Europe, where important differences still exist between different socioeconomic statuses and different countries (WHO European Office, 2019). The living environment gained particular importance in the daily wellbeing of people during the COVID-19 pandemic, as the public health emergency forced many to work from home or shelter-in-place. In the European Union, 17% of the population lived in an overcrowded dwelling in 2019, 7% were unable to keep their house adequately warm during the winter, and 2% of the population still lacked access to a private flushing toilet in their house (Eurostat, 2021, 2020a). This gives an indication of the difficult environmental conditions in which many entered the pandemic and will have had important consequences for inequalities in experiences of COVID-19 policy responses.

Key Points

- Data from the 2019 EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (SILC) survey showed that overcrowding, a persisting problem in Europe, was much higher for the poorest share of the population in all countries under analysis.
- Single-parent households were more likely to live in inadequate housing in 2019, with mothers representing the share of the population most affected by this problem.
- Non-pharmaceutical interventions, such as national lockdowns and curfews, which have been imposed in the EU/EEA to stop the spread of infection have forced these families to live for a long period of time in confined spaces, which have been more crowded than usual.
- Overcrowding increases the risk of infection and also puts a higher burden on the wellbeing of those who had to transition to teleworking. As a result, working parents in the lowest income quintile have been identified as a particularly high-risk group.
- Short-term solutions to the problems related to the living environment seem complex to develop, but public opinion is strongly favourable to significant

changes in the way which cities are organised, and a majority of polled citizens would not be willing to go back to the pollution levels experienced before the pandemic.

- Better, more granular data is necessary to assess the importance which the environment has on population health as well as the inequalities present, with a particular focus on people's dwellings and their surroundings.

European-level Insights

Environmental justice entails a wide array of factors contributing to the wellbeing and health of people. While emergencies such as the one caused by COVID-19 likely impacted this domain largely, it remains hard to pinpoint these effects independently due to a lack of data. With the implemented stay-at-home orders in many countries over the course of 2020, the living and working environment of people became increasingly important. Housing played a critical role in population health and wellbeing, with those living in inadequate dwellings or working in poor environments disproportionately affected by restrictions, leading to widening inequalities. Overcrowded houses mean closer contact between residents, which may result in several negative outcomes. For example, those working from home might be unable to find an adequate space to work and self-isolation in the event of an infection is more difficult. Welfare policies designed to protect people from devastating outcomes during the crisis had limited means for countering these effects. Housing inequalities are exacerbated across socio-economic status regardless of gender, and can be worsened by rising living costs. Data from 2019 show that in the EU over 11% of city dwellers lived in houses which cost them more than 40% of their disposable income (Eurostat, 2020b).

Figure 21 shows the difference between women and men reporting an inadequate living environment (which is defined as the presence of a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames or floor) in 2019 according to the EU-SILC survey results. Reported poor household conditions present some significant differences when disaggregated by type of household. Single people with no dependent children or adults to take care of report significantly less often an inadequate household than single parents with a dependent child for both women and men. As a result, single parents seemed to be among those most at risk of experiencing adverse effects of the restrictive measures enacted to stop the spread of COVID-19, with knock-on consequences for their children.

Similarly, overcrowding represents another important indicator on the quality of housing, and a significant risk factor for COVID-19 infections. Looking at poverty with reference to median national income, women and men present similar inequalities across Europe, with men having higher overcrowding rates than women in the lower socioeconomic status income bracket (Figure 22). Generally, overcrowding seems to be worryingly prevalent among those at the lower end of the socioeconomic status spectrum, with a significant

gap observable for both women and men. For the transmission dynamics of COVID-19, those living in overcrowded dwellings are at higher risk of family transmission and of negative mental health outcomes: for both sexes and across all countries it is those with the lowest income who suffer from this problem the most.

Figure 21: Percentage of total population living in inadequate dwelling (leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames or floor) among different types of households in Europe 2019, most complete data series available

Source: Eurostat-EU-SILC, online data code: ILC_MDHO01\$DV_424

Figure 22. Percentage of total population living in an overcrowded home in various European countries by sex and socioeconomic status 2019, most complete data series available

Percentage of total population living in an overcrowded dwelling by sex and socioeconomic status
2019, most complete data series available

Source: Eurostat EU-SILC, online data code: ILC_LVHO05A

Especially when living in poor or overcrowded dwellings, green spaces can be an important resource, however the restrictive measures implemented in all countries during the peak of the pandemic have highlighted inequalities in access to gardens and green spaces in densely populated cities. Future policies centred on mobility restriction should take close consideration of the psychological impact of lockdowns and the significant inequalities in access to green spaces within urban settings.

While no literature has yet highlighted the role of public transport in the spread of COVID-19, buses, trains, and trams can be generally thought to be closed spaces, with poor ventilation, and in which close contact is all but inevitable. These are spaces that are therefore considered as high risk for infection of COVID-19 (European Centre for Disease

Control, 2020a, 2020b). There is a general lack of data on the use of public transport across Europe. It can be deduced that private vehicle ownership is associated with higher SES, and therefore that we might observe a difference in exposure to risk of infection on public transport to increase among people of lower SES. However, no observations are available as of now.

While the economic effects of stay-at-home orders have been largely negative, the air quality in Europe significantly improved in this period, as less movement and economic activity reduced exposure to toxic pollutants among the population. Areas surrounding major factories for industries that kept on working during the pandemic will have enjoyed these benefits less, suggesting inequalities in relation to socioeconomic status in exposure to pollution during the pandemic (Chang et al., 2020). However, again, no data are available yet at European level to confirm these hypotheses. The relationship between environmental pollutants and COVID-19 infections remains poorly studied and largely theoretical, with most literature available focusing on observational studies to propose possible relationships (Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union (European Parliament) et al., 2020). While open air transmission of COVID-19 has now been deemed as extremely rare (Bulfone et al., 2021), patterns of pollution across cities could be an appropriate measurement of deprivation and socioeconomic status, which seem to have been more affected by infection rates, as shown by some local and national level studies (Deguen and Kihal-Talantikite, 2021; Marí-Dell’Olmo et al., 2021). Disaggregation of the impacts of environmental injustices at wider European level by sociodemographic indicators, however, remain largely unobserved, with no literature available showing the direct impact which the pandemic might have had on the exposure to pollutants (Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union (European Parliament) et al., 2020).

The crisis created by the pandemic has drawn attention to the severe urban and living inequalities in Europe, and the need to reshape cities around more sustainable models. Across various major urban centres, many respondents to recent polls expressed the need for better mobility policies in their cities, cleaner air, and demand change in the outlook of urban life in the future (Figure 23).

The development of an environmental justice policy agenda in the European Union should be centred, amongst other things, on the prevention and reduction of health risks due to the environment in the whole population but, most importantly, in the socioeconomic groups most affected by them. This aim, in part, is achieved by ensuring equal access to green spaces, a reduction in an exposure to environmental pollutants, and allowing all citizens to make environmentally conscious consumption choices (Ganzleben and Kazmierczak, 2020). The recently set-up European Green Deal identifies these problems as causes of unequal health outcomes (European Commission, 2019). However, levels of access to green areas, exposure to pollution, and availability of recycling schemes are under-researched. To understand the unequal impact of climate change in Europe, more

data are needed that is both representative and disaggregated by factors such as socioeconomic status and education (Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union (European Parliament) et al., 2020; European Environment Agency, 2019; Ganzleben and Kazmierczak, 2020; WHO European Office, 2019).

Figure 23. Response to YouGov Opinion polling in 21 European Cities (percentage of respondents strongly agreeing and strongly disagreeing with selected questions.)
Poll conducted 14-21 May 2020.

Source: YouGov, data obtained and available at: <https://www.transportenvironment.org/publications/no-going-back-european-public-opinion-air-pollution-covid-19-era>

National Insights

In alignment with the limited European-level data on environmental justice, only 12 national RAS were identified as pertaining to this domain. However, few of these focused on the environment in a meaningful way and of these only one included gendered analysis (GR06).

Common Findings

A key finding among these limited RAS was that concern about the environment appears to be more prevalent among women than men. The Global Female Leaders Outlook COVID-19 Special Edition (NL01) identified climate change as a key concern among the 675 female leaders who were surveyed across 52 countries. A RAS from Greece (GR06) with 730 respondents aged over 18 years old and living in urban areas indicates that women were more concerned about their neighbourhoods during the pandemic and moved around in them more. Among all respondents to this survey, concerns about urban space increased, especially as far as the quality of public space, walking conditions, and cycling facilities. However, a longitudinal Austrian RAS (AT05) on renewable energy suggests that positive effects of the pandemic on environmental concern have waned over time. In June 2020, 63% agreed with the statement that they are satisfied with less consumption as a result of the crisis, but in October/November 2020 only 54% agreed.

Gender+ Dimensions

Given the very small number of RAS focusing on this domain, intersectional analysis was extremely limited. One key study on environmental issues from Greece (GR06) did find differences in responses according to age, as well as gender: young people expressed more concern about cycling facilities, while older respondents were more interested in the improvement of public space and walking conditions.

Conclusion

This report has provided an examination of the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19 in Europe via the mapping of quantitative indicators at both cross-national and local levels. This first cycle of collection and analysis has been exploratory in nature, identifying key issues and exploring the state of social and health inequalities at European level. It also sets the baseline for cycles two and three of the project, which will delve deeper into the issues highlighted in this first review and investigate the evolution of inequalities throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. This first cycle of data mapping will also inform our development of a web and mobile app that aims to collect data on circumstances, opinions, attitudes, and behaviours of respondents across different regions and countries in Europe, which will enable us to produce insights into assessing gender+ inequalities in relation to policies responding the COVID-19 pandemic.

The overall findings of this first cycle of European mapping describe a complex picture, where women remain significantly disadvantaged across all domains despite the progress in gender equality made in the last decade. While at first glance some gender differences might seem small, a closer look at disaggregated data shows substantial disparities in the standards of living and in the wellbeing between different socioeconomic groups, which are posed to deteriorate if governments do not ensure that the most vulnerable are adequately protected and cared for.

While evidence provided a clear picture of some aspects of inequalities in Europe, a detailed analysis was not possible for all domains due to data availability. For instance, there was a lack of comparable and harmonised data at a European level to address and quantify the urgent problem of gender-based violence, which is likely to have intensified as a result of the interventions enacted in most countries. Similarly, data on the gender pay gap, decision making and environmental justice remain scarce and only a few, localised observations were found, which could not be extrapolated at a wider European level. Importantly, existing data is particularly limited for the most marginalised groups in society and current analyses rarely extend beyond differences in socioeconomic status, family structure and education. Non-registered workers, migrants, refugees and the homeless are likely to have been severely affected by COVID-19 and related government restrictions, however little evidence is available to assess these implications across the domains of interest. There is an urgent need for European databases to take varied inequality grounds into consideration to better understand the economic, social and environmental impacts of COVID-19 related policies through a gender+ lens. Local rapid assessment surveys, providing fast, research-based assessments, have proved useful for filling some these gaps and offer an insight into issues at national level. However, further data and/or better integration of existing data is needed, especially at a European level.

The pandemic has clearly highlighted and has contributed to exacerbating socioeconomic

and health inequalities, and there is now an opportunity to develop research agendas centred around better understanding these differences and their determinants, as well as creating policies to diminish them. Governments around the world have responded to the economic crisis with welfare policies such as partial universal basic incomes, expanded and less demanding unemployment benefits, and improved maternal and paternal leave (International Labour Organization, 2020). These could potentially set a new standard of welfare state and help narrow the inequalities that have been created over the last two centuries of development. The European Union seems devoted and prepared to build back a fairer, more inclusive, and green economy as demonstrated by the Green Deal and the subsequent Recovery plans presented to the European Commission, which had to include evidence of a spending plan committed to diminishing inequities (European Commission, 2020a, 2020b, 2019) for the budget to be released (NextGeneration EU). Whether countries will be committed to these standards and values remains yet to be seen.

References

- Adams-Prassl, A., Boneva, T., Golin, M., Rauh, C., 2020. Inequality in the impact of the coronavirus shock: Evidence from real time surveys. *Journal of Public Economics* 189, 104245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2020.104245>
- Alon, T., Doepke, M., Olmstead-Rumsey, J., Tertilt, M., 2020. *The Impact of COVID-19 on Gender Equality*.
- Alonso, J., Codony, M., Kovess, V., Angermeyer, M.C., Katz, S.J., Haro, J.M., De Girolamo, G., De Graaf, R., Demyttenaere, K., Vilagut, G., Almansa, J., Lépine, J.P., Brugha, T.S., 2007. Population level of unmet need for mental healthcare in Europe. *Br J Psychiatry* 190, 299–306. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.106.022004>
- Andrew, A., Cattan, S., Dias, M.C., Farquharson, C., Kraftman, L., Krutikova, S., Phimister, A., Sevilla, A., 2020. *How are mothers and fathers balancing work and family under lockdown?* [WWW Document]. <https://doi.org/10.1920/BN.IFS.2020.BN0290>
- Apap, J., Claros, E., Zamfir, I., 2019. *Women in politics: A global perspective*. European Parliamentary Research Service.
- Arts, W.I.L., Gelissen, J., 2002. Three worlds of welfare capitalism or more? A state-of-the-art report: *Journal of European Social Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952872002012002114>
- Arulampalam, W., Booth, A.L., Bryan, M.L., 2007. Is There a Glass Ceiling over Europe? Exploring the Gender Pay Gap across the Wage Distribution. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review* 60, 163–186.
- Baeten, Slavina Spasova, Bart Vanhercke, Stéphanie Coster, 2018. *Inequalities in access to healthcare - A study of national policies (No. 1)*. European Commission, Brussels, Belgium.
- Bali, S., Dhatt, R., Lal, A., Jama, A., Daalen, K.V., Sridhar, D., 2020. Off the back burner: diverse and gender-inclusive decision-making for COVID-19 response and recovery. *BMJ Global Health* 5, e002595. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-002595>
- Bambra, C., Riordan, R., Ford, J., Matthews, F., 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic and health inequalities. *J Epidemiol Community Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2020-214401>
- Barigozzi, F., Cremer, H., Lozachmeur, J.-M., 2021. *Gender Wage and Longevity Gaps and the Design of Retirement Systems* (IZA Discussion Paper No. 14394). Institute of Labor Economics (IZA).
- Bell, K., 2016. Bread and Roses: A Gender Perspective on Environmental Justice and Public Health. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13101005>
- Biletta, Isabella, Mullan, Jack, Parent-Thirion, Agnès, Wilkens, Mathijn, 2018. *Women in management: Underrepresented and overstretched?* (No. 1). Eurofund, Luxembourg.
- Boerma, T., Hosseinpoor, A.R., Verdes, E., Chatterji, S., 2016. A global assessment of the

gender gap in self-reported health with survey data from 59 countries. *BMC Public Health* 16, 675. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3352-y>

Bonaccorsi, G., Pierri, F., Cinelli, M., Porcelli, F., Galeazzi, A., Flori, A., Pammolli, F., 2020. Economic and social consequences of human mobility restrictions under COVID-19. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.

Boserup, B., McKenney, M., Elkbuli, A., 2020. Alarming trends in US domestic violence during the COVID-19 pandemic. *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine* 38, 2753–2755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2020.04.077>

Bouziri, H., Smith, D.R.M., Descatha, A., Dab, W., Jean, K., 2020. Working from home in the time of COVID-19: how to best preserve occupational health? *Occup Environ Med* 77, 509–510. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2020-106599>

Bradbury-Jones, C., Isham, L., 2020. The pandemic paradox: The consequences of COVID-19 on domestic violence. *Journal of Clinical Nursing* 29, 2047–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15296>

Brugiavini, A., Buia, R., Simonetti, I., 2021. *Occupation and Working Outcomes During the Coronavirus Pandemic* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. ID 3781534). Social Science Research Network, Rochester, NY. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3781534>

Budig, M.J., England, P., 2001. The Wage Penalty for Motherhood. *American Sociological Review* 66, 204–225. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2657415>

Bulfone, T.C., Malekinejad, M., Rutherford, G.W., Razani, N., 2021. Outdoor Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 and Other Respiratory Viruses: A Systematic Review. *J Infect Dis* 223, 550–561. <https://doi.org/10.1093/infdis/jiaa742>

Burkevica, I., Humbert, A.L., Oetke, N., Paats, M., 2015. *Gender Gap in Pensions in the EU - Research note to the Latvian Presidency*. EIGE, Vilnius.

Buzelli, M.L., Boyce, T., 2021. The Privatization of the Italian National Health System and its Impact on Health Emergency Preparedness and Response: The COVID-19 Case. *Int J Health Serv* 00207314211024900. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207314211024900>

Capaldi, D.M., Knoble, N.B., Shortt, J.W., Kim, H.K., 2012. A Systematic Review of Risk Factors for Intimate Partner Violence. *Partner Abuse* 3, 231–280. <https://doi.org/10.1891/1946-6560.3.2.231>

Caroli, E., Weber-Baghdiguan, L., 2016. Self-reported health and gender: The role of social norms. *Social Science & Medicine* 153, 220–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2016.02.023>

Caspi, G., Dayan, A., Eshal, Y., Liverant-Taub, S., Twig, G., Shalit, U., Lewis, Y., Shina, A., Caspi, O., 2021. Socioeconomic disparities and COVID-19 vaccination acceptance: a nationwide ecologic study. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.05.030>

Chang, S., Pierson, E., Koh, P.W., Gerardin, J., Redbird, B., Grusky, D., Leskovec, J., 2020. Mobility network models of COVID-19 explain inequities and inform reopening. *Nature* 1–

8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2923-3>

Cibin, R., Stöckelová, T., Linková, M., 2021. *RESISTIRE D2.1 - Summary Report mapping cycle 1*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5361042>

Cook, R., Grimshaw, D., 2021. A gendered lens on COVID-19 employment and social policies in Europe. *European Societies* 23, S215–S227. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616696.2020.1822538>

Cumming, C., Wood, L., & Davies, A., 2020. People experiencing homelessness urgently need to be recognised as a high-risk group for COVID-19. *Health Promotion Journal of Australia*. Wiley & Sons Inc.

Davis, S.N., Greenstein, T.N., 2009. Gender Ideology: Components, Predictors, and Consequences. *Annual Review of Sociology* 35, 87–105. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-070308-115920>

Deaton, A., 2013. *The Great Escape: Health, Wealth, and the Origins of Inequality*, 1st ed. Princeton University Press, Princeton.

Deguen, S., Kihal-Talantikite, W., 2021. Geographical Pattern of COVID-19-Related Outcomes over the Pandemic Period in France: A Nationwide Socio-Environmental Study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, 1824. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18041824>

Del Boca, D., Oggero, N., Profeta, P., Rossi, M.C., 2020. *Women's Work, Housework and Childcare, Before and During COVID-19* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. ID 3644817), CESifo Working Paper No. 8403. Munich Society for the Promotion of Economic Research - CESifo GmbH, Munich, Germany.

Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union (European Parliament), Smit, L.A.M., Koopmans, M.P.G., Brunekreef, B., Hoek, G., Downward, G., Forastiere, F., Gehring, U., Vermeulen, R.C.H., Heederik, D.J.J., 2020. *Air pollution and COVID-19: including elements of air pollution in rural areas, indoor air pollution, vulnerability and resilience aspects of our society against respiratory disease, social inequality stemming from air pollution*. Publications Office of the European Union, LU.

EIGE, 2021a. *Gender inequalities in care and consequences for the labour market*. European Institute for Gender Equality, Vilnius.

EIGE, 2021b. *Indicator: European Commission: president and commissioners | Gender Statistics Database* [WWW Document]. European Institute for Gender Equality. URL https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmidm_pol_gov_wmid_ec (accessed 7.30.21).

EIGE, 2021c. *Indicator: [WWW Document]*. European Institute for Gender Equality. URL https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmidm_pol_comm_wmid_eucom/hbar/year:2019-Q2/geo:EU,BE,BG,CZ,DK,DE,EE,IE,EL,ES,FR,HR,IT,CY,LV,LT,LU,HU,MT,NL,AT,PL,PT,RO,SI,SK,FI,SE,UK/sex:M,W/unit:PC/POSITION:MEMB_COMM/EGROUP:EUR_COM/ENTITY:EESC,COR,TOT

EIGE, 2021d. *Covid-19 and gender equality* [WWW Document]. European Institute for Gender Equality. URL <https://eige.europa.eu/topics/health/covid-19-and-gender-equality> (accessed 7.9.21).

EIGE, 2020. *Coronavirus puts women in the frontline* [WWW Document]. European Institute for Gender Equality. URL <https://eige.europa.eu/news/coronavirus-puts-women-frontline> (accessed 6.25.21).

EIGE, 2017. *Gender, skills and precarious work in the EU: Research note*. European Institute for Gender Equality, Vilnius.

EIGE, 2015. *Beijing + 20: The 4th Review of the Implementation of the Beijing Platform for Action in the EU Member States* (No. 4), Beijing + 20. European Institute for Gender Equality, Vilnius.

EPP Group in the European Parliament, 2019. *Social, Economic and Political Empowerment for Women*. European Parliament, Brussels.

Eurofound, 2020. *Living, working and COVID-19 dataset*, Dublin, <http://eurofound.link/covid19data>

Eurofound, 2021. *Living, working and COVID-19 (Update April 2021): Mental health and trust decline across EU as pandemic enters another year* (No. 3), *Living, working and COVID-19*. Eurofound, Brussels, Belgium.

European Centre for Disease Control, 2020a. *Considerations for infection prevention and control measures on public transport in the context of COVID-19* (Technical Report). ECDC, Stockholm, Sweden.

European Centre for Disease Control, 2020b. *Heating, ventilation and air-conditioning systems in the context of COVID-19: first update* (Technical Report), 1. ECDC, Stockholm, Sweden.

European Commission, 2021a. *European Economic Forecast. Summer 2021* (Text No. 4), *European Economic Forecast*. European Commission, Brussels.

European Commission, 2021b. *European Business Cycle Indicators – 2nd Quarter 2021* (Text), EBCI. European Commission, Brussels.

European Commission, 2021c. *What is gender-based violence?* [WWW Document]. European Commission - European Commission. URL https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-based-violence/what-gender-based-violence_en (accessed 9.6.21).

European Commission, 2021d. *Coronavirus: 70% of the EU adult population fully vaccinated*. European Commission - European Commission. URL https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_4362 (accessed 9.2.21).

European Commission, 2021e. *2021 report on gender equality in the EU*. European Commission, Brussels, Belgium.

European Commission, 2020a. *Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee*

of the Regions - A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 (No. COM(2020) 152). European Commission, Brussels.

European Commission, 2020b. *Health at a Glance: Europe 2020 State of the Health in the EU Cycle* (Text), *Health at a Glance*. European Commission, Brussels, Belgium.

European Commission, 2020c. *EU'S NEXT LONG-TERM BUDGET & NextGenerationEU: KEY FACTS AND FIGURES* (Key facts and figures No. 1). European Commission, Brussels, Belgium.

European Commission, 2020d. *Recovery plan for Europe*. European Commission - European Commission. URL https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/recovery-plan-europe_en (accessed 7.20.21).

European Commission, 2019. *The European Green Deal Communication from the Commission to The European Parliament, The European Council, The Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions*, COM(2019) 640 final.

European Environment Agency, 2019. *Unequal exposure and unequal impacts: social vulnerability to air pollution, noise and extreme temperatures in Europe* (Publication No. 22). EEA.

European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2014. *Violence against women: An EU-wide survey*. Main results. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

Eurostat, 2021. *Statistics explained: Living conditions in Europe - housing*. Statistics Explained. URL https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Living_conditions_in_Europe_-_housing (accessed 6.28.21).

Eurostat, 2020a. *Statistics explained: Do you have access to your own indoor flushing toilet?* Statistics Explained. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/edn-20201118-1> (accessed 6.22.21).

Eurostat, 2020b. *Housing in Europe - Is housing affordable?* Housing in Europe. URL <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/digpub/housing/bloc-2b.html?lang=en> (accessed 6.23.21).

Eydoux, A., 2014. *Women during Recessions in France and Germany*. Revue de l'OFCE N° 133, 153–188.

Ferrer, J.N., 2021. *Impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on EU industries*. CEPS, Brussels, Belgium.

Fielding, S., 2020. *In quarantine with an abuser: surge in domestic violence reports linked to coronavirus* [WWW Document]. the Guardian. URL <http://www.theguardian.com/us-news/2020/apr/03/coronavirus-quarantine-abuse-domestic-violence> (accessed 6.25.21).

Fondazione Studi Consulenti del Lavoro, 2020. *Ripartire dalla risorsa donna*.

Fortin, N.M., 2005. Gender Role Attitudes and the Labour-market Outcomes of Women across OECD Countries. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy* 21, 416–438. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/gri024>

Ganzleben, C., Kazmierczak, A., 2020. Leaving no one behind – understanding environmental inequality in Europe. *Environmental Health* 19, 57. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-020-00600-2>

Gerster, J., 2020. *When home isn't safe: How coronavirus puts neighbours on front lines of abuse* [WWW Document]. Global News. URL <https://globalnews.ca/news/6723582/coronavirus-domestic-abuse/> (accessed 6.25.21).

Google, 2020. *COVID-19 Community Mobility Report*. Google.

Graham-Harrison, E., Giuffrida, A., Smith, H., Ford, L., 2020. *Lockdowns around the world bring rise in domestic violence* [WWW Document]. the Guardian. URL <http://www.theguardian.com/society/2020/mar/28/lockdowns-world-rise-domestic-violence> (accessed 9.10.21).

Grosse Frie, K., Eikemo, T.A., von dem Knesebeck, O., 2010. Education and self-reported health care seeking behaviour in European welfare regimes: results from the European Social Survey. *Int J Public Health* 55, 217–220. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-009-0073-3>

Guenfoud, I., 2020. *French women use code words at pharmacies to escape domestic violence during coronavirus lockdown* [WWW Document]. ABC News. URL <https://abcnews.go.com/International/french-women-code-words-pharmacies-escape-domestic-violence/story?id=69954238> (accessed 6.25.21).

ILO, 2020. *ILO Violence and Harassment Convention, 2019 (No. 190): 12 ways it can support the COVID-19 response and recovery* (Publication). ILO, Geneva.

ILO, 2018. *Care work and care jobs for the future of decent work*. International Labour Office, Geneva.

ILO, 2007. *ABC of women workers' rights and gender equality*. International Labour Office, Geneva.

International Labour Organization, 2021. *ILO Monitor: COVID-19 and the world of work*. Seventh edition. Updated estimates and analysis. ILO.

International Labour Organization, 2020. *ILO Social Protection Platform: Social protection Responses to COVID-19 Crisis around the World* [WWW Document]. ILO Social Protection Platform. URL <https://www.social-protection.org/gimi/ShowWiki.action?id=3417> (accessed 6.30.20).

International Labour Organization, 2018. *Global Wage Report 2018/19: What lies behind gender pay gaps* (Report). ILO, Geneva.

Ipsen, C., van Veldhoven, M., Kirchner, K., Hansen, J.P., 2021. Six Key Advantages and Disadvantages of Working from Home in Europe during COVID-19. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, 1826. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18041826>

Joint Research Centre (European Commission), Blaskó, Z., Papadimitriou, E., Manca, A.R., 2020. *How will the COVID-19 crisis affect existing gender divides in Europe?* Publications

Office of the European Union, LU.

June, K., Morgan, T., 2020. *Coronavirus: Domestic abuse calls up 25% since lockdown, charity says*. BBC News.

Kontoangelos, K., Economou, M., Papageorgiou, C., 2020. Mental Health Effects of COVID-19 Pandemia: A Review of Clinical and Psychological Traits. *Psychiatry Investig* 17, 491–505. <https://doi.org/10.30773/pi.2020.0161>

Leythienne, D., Ronkowski, P., 2018. *A decomposition of the unadjusted gender pay gap using Structure of Earnings Survey data*. Eurostat, Luxembourg.

Lewnard, J. A., & Lo, N. C., 2020. Scientific and ethical basis for social-distancing interventions against COVID-19. *The Lancet*. Infectious disease.

Lokot, M. & Avakyan, Y., 2020. Intersectionality as a lens to the COVID-19 pandemic: implications for sexual and reproductive health in development and humanitarian contexts. *Sexual and Reproductive Health Matters*, 28:1.

Lombardo, E., & Kantola, J., 2019. European integration and disintegration: Feminist perspectives on inequalities and social justice. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 57(S1), 62–76.

Lynch, J., 2020. *Regimes of Inequality: The Political Economy of Health and Wealth*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781139051576>

Maarse, H., 2006. The Privatization of Health Care in Europe: An Eight-Country Analysis. *Journal of Health Politics, Policy and Law* 31, 981–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1215/03616878-2006-014>

Mangiavacchi, L., Piccoli, L., Pieroni, L., 2021. Fathers matter: Intrahousehold responsibilities and children's wellbeing during the COVID-19 lockdown in Italy. *Economics & Human Biology* 42, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ehb.2021.101016>

Marí-Dell'Olmo, M., Gotsens, M., Pasarín, M.I., Rodríguez-Sanz, M., Artazcoz, L., Garcia de Olalla, P., Rius, C., Borrell, C., 2021. Socioeconomic Inequalities in COVID-19 in a European Urban Area: Two Waves, Two Patterns. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, 1256. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18031256>

Mazzucato, M., 2018. *The Value of Everything: Making and Taking in the Global Economy*. Penguin UK.

McKee, M., Balabanova, D., Basu, S., Ricciardi, W., Stuckler, D., 2013. Universal Health Coverage: A Quest for All Countries But under Threat in Some. *Value in Health* 16, S39–S45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jval.2012.10.001>

Megan Carney, Bayla Ostrach, 2020. *Austerity, Not COVID-19, Strains National Healthcare Systems*. *Somatosphere*. URL <http://somatosphere.net/2020/austerity.html/> (accessed 8.5.21).

Mittal, S., Singh, T., 2020. Gender-Based Violence During COVID-19 Pandemic: A Mini-Review. *Front. Glob. Womens Health* 1. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2020.00004>

Murphy, J., Vallières, F., Bentall, R.P., Shevlin, M., McBride, O., Hartman, T.K., McKay, R., Bennett, K., Mason, L., Gibson-Miller, J., Levita, L., Martinez, A.P., Stocks, T.V.A., Karatzias, T., Hyland, P., 2021. Psychological characteristics associated with COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy and resistance in Ireland and the United Kingdom. *Nat Commun* 12, 29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20226-9>

Nicola, M., Alsafi, Z., Sohrabi, C., Kerwan, A., Al-Jabir, A., Iosifidis, C. & Agha, R., 2020. The socio-economic implications of the coronavirus and COVID-19 pandemic: a review. *International Journal of Surgery*.

Nouvellet, P., Bhatia, S., Cori, A., Ainslie, K.E.C., Baguelin, M., Bhatt, S., Boonyasiri, A., Brazeau, N.F., Cattarino, L., Cooper, L.V., Coupland, H., Cucunuba, Z.M., Cuomo-Dannenburg, G., Dighe, A., Djaafara, B.A., Dorigatti, I., Eales, O.D., van Elsland, S.L., Nascimento, F.F., FitzJohn, R.G., Gaythorpe, K.A.M., Geidelberg, L., Green, W.D., Hamlet, A., Hauck, K., Hinsley, W., Imai, N., Jeffrey, B., Knock, E., Laydon, D.J., Lees, J.A., Mangal, T., Mellan, T.A., Nedjati-Gilani, G., Parag, K.V., Pons-Salort, M., Ragonnet-Cronin, M., Riley, S., Unwin, H.J.T., Verity, R., Vollmer, M.A.C., Volz, E., Walker, P.G.T., Walters, C.E., Wang, H., Watson, O.J., Whittaker, C., Whittles, L.K., Xi, X., Ferguson, N.M., Donnelly, C.A., 2021. Reduction in mobility and COVID-19 transmission. *Nat Commun* 12, 1090. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21358-2>

OECD, 2021a. *Tackling the mental health impact of the COVID-19 crisis: An integrated, whole-of-society response* (No. 1). OECD, Paris, France.

OECD, 2021b. *Strengthening the frontline: How primary health care helps health systems adapt during the COVID 19 pandemic, OECD Policy Responses to Coronavirus (COVID-19)*. OECD, Paris, France.

OECD, 2020. *OECD Employment Outlook 2020: Worker Security and the COVID-19 Crisis*.

Office for National Statistics, 2021. *Coronavirus and vaccination rates in people aged 50 years and over by socio-demographic characteristic, England (No. 1)*, Health Inequalities. ONS, London, UK.

Petitclerc, A., Côté, S., Doyle, O., Burchinal, M., Herba, C., Zachrisson, H.D., Boivin, M., Tremblay, R.E., Tiemeier, H., Jaddoe, V., Raat, H., 2017. Who uses early childhood education and care services? Comparing socioeconomic selection across five western policy contexts. *International Journal of Child Care and Education Policy* 11, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40723-017-0028-8>

Piquero, A.R., Riddell, J.R., Bishopp, S.A., Narvey, C., Reid, J.A., Piquero, N.L., 2020. Staying Home, Staying Safe? A Short-Term Analysis of COVID-19 on Dallas Domestic Violence. *Am J Crim Just* 45, 601–635. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12103-020-09531-7>

Public Health Wales, 2020. *How are you doing? Public Engagement Survey on Health and Wellbeing during Coronavirus Measures (No. 1)*, How are we doing Wales? Public Health Wales, Wales.

Purkayastha, S., Salvatore, M., Mukherjee, B., 2020. Are women leaders significantly better at controlling the contagion during the COVID-19 pandemic? *J Health Soc Sci* 5, 231–240.

Quaglio, G., Karapiperis, T., Van Woensel, L., Arnold, E., McDaid, D., 2013. Austerity and health in Europe. *Health Policy* 113, 13–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2013.09.005>

Reichelt, M., Makovi, K., Sargsyan, A., 2021. The impact of COVID-19 on gender inequality in the labor market and gender-role attitudes. *European Societies* 23, S228–S245. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616696.2020.1823010>

Rubery, J., 1992. Pay, Gender and the Social Dimension to Europe. *British Journal of Industrial Relations* 30, 605–621. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8543.1992.tb00794.x>

Rubery, J., Grimshaw, D., Figueiredo, H., 2005. How to close the gender pay gap in Europe: towards the gender mainstreaming of pay policy. *Industrial Relations Journal* 36, 184–213. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2338.2005.00353.x>

Rubery, J., Tavora, I., 2020. The Covid-19 crisis and gender equality: risks and opportunities, in: *Social Policy in the European Union: State of Play 2020*. European Trade Union Institute.

Samek Lodovici, M., et al., 2021. *The impact of teleworking and digital work on workers and society*. Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, European Parliament, Luxembourg.

Seguino, S., Braunstein, E., 2019. The Costs of Exclusion: Gender Job Segregation, Structural Change and the Labour Share of Income. *Development and Change* 50, 976–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dech.12462>

Sevilla, A., Smith, S., 2020. Baby steps: the gender division of childcare during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Oxford Review of Economic Policy* 36, S169–S186. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/graa027>

Shreeves, R., Prpic, M., 2020. *Violence against women in the EU - State of play*. European Parliamentary Research Service.

Soares, P., Rocha, J.V., Moniz, M., Gama, A., Laires, P.A., Pedro, A.R., Dias, S., Leite, A., Nunes, C., 2021. Factors Associated with COVID-19 Vaccine Hesitancy. *Vaccines (Basel)* 9, 300. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vaccines9030300>

Stuckler, D., Reeves, A., Loopstra, R., Karanikolos, M., McKee, M., 2017. Austerity and health: the impact in the UK and Europe. *European Journal of Public Health* 27, 18–21. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckx167>

Teunissen, T. a. M., Rotink, M.E., Lagro-Janssen, A.L.M., 2016. Gender differences in quality-of-care experiences during hospital stay: A contribution to patient-centered healthcare for both men and women. *Patient Educ Couns* 99, 631–637. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2015.10.033>

Timon Forster, Alexander Kentikelenis, Clare Bamba, 2018. *Health Inequalities in Europe. Setting the Stage for Progressive Policy Action*. Foundation for European Progressive Studies.

Topriceanu, C.-C., Wong, A., Moon, J.C., Hughes, A.D., Bann, D., Chaturvedi, N., Patalay,

P., Conti, G., Captur, G., 2021. Evaluating access to health and care services during lockdown by the COVID-19 survey in five UK national longitudinal studies. *BMJ Open* 11, e045813. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-045813>

UN Women, 2020. *COVID-19 and ending violence against women and girls*.

United Nations, 2021. *What Is Domestic Abuse?* [WWW Document]. United Nations. URL <https://www.un.org/en/coronavirus/what-is-domestic-abuse> (accessed 6.25.21).

Van Bavel, J. J., Baicker, K., Baggio, P. S., Capraro, V., Cichocka, A., Cikara, M., & Drury, J. , 2020. Using social and behavioural science to support COVID-19 pandemic response. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1-12.

Verloo, M. (2013) Intersectional and cross-movement politics and policies. *Signs* 38(4), 893–915.

Walby, S., 2015. *Crises*. Bristol: Polity Press.

Walby, S., Armstrong, J. & Strid, S., 2012. Intersectionality. Multiple tensions in social theory. *Sociology* 46(2), 224–240.

Walter, L. A., & McGregor, A. J., 2020. Sex-and gender-specific observations and implications for COVID-19. *The Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*. NLM Medline.

Wenham, C., Smith, J., Morgan, R., 2020. COVID-19: the gendered impacts of the outbreak. *The Lancet* 395, 846–848. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30526-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30526-2)

Whitehead, M., Taylor-Robinson, D., Barr, B., 2021. Poverty, health, and covid-19. *BMJ* 372, n376. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n376>

WHO European Office, 2019. *Environmental health inequalities in Europe*. Second assessment report. World Health Organization, Copenhagen.

WHO European Office, 2010. *Social and gender inequalities in environment and health* (No. 2). World Health Organization, Copenhagen.

Women in Global Health, 2021. *OPERATION 50/50: Women’s Perspectives Save Lives* [WWW Document]. *Women in Global Health*. URL <https://www.womeningh.org/operation-50-50> (accessed 7.9.21).

World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe, 2021. *Strengthening population health surveillance: a tool for selecting indicators to signal and monitor the wider effects of the COVID-19 pandemic* (No. WHO/EURO:2021-2297-42052-57877). World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe.

World Health Organization, United Nations, 1946. *World Health Organization Constitution*.

Annex 1 – Pathways and Indicators

In this Annex we provide an overview of the results of the first mapping of quantitative indicators. First, we report the pathways through which COVID-19 has contributed to generate or amplify gender inequalities for each domain. The identification of these pathways is the result of the scoping review that we performed during cycle 1. For each pathway, we indicate whether the impact of COVID-19 on inequalities in that domain has been direct, indirect or unobserved.

The second part of this Annex contains several tables – one for each domain – reporting the indicators of inequalities available at European, national or international levels. For each of the pathways, one or more indicators have been identified. The indicators were primarily at a European or international level, and were complemented by analysis of studies conducted in one or a small sample of countries. Indicators were based on the available data sources (one or more sources, in case the indicator was collected in more than one survey with a similar wording). In the following columns, we reported years of availability (up to the more recent one), available and not available disaggregation based on the available data and/or codebook (i.e., individual characteristics that are relevant to investigate intersections of inequalities), and the link to the webpage where the indicator can be found (if available).

Pathways of inequalities

Pathways for economy/work and labour market domain

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Effects on employment status	Direct effect	Reduction in working hours, drop in employment rates, increased unemployment (especially for those sectors severely hit by the crisis). These consequences are especially felt by particular groups, such as women (more likely to be affected by a change in employment as both consequence of the crisis and their increased caring responsibilities) and/or less educated.
Problematic working conditions	Direct effect	Working conditions might become problematic, both for those who are obliged to work from home and for those who still work at their workplace but with no secure conditions.
Economic consequences	Indirect effect	Especially those in riskier positions (e.g. with informal jobs, on temporary contracts, or with no formal contract), but also those who work in sectors more severely hit (e.g. food service, arts and entertainment), have been affected by income losses and/or financial insecurity.
Human capital loss	Direct effect	Negative impact on career prospects especially for workers with caring responsibilities, and negative effects on productivity.
Development of new skills	Direct effect	Possible positive impacts on the employability of the workers and their skills because of the remote working (e.g. increase in IT skills and more possibilities to follow online trainings).
Health consequences	Direct effect	Those in frontline services have a greater risk of getting infected, especially in workplaces with limited measures or interventions to ensure a secure workplace.
Health consequences	Indirect effect	Workers who experienced job loss, change in working hours, etc. are more likely to report a worsening of health conditions.

Change in gender-role attitudes	Indirect effect	Changing employment conditions and the associated potential increase in time spent at home might influence attitudes towards gender-role and the gendered divisions of tasks.
Stalling of progress in achieving gender equality	Indirect effect	Because of the crisis created by the pandemic, the progress for women's equal treatment in the economy risks being stalled or pushed back. The progress achieved until now will be greatly at risk because of the increased burden of care and work which women have inevitably faced during the pandemic (European Commission, 2021e).
Loss of market bargaining power because of less favourable economic situation after the pandemic	Indirect effect	The interventions enacted to stop the spread of COVID-19 have created a weaker economic situation, which have affected women directly the most due to the sectoral segregation found in the labour market. The service, food, and care sector which will likely suffer the longest effects from the pandemic, employs mostly women, who might have to settle for much lower wages or compete in a scarcer labour market because of the pandemic, with less skilled workers inevitably facing the worst consequences.

<p>A possible economic recession with a slow recovery will affect women the most</p>	<p>Direct effect</p>	<p>The prospects of an economic recession due to the halt to the economic and social life in 2020 are realistic (Ferrer, 2021), with predictions remaining very uncertain of the possible future economic developments. While the rebound of the European economy was better than expected in summer 2021 (European Commission, 2021a), new variants of COVID-19 (most notably the Delta variant which became the dominant strain in most European countries early in the season) will likely hinder the progress achieved so far, with prospects remaining unclear for autumn 2021. The recovery and exit from the pandemic remain unclear (European Commission, 2021a, 2021b), and within the economic crisis created by the public health emergency, women will likely face the longest negative effects, with lower wages, decreased working hours, and less accessible job markets, meaning they will have to rely more heavily on welfare support of governments.</p>
<p>Rebuilding back a fairer economic and social system, eliminating existing social and economic inequalities</p>	<p>Indirect effect</p>	<p>The European Union seems devoted and prepared to build back a fairer, more inclusive, and green economy, centred around the elimination of existing inequities and an unfair economic system. The announced Green Deal (European Commission, 2019), and the subsequent Recovery plans presented to the European Commission for the release of the budget (NextGeneration EU) had to include strong evidence of a spending plan tailored for all parts of society, and committed to diminishing inequities (European Commission, 2020c, 2020d). Whether countries will be committed to these standards and values remains to be seen, however the recent threats of freezing funds issued by the Commission against the policies enacted by the Hungarian government limiting the freedoms of expression which the Union is committed to is a sign that the governments of the EU will find tangible repercussions for governments not committed to improvements.</p>

Pathways for gender pay and pension gaps

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Widening of the gender pay gap	Direct effect	Given the sectoral gender segregation, as well as the general gender pay gap observed at European level, women are expected to experience a greater shock on their average hourly earnings as well as suffer from temporary unemployment due to the interventions enacted at EU/EEA level to stop the spread of COVID-19 (Cook and Grimshaw, 2021).
Women, earning less than men, found themselves in a more precarious situation as a result of the pandemic	Direct effect	Fewer hours of paid work are undertaken by women than by men in Europe, due to a mix of: a) the higher unemployment rate for women in the labour market (which according to the latest available data (2014) was 10.5 percentage points higher for women than for men in the EU) (Leythienne and Ronkowski, 2018), and b) the smaller number of hours worked by women (139 average monthly paid working hours compared to 162 for men), in part due to a higher proportion of women employed in part-time positions (Leythienne and Ronkowski, 2018).
Labour market shock will affect sectors where women are mostly employed in service and hospitality	Indirect effect	Women's employment is increasingly concentrated in service, hospitality, and other sectors severely hit by the pandemic (Cook and Grimshaw, 2021), and will therefore suffer more of the economic consequences of the public health emergency. The International Labour Organization (ILO) observes that, in 2018, 84% of employed women were working in the service sector across Europe, compared to 61% of men (Joint Research Centre (European Commission) et al., 2020).

<p>Increase in part-time or precarious work because of increase in childcare created by the pandemic</p>	<p>Indirect effect</p>	<p>Because of gender stereotypes related to care responsibilities, the increased burden of care created by school closures seems to be falling more often on women than men, likely pushing more women out of employment and widening both the wage and unemployment gap in Europe (Cook and Grimshaw, 2021; Joint Research Centre (European Commission) et al., 2020). These inequalities worsen for women with lower education levels, in more precarious work, or in lower-paid jobs, and those who are less likely to access the welfare policies and employment benefits because of their lower participation in the labour market (Petitclerc et al., 2017; Seguino and Braunstein, 2019).</p>
--	------------------------	--

Pathways for gender care gap

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Increase of care responsibilities for women	Direct effect	Stay-at-home measures and home-schooling increase care workload within the families, both indirect care (e.g. cooking) and direct care (childcare). This workload is likely to disproportionately fall on women - compared to men - and might particularly aggravate the situation of working women. Regarding childcare responsibilities, working women with young children (0-5 y.o.) are more likely to be affected by the crisis (Del Boca et al., 2020).
Difficulties in combining paid work and family duties	Direct effect	For women with paid employment, the increase of care work might have consequences on their labour market position and career (for example, they might take more leave, they are more at risk of job loss). Work-life balance seems to be particularly difficult for women whose partner has continued working outside of the home during the pandemic (Del Boca et al., 2020).
Mental and physical health issues	Indirect effect	Women are overburdened with care work and might experience health problems, for instance stress, depression, etc.
Change in norms and attitudes towards gender division of care	Indirect effect	Due to the increase in recommended or mandatory teleworking, fathers may be more involved in childcare and there might therefore be a change in attitudes towards gender division of care.

Pathways for gender-based violence

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Increased gender-based violence within the household	Direct effect	As a result of the stay-at-home policies, women who are victims of domestic violence are more likely to experience a worsening of their situation, as they cannot leave the house. This can be exacerbated by their economic conditions: if they are not working, they are less likely to escape domestic violence since they may rely financially on their abuser. Women who are part of a marginalized community (e.g., refugees or immigrants) might feel even more isolated when they experience violence (Gerster, 2020). Violence can be physical, sexual, psychological and/or economic.
Psychological violence	Direct effect	Women and men can be victims of psychological violence, both in the context of private life (within the household, and outside) and in the workplace (e.g. harassment).
Increase in homicides	Direct effect	Domestic violence can escalate to homicide, and emerging evidence suggests that during the lockdown homicides within the households have increased.
New forms of gender-based violence	Direct effect	As a consequence of the increased use of technologies and social media, there is a higher risk for everyone to be victim of online violence. This risk might be greater for women coming from poorer backgrounds and/or with less education, as well as for children.
Effects on health	Direct effect	Women who are victims of violence are more likely to suffer from health issues, as a consequence of physical violence. In particular, this might be experienced more by women from a lower socioeconomic status, and older women.
Greater awareness of GBV	Indirect effect	The public may become more aware of the problem, and may therefore change their attitudes towards domestic violence and gender-based violence (more likely that violence becomes less and less acceptable, and there is less victim blaming).

Pathways for human rights

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Decreased access to quality care due to overwhelming of the healthcare system	Direct effect	As the COVID-19 pandemic severely stressed hospitals and healthcare systems around Europe unlike any other modern catastrophe, the provision of non-urgent care was often postponed (OECD, 2021b). Private centres offer continuous care, but at a price that the most disadvantaged usually cannot afford. Single women with lower income, as well as those with lower educational attainment, are generally thought to be the ones with the highest healthcare seeking behaviours (Grosse Frie et al., 2010), and therefore more in need, but with reduced access.
Decreased investments in healthcare could lead to worse healthcare outcomes	Indirect effect	Economic crises notoriously lead to periods of austerity, with governments trying to cut the costliest sectors of public spending. Healthcare often suffers the worst public budget cuts following periods of recessions (Baeten et al., 2018; Quaglio et al., 2013), which threatens the essential goal toward universal health coverage for the whole population (McKee et al., 2013). Inevitably, those that suffer the most from this loss in coverage are those most economically and socially disadvantaged, as private care can always compensate the needs of those who can afford it (Stuckler et al., 2017). Austerity policies can be connected to many of the healthcare failures seen around Europe in the management of the pandemic, with effects which trickle down from the quality of care to worst perceived health outcomes of people (Buzelli and Boyce, 2021; Megan Carney and Bayla Ostrach, 2020).

<p>Rise in unmet need of mental health support largely overlooked during COVID-19 for the least well-off</p>	<p>Direct effect</p>	<p>The mental health and wellbeing toll which the pandemic has had on the European population is still hard to quantify, but its side effects will likely outlive the emergency (Kontoangelos et al., 2020; Public Health Wales, 2020). Mental health support needs remain largely unmet, especially for those with a lower socioeconomic status, who are also often suffering the worst mental health outcomes (Eurofound, 2021). Unemployment, uncertainties about the future, and work-life balance have become consistently harder to bear, with recent Eurofound results showing an increase in depression across all age groups and both sexes between summer 2020 and spring 2021, and an increase in the percentage of women feeling tense, lonely, and depressed in all age groups in the same period (Eurofound, 2021). There is a notoriously high level of mental unmet need in Europe (Alonso et al., 2007), and this crisis will inevitably increase this, especially for the most vulnerable.</p>
<p>Rise in healthcare unmet need</p>	<p>Direct effect</p>	<p>A significant rise in unmet need has already been recorded across all Europe both in summer 2020 and spring 2021 according to Eurofound (Eurofound, 2021). This is likely to reflect an overburdened healthcare system, which had to indefinitely delay much non-urgent care. People who can afford to pay for private, specialized care will likely be able to bypass these delays. This will inevitably widen the gap between socioeconomic status related to both self-perceived health and trust in the healthcare system, directly affecting health inequalities already present across Europe (Lynch, 2020).</p>

Pathways for decision-making and politics

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Imbalanced presence of women and men in decision-making	Direct effect	This imbalance makes more likely that policies aimed to fight the pandemic do not take into account specific needs of women, because they are mainly designed by male-majority governments.
Disadvantages for women	Direct effect	See also the other domains (e.g. economy and work and labour market). The proportion of women employed in the care sector is very high, as well as in other essential jobs in which they have physical contact with others, such as supermarket cashiers. Policymakers should consider these aspects when implementing policies (EIGE, 2021d).

Pathways for environmental justice

Pathways	Direct/indirect/unobserved effect	Impacts
Living environments affect the wellbeing and health of people, who were forced to spend more time at home due lockdowns	Direct effect	The non-pharmaceutical interventions which have been imposed in the EU/EEA have forced families to live for a long period of time in spaces more crowded than usual. Women, systematically required to care for the family more than their male partners, were also faced with an abundance of work due to the increased care of children left at home (Joint Research Centre (European Commission) et al., 2020).
Areas more affected by environmental pollution could expose residents to a higher risk of COVID-19 infection	Indirect effect	The relationship between environmental pollutants and COVID-19 infections remains poorly studied and largely theoretical, with most literature available focusing on ecological designs in order to propose possible relationships (Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union (European Parliament) et al., 2020). While open air transmission of COVID-19 has now been deemed as extremely rare (Bulfone et al., 2021), patterns of pollution across cities could be an appropriate measurement of deprivation and socioeconomic status (SES), which seem to have been more affected by infection rates as shown by some local and national level studies (Deguen and Kihal-Talantikite, 2021; Marí-Dell’Olmo et al., 2021). Disaggregation of the impacts which environmental injustices at wider European level, and disaggregated by social indicators, however, remain largely unobserved, with no literature available showing the differential impact which the pandemic might have had on the exposure to pollutants (Directorate-General for Internal Policies of the Union (European Parliament) et al., 2020).

<p>Changes in exposure to air pollution due to less movement for the stay-at-home orders issued</p>	<p>Indirect effect</p>	<p>Due to the non-pharmaceutical interventions imposed on most of the population of Europe, social and economic life was almost completely halted in the first half of 2020 (Google, 2020; Nouvellet et al., 2021). While the economic effects of these stay-at-home orders have been largely negative, the air quality in Europe significantly improved in this period, as less movement, as well as economic activity, reduced exposure to toxic pollutants of the population. It is likely that industrialised areas which host plants of major factories for industries which kept on working during the pandemic had enjoyed these benefits less, showing a SES pattern in exposure to pollution during the pandemic (Chang et al., 2020), however no data is still available at European level to deduce these conclusions.</p>
<p>Public transport and increased risk of infection</p>	<p>Unobserved effect</p>	<p>While no literature has yet highlighted the role of public transport in the spread of COVID-19 buses, trains, and trams can be generally thought to be closed spaces, with poor ventilation, and in which close contact is all but inevitable, spaces that are considered at the highest risk of infection of COVID-19 (European Centre for Disease Control, 2020a, 2020b). There is a general lack of data on the use of public transport across Europe. It can be deduced that private vehicle ownership is associated with higher SES, and therefore that we might observe a difference in exposure to risk of infection on public transport to increase among people of lower SES. However, no observations are available as of right now.</p>

<p>Women might be in more precarious housing situations because of the pandemic</p>	<p>Direct effect</p>	<p>With the growing unemployment rate due to the restrictions implemented in the EU, making ends meet and paying monthly rentals can become harder, especially for single mothers facing the pandemic with precarious or no employment: these inequalities are exacerbated across SES, and the latest 2019 data shows us that in the EU 11.8 % of the population in cities lived in dwellings which cost them more than 40% of their disposable income (Eurostat, 2020b).</p>
<p>Women are employed in sectors which were required to work throughout the pandemic and more at risk of infection</p>	<p>Indirect effect</p>	<p>A larger proportion of women work in the care and hospitality sectors, which could not transition to home working (Joint Research Centre (European Commission) et al., 2020; Seguino and Braunstein, 2019). This difference also exacerbates through SES, as people and women who work in jobs unable to transition to remote workspaces might be more at risk of being infected (Cook and Grimshaw, 2021).</p>

Indicators of Inequalities

Indicators for economy/work and labour market domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/Comment
Effects on employment status	European	Unemployment rates	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS) (or ILO or OECD but no disaggregation possible)	Up to 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Occupational status Educational attainment levels Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnicity Gender identity 	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/une_rt_a/default/table?lang=en
	European	Employment rates	Eurostat LFS (or ILO)	Up to 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Occupational status Educational attainment levels Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnicity Gender identity 	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFSI_EMP_A_custom_1086519/default/table?lang=en
	European	Gender gap in part-time employment	LFS	Up to 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Microdata unavailable. 	http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=tepsr_lm210&lang=en
	European	Index of total actual hours worked in the main job	LFS	Up to 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Occupational status Educational attainment levels Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnicity 	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFSI_AHW_Q_custom_1076313/default/line?lang=en

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity 	
	European	Number of hours usually worked per week in main job	Eurostat EU-SILC	Up to 2019	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (groups) • Household type • Educational attainment levels • Citizenship and country of birth • Income (personal/household) <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	Not available online
	European	Work interruption due to the Corona crisis	SHARE COVID-19	2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (only 50+) • Education • Marital status • Income <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	http://www.share-project.org/special-data-sets/share-corona-survey.html
	European	Length of work interruption	SHARE COVID-19	2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (only 50+) • Education • Marital status • Income 	http://www.share-project.org/special-data-sets/share-corona-survey.html

					<p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	
	European	Started to work from home as a result of the situation	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	Only round 1 (Feb/Mar 2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/working-teleworking
Problematic working conditions	European	Ability to perform the work properly with the equipment at home	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	Only second wave (2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/working-teleworking
	European	Health and safety for	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	Only second wave (2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/working-teleworking

		employees (4 items)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	
	European	Satisfaction with the working conditions in your main paid job	European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS)	2015	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Educational level • Income <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender • Race 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/european-working-conditions-survey (under the area: working life perspectives)
Economic consequences	European	Able to make ends meet	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020 (round 1 & 2), 2021 (round 3)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/financial-situation

	European	Financial situation of the household now compared to 3 months ago	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020 (round 1 & 2), 2021 (round 3)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/financial-situation
	European	At-risk-of-poverty rate	Eurostat EU-SILC	2019 (for some countries, already 2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (groups) • Household type • Educational attainment levels • Broad group of country of birth • Type of contract • Income <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_li02/default/table?lang=en
	European	In-work at-risk-of-poverty rate	Eurostat EU-SILC	2019 (for some countries, already 2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (groups) • Household type • Educational attainment levels 	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_iw01/default/table?lang=en

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broad group of country of birth • Type of contract • Income <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	
	European	Performance (quantity)	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	Only second wave (June/July 2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/working-teleworking
Human capital loss	European	Labour productivity per person employed and hour worked (EU27_2020 =100)	Eurostat	Up to 2019	Microdata unavailable	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tesem160/default/table?lang=en
	European	Transition from fixed term contracts to	Eurostat LFS (longitudinal)	Up to 2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (groups) <p>Microdata unavailable</p>	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsi_long_e09/default/table?lang=en

		permanent contracts				(Experimental item: i.e., not harmonized)
	European	Labour market transitions	Eurostat LFS (longitudinal)	Up to 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age (groups) Microdata unavailable	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFSI_LONG_A_custom_1086588/default/table?lang=en
						(Experimental item)
Development of new skills		No indicators available				
Health consequences	European	WHO mental wellbeing index	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020, 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/quality-of-life
Change in gender-role attitudes	International	Gender-role attitudes	ISSP (International Social Survey Programme)	2012, 2002 (different questions)	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Education • Race 	Data not currently available to compare before/after
	European	Gender-role attitudes	ESS (European Social Survey)	2004 and 2010	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age 	Data not currently available to compare before/after

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education • Income • Household composition • Marital status • Belong to a minority ethnic group 	
Loss of market bargaining power because of less favourable economic situation after the pandemic	European	Index of total actual hours worked in the main job by sex and age group (2021 = 100) - quarterly data	Eurostat, Labour force Survey (LFS)	2021 Quarterly data available	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age group Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational level • Income • Ethnicity • Economic sector 	Data available for comparison: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsi_ahw_q/default/table?lang=en
	European	Employment by sex, age and economic activity	Eurostat, Labour force Survey (LFS) Quarterly	2021 Quarterly data available	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age group • Economic activities Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational level • Income • Ethnicity 	Data available for comparison: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFSO_EGAN2_custom_1159990/default/table?lang=en
	European	Unemployment by sex and age – monthly data	Eurostat, Labour force Survey (LFS) Monthly	2021 Monthly data available	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational level 	Data available for comparison: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/UNE

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Income Economic sector Ethnicity 	RT_M_custom_1161321/default/table?lang=en
	European	Part-time employment	Eurostat, Labour force Survey (LFS)	2019 (2020 partly available)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Age Educational level Citizenship Degree of urbanization <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender identity Income Economic sector Ethnicity 	<p>Data not currently available for comparison:</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFST_RT_M_custom_1161308/default/table?lang=en</p>
	European	Unemployed receiving unemployment benefits	ILO Social Security Inquiry Database	2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender identity Income Economic sector Ethnicity 	<p>Data available for comparison:</p> <p>https://www.ilo.org/shinyapps/bulkexplorer47/?lang=en&segment=indicator&id=EA_P_2WAP_SEX_AGE_RT_A</p>
Stalling of progress for equality for women (Labour market gender segregation, differences in	European	Students enrolled in tertiary education (Labour market gender segregation)	Eurostat		<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Age Educational level Economic sector <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender identity 	<p>Data not currently available for comparison:</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EDUC_UOE_ENRT03_custom_1161489/default/table?lang=en</p>

median income, and access to labour market)					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income • Ethnicity 	
	European	Mean and median income by age and sex (Difference in median income)	Eurostat EU-SILC and ECHP (European Community Household Panel) surveys	2019 (partially available for 2020)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Educational level • Income • Economic sector • Ethnicity 	Data not currently available for comparison: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ILC_DI03_custom_1161669/default/table?lang=en
	European	Gender gap in part-time employment (Access to labour market)	Eurostat, Labour force Survey (LFS)	2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age group <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Educational level • Income • Economic sector • Ethnicity 	Data not currently available for comparison: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tepsr_lm210/default/table?lang=en
European	Females share of employment in managerial positions	ILOSTAT, Labour force Survey (LFS)	2020	<p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Educational level • Income • Economic sector • Ethnicity 	Data not currently available for comparison: https://www.ilo.org/shinyapps/bulkexplorer43/?lang=en&segment=indicator&id=HOW_2LSS_NOC_RT_A	

	European (Not all countries)	Mean hours actually worked of prime-aged employed person by sex and type of household (Access to labour market)	ILOSTAT Labour force Survey (LFS)	2019, 2020 (depending on country)	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Household type (presence of children) Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Educational level • Income • Economic sector • Ethnicity 	Data currently not available for comparison https://www.ilo.org/shinyapps/bulkexplorer38/?lang=en&segment=indicator&id=HOW_2LSS_NOC_RT_A
--	-------------------------------------	---	--	-----------------------------------	---	--

Indicators for gender pay and pension gap domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/Comment
Widening of the gender pay gap	European	Unadjusted gender pay gap (GPG)	Eurostat Structure of Earnings Survey (SES) Labour Force Survey (LFS)	Yearly update on International Women's Day. Data are available from 2007 onwards. However, data for EU-28 are available from 2011 onwards and data for EU-27 and Euro area are available from 2008 onwards.	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Age Economic activity Working time Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnic/racial disaggregation Gender identity Educational attainment 	The data are currently available only until 2019: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sdg_05_20/default/table?lang=en
Women, earning less than men, found themselves in a more precarious situation during and after the pandemic	European	Mean hourly earnings	Eurostat Structure of Earnings Survey (SES)	2018	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Economic activity Employment contract Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnic/racial disaggregation Gender identity Education 	Data not currently available to compare before/after https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/earn_ses18_15/default/table?lang=en

Labour market shock will affect sectors which women are mostly employed in (service and hospitality)	European	Gender unemployment gap	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS)	Yearly update 2019, 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Employment • Economic activity • Educational attainment Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic/racial disaggregation • Gender identity 	Data currently available for comparison https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFSI_EMP_A/default/table?lang=en
	European	Employment rate	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS)	Quarterly update 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Educational attainment Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic/racial disaggregation • Gender identity 	Data currently available for comparison https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsq_erga_ed/default/table?lang=en
Increase in part-time or precarious work because of increase in care of children and job market created by the pandemic	European	Main reason for part-time employment: care of adults with disabilities or children	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS)	2000-2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic/racial disaggregation • Gender identity 	Data will be available for comparison https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lfsa_epgar&lang=en

	European	Gender unemployment gap	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS)	Yearly update 2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Employment • Activity <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic/racial disaggregation • Gender identity 	<p>Data currently available for comparison</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/LFSI_EMP_A/default/table?lang=en</p>
	European	Temporary employees	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS)	Quarterly update 2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Education • Economic Activity • Duration of work contract <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethnic/racial disaggregation • Gender identity 	<p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsq_etgae/default/table?lang=en</p>

Indicators for gender care gap domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/Comment
Increase of care responsibilities for women	European	Number of hours spent on cooking and housework	EWCS; Other possible sources: (1) Time Use Survey (HETUS); (2) EQLS.	EWCS: 2005, 2010; 2015 HETUS: 2000, 2010 (unknown for 2020) EQLS: 2016	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Employment status • Occupation • Education • Income • Marital status • Number of children/household size • Partner working (hours normally worked per week) Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	Data not currently available to compare before/after
	National	Percentage of women doing more housework during the COVID-19 emergency	Italy	April-July 2019, April 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working arrangement (of woman and the partner) • Age • Having a university degree • Having children/number of children • Age of children 	Project: https://www.carloalberto.org/research/competitive-projects/clear-closing-the-gender-pension-gap-by-increasing-womens-awareness Article: https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3644817
	European	Number of hours spent caring for and	EWCS	2005, 2010, 2015	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age 	Data not currently available to compare before/after

		or/educating your children/grandchildren			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employment status • Occupation • Education • Income • Marital status • Number of children/household size • Partner working (hours normally worked per week) <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	
National	Percentage of men and women spending more hours on childcare during the COVID-19 emergency	Italy	April-July 2019, April 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working arrangement (of woman and the partner) • Age • Having a degree • Having children/number of children • Age of children 	<p>Project: https://www.carloalberto.org/research/competitive-projects/clear-closing-the-gender-pension-gap-by-increasing-womens-awareness</p> <p>Article: https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3644817</p>	
European	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time spent on childcare as primary or secondary activity - Time spent with children 	HETUS (Harmonised European Time Use Surveys)	2000, 2010	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Employment status <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education 	<p>Data not currently available to compare before/after</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tus_00np_aycare/default/table?lang=en</p>	

	National	Hours spent on a “typical” work day during the past week on active childcare and home schooling	Surveys in US, UK, DE	2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • University degree • Employment status 	Article: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0047272720301092
Difficulties to combine paid work and family duties	European	Change in working hours	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020 (round 1 and 2)	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/working-teleworking
	European	Main reason for part-time employment: care of adults with disabilities or children	Eurostat EU-LFS [lfsa_epgar]	2000-2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age groups 	https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=lfsa_epgar&lang=en
	European	Effects of childcare responsibilities on	EU-LFS ad hoc module [lfsa_18ceffed]	2018	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age groups • Education 	https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsa_18ceffed/default/table?lang=en

		employment of women and men				
	European	Family responsibilities prevented you from giving the time you should to your job	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020 (round 1 and 2), 2021	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/working-teleworking
Mental (and physical) health issues	European	Feeling tension, loneliness, depression	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020, 2021	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/quality-of-life
	European	WHO mental wellbeing index	Living, working and COVID-19 data (Eurofound)	2020, 2021	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (option: describe myself in another way) • Age (groups) 	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19/quality-of-life

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education level completed • Spouse or partner in household • Number of children in household <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity 	
Change in norms and attitudes towards gender division of care	European	'Acceptance of gender stereotypes' (several items, e.g.: the most important role of a woman is to take care of her home and family; the most important role of a man is to earn money)	Eurobarometer	Eurobarometer: 2017, 2014, 2009 (different questions)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Education • Occupation • <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race • Income • Gender identity 	Data not currently available to compare before/after
	International	Attitudes towards gender roles	ISSP	2012, 2002 (different questions)	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Education • Race 	Data not currently available to compare before/after

Indicators for gender-based violence domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/Comment
Increased gender-based violence within the household	European (only few countries)	Annual number of women victims of intimate partner violence (aged 18 and over) committed by men (aged 18 and over), as recorded by police [administrative data]	EIGE	Up to 2018	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Income • Education • Race/ethnicity • Place of residence 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_int_adm_ipv_ipv_indic_1 (not harmonised data and only very few countries)
	European	Prevalence of physical and sexual violence by intimate partners since the age of 15 and during the 12 months prior to the interview [survey data]	EU FRA	2012	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age victim • Education victim • Main activity victim • Type of perpetrator (relationship) Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Age • Income • Race/ethnicity • Place of residence 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_int_sur_phy_prev_phys_sex_ipv_grand

Psychological violence	European	Felt discriminated against or harassed on the basis of one or more of the following grounds (e.g. gender, political opinion, ethnic origin, skin color, being intersex, disability...)	Eurobarometer	2015 and 2019	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Education <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_psy_sur_eb_spec_feltdis
	European	Being subject to harassment during the course of your work	Eurofound - EWCS	2005, 2010, 2015	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Employment status • Occupation • Education • Income • Marital status • Number of children/household size <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_psy_sur_ewcs_harassment
	European	Being subjected to	Eurofound - EWCS	2010, 2015	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-

		verbal abuse during the course of your work			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Employment status • Occupation • Education • Income • Marital status • Number of children/household size <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Race 	statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_psy_sur_ewcs_verbale_buse
Increase in homicides	European	Intentional homicide victims by victim-offender relationship and sex	Eurostat (from EIGE website)	Up to 2018	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Age • Income • Education • Race/ethnicity • Place of residence 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_int_adm_oth_crim_hom_vrel
New form of gender-based violence		No indicators available				
Consequences health	European	Self-perceived health	Eurostat EU SILC	Up to 2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Employment status • Income • Marital status <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/ta_hlthmort_hlth_self_gen_hlth_silc_01

Raise in consciousness	European	Consider each of the following forms of domestic violence against women to be serious	Eurobarometer	2010	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Education • Marital status • Household composition Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income • Gender identity • Race 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_att_opin_acc_eb_spec_howserious
	European	Attitudes towards acceptability of GBV	Eurobarometer	2016	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Education • Marital status • Household composition Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income • Gender identity • Race 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_att_opin_acc_eb_spec_wrongillegal
	European	Opinions on where violence against women is more likely to occur	Eurobarometer	2016	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Education • Marital status • Household composition Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income • Gender identity • Race 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/genvio_att_opin_car_eb_spec_valocation

Indicators for human rights domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/Comment
Decreased access to quality care due to overwhelming of the healthcare system	European	Share of people with good or very good perceived health by sex	Eurostat EU-SILC	2019	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age Sex Income quintiles Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender Ethnicity Educational level 	Data currently not available for comparison https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/HLTH_SILC_10_custom_1262122/default/table?lang=en
Decreased investments in healthcare could lead to worst healthcare outcomes	European	Healthcare expenditure for preventive care	Eurostat	2019 Yearly updated	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European countries Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not relevant for indicator 	Data currently not available for comparison http://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/submitViewTableAction.do
Rise in healthcare unmet need	European	Self-reported unmet need for medical care by sex	Eurostat, EU-SILC	2020 Yearly updated	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex Age group Income quantile Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender Ethnicity Educational attainment 	Data currently not available for comparison https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/HLTH_SILC_08/default/table?lang=en
	European	Out-of-pocket expenditure on healthcare	Eurostat, OECD	Eurostat 2020 Yearly updated	Available for Eurostat <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European countries Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Socioeconomic status 	Data currently not available for comparison Eurostat:

				OECD 2018	<p>Available for OECD</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European countries • Type of expenditure <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socioeconomic status 	<p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tep_sr_sp310/default/table?lang=en</p> <p>OECD: https://stat.link/qb82cj</p>
--	--	--	--	-----------	--	---

Indicators for decision-making domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/comment
Imbalanced presence of women and men in decision-making	European	Major political parties: leader and deputy leaders	EIGE	Up to 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmid_m_pol_part_wmid_polpart
	European	European committees: presidents and members	EIGE	Up to 2021 Q2	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmid_m_pol_comm_wmid_eucom
	European	Regional executives: president and members	EIGE	Up to 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmid_m_pol_gov_wmid_regall_ex ec
	European	Local/municipal councils: mayors or other leaders and members	EIGE	Up to 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmid_m_pol_parl_wmid_locpol
	European	National academies of science: presidents and members of the highest decision-making body	EIGE	2017, 2019, 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmid_m_educ_wmid_acadsci
	European	Largest listed companies: CEOs, executives	EIGE	Up to 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex 	https://eige.europa.eu/gender-statistics/dgs/indicator/wmid

		and non-executives				m_bus_bus_wmid_comp_compex
	Not specified	Heads of global health organizations & boards of global health organizations	Global Health 50/50 Report	2018	Microdata unavailable	https://globalhealth5050.org/wp-content/uploads/Global-Health-5050-2021-Report.pdf?v2

Indicators for environmental justice domain.

Pathway	Level	Indicator(s)	Data source(s)	Years of availability	Socioeconomic disaggregation available for defined indicators	Link/Comment
Living environments affect the wellbeing and health of people, who were forced to live more at home due to the non-pharmaceutical interventions enacted during the public health emergency	European	Population living in a dwelling with a leaking roof, damp walls, floors or foundation, or rot in window frames or floor	EU-SILC	Updated yearly 2019	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Income situation in relation to the risk of poverty • Type of household (including sex and age groups) <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Education • Employment status • Race/ethnicity 	Data available for 2019 and for comparison in the future https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_mdho01\$DV_424/default/table?lang=en

	European	Overcrowding rate	EU-SILC	Updated yearly 2019	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Citizenship • Income situation in relation to the risk of poverty • Type of household (including sex and age groups) <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Education • Employment status • Race/ethnicity 	Data available for 2019 and for comparison in the future https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_lvho05a/default/table?lang=en
	European	Share of total population not having indoor flushing toilet for the sole use of their household	EU-SILC	Updated yearly 2019	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Income situation in relation to the poverty threshold • Type of household (including sex and age groups) <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender identity • Education • Employment status • Race/ethnicity 	Data available for 2019 and for comparison in the future https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/tessi294/default/table?lang=en

	European	Inability to keep home adequately warm	EU-SILC	Updated yearly 2019	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type of household (including sex and age groups) Income situation in relation to the risk of poverty <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender Education Employment status Race/ethnicity 	Data available for 2019 and for comparison in the future https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_mdes01/default/table?lang=en
	European (cities)	Answer to poll: I have experienced good clean air and I don't want to go back to the air pollution levels we previously had	EPHA (European Public Health Alliance) & YouGov Opinion Poll	2020 No update foreseen	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metropolitan area <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age Gender identity Education Race/ethnicity Employment status 	No data available for comparison https://www.transportenvironment.org/press/no-going-back-pre-covid-air-pollution-levels-opinion-poll

Changes in exposure to air pollution due to less movement for the stay-at-home orders issued	European	Urban population exposure to air pollution by particulate matter	Air Quality e-Reporting European Environmental Agency	Updated yearly 2019	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical disaggregation Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Gender identity • Education • Employment status • Race/ethnicity 	Data available for 2019 and for comparison in the future https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/t2020_m210/default/table?lang=en
	European (Cities)	weekly and monthly average concentrations of nitrogen dioxide (NO2) and particulate matter (PM10 and PM2.5)	Air Quality and COVID-19 European Environmental Agency	Update Weekly 2021	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Country • City Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Sex • Gender identity • Education • Employment status • Race/ethnicity 	Data available for comparison https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/air/air-quality-and-covid19/air-quality-and-covid19

	European (cities, NUTS2, NUTS3)	relationship between various indicators related to social deprivation or vulnerability and air and noise pollution exposure within cities	European Environmental Agency Analysis of Air Pollution and Noise and Social Deprivation	2014 (NUTS2, NUTS 3) 2012 (Cities) No update foreseen	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Unemployment • Education • Household income • Housing situation • GDP per capita (NUTS 3 only) Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity • Sex • Gender identity 	No data available for comparison https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/eionet_rep_etcacm_2018_7_deprivation_aq_noise
Areas more affect by environmental pollution could expose residents to a higher risk of COVID-19 infection	European	Employment rate	Eurostat Labour Force Survey (LFS)	Quarterly update 2020	Available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • Educational attainment Not available: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity • Gender identity • SES 	Data currently available for comparison https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfsq_erga-ed/default/table?lang=en

	European	Distribution of population by tenure status	EU-SILC	2019 Update yearly	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tenure status (own/rent) • Type of household (including sex and age groups) • Income situation in relation to the risk of poverty <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity • Gender identity 	<p>Data available for 2019 and for comparison in the future</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ILC_LVH002_custom_137548/bookmark/table?lang=en&bookmarkId=1f26f568-0301-45d0-a454-86bad3f5ce64</p>
Women might be in more precarious housing situations because of the pandemic	Eurostat	Housing cost overburden rate	Eurostat	2020	<p>Available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree of urbanization <p>Not available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sex • Age • SES • Education level • Race/ethnicity • Gender identity 	<p>Data not currently available to compare before/after</p> <p>https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ILC_LVH007D_custom_138509/bookmark/table?lang=en&bookmarkId=a403e087-6bbc-42d0-be2b-89e0c244d67d</p>

Annex 2 – RAS grid template

RESISTIRÉ – RAS

CODE:	RAS	Click here to enter text.
-------	-----	---------------------------

Please, add here a country code and a progressive number (e.g.: IT01)

OVERALL DESCRIPTION

Type of RAS	Rapid Assessment Survey reporting primary data	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Rapid assessment/analysis of existing datasets	<input type="checkbox"/>

1. COUNTRY(IES):	Click here to enter text.	
2. Name of the RAS or Project Title:	Click here to enter text.	
3. Name of the body(ies)/author(s) who administered/coordinated this RAS (e.g., Ministry of Education):	Click here to enter text.	
4. Name/info of a lead/contact person (where available):	Click here to enter text.	
5. Body(ies)/author(s) type:	Government	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Non-Governmental Organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Think-tank	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Higher Education Institution	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.1. If "other", please specify:	Click here to enter text.	
6. Web link to the body(ies)/author(s) administering this RAS:	Click here to enter text.	
7. Weblink to report/outputs (if available):	Click here to enter text.	

8. When was the RAS results published (MM/YYYY)?	Click here to enter a date.	
9. Is this RAS?	One-off	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Longitudinal, i.e., replicated at different points in time (please specify)	<input type="checkbox"/>
9.1. If "longitudinal", please specify:	Click here to enter text.	

TARGET GROUPS AND INEQUALITIES

10. Who is the target group of the RAS?	General population	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
10.1. If "other", please specify:	Click here to enter text.	
11. (If RAS reporting primary data) Number of respondents in the RAS	Click here to enter text.	
12. (If assessment/analysis of existing datasets) Are number of respondents of the different sources reported?	Choose an item.	
13. (If RAS reporting primary data) Is the sampling based on a random procedure (e.g., simple, stratified, etc.) or not?	Choose an item.	
13.1. If "yes", please specify:	Click here to enter text.	
14. What are the main topics covered in the RAS? (e.g., mental health, working conditions, vaccination, restriction measures):	Click here to enter text.	
15. Which of the following domains does this RAS cover (multiple selection possible):	Gender-based violence	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Work/labour market	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Economy	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Gender pay and pension gaps	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Gender care gap	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Decision-making and politics	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Environmental justice	<input type="checkbox"/>

	Human and fundamental rights	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>

15.1. If "other", please specify:	Click here to enter text.	
-----------------------------------	---------------------------	--

15.2. If stereotypes are addressed in discussing inequalities within the covered domains, please briefly describe in what terms	Click here to enter text.	
---	---------------------------	--

	Sex and/or gender	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	-------------------	--------------------------

	Social class/socioeconomic background	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	---------------------------------------	--------------------------

	Age	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	-----	--------------------------

	Disability	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	------------	--------------------------

16. Which of the following inequality grounds does the RAS cover (multiple selection possible):	Nationality	<input type="checkbox"/>
---	-------------	--------------------------

	Race/ethnicity	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	----------------	--------------------------

	Religion/belief	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	-----------------	--------------------------

	Sexuality	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	-----------	--------------------------

	Gender identity	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	-----------------	--------------------------

	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	-------	--------------------------

16.1. If "other", please specify:	Click here to enter text.	
-----------------------------------	---------------------------	--

17. What are the key findings in relation to inequality grounds? (If available, copy and paste the RAS abstract, otherwise summarise key findings in max 300 words)
--

Click here to enter text.

Annex 3 – RAS Country Report Template

RESISTIRÉ RESponding to outbreakS through co-creaTive inclusive equality stRatEgies

COUNTRY LEVEL TEMPLATE FOR RAS MAPPING

Considering the responses you have provided to the Grid about individual RAS, please synthesise this information to fill in the following Template in relation to the country you have been working on.

Country:

- What kind of inequalities/target groups have the RAS identified in the grids mostly been addressing? What is missing?

- What domains have the RAS identified mostly been addressing? What is missing?

- Among the RAS you have selected, can you recommend which are most important and/or promising to contribute towards a gender+ inclusive COVID-19 recovery? Which should we follow-up on in further work, e.g. extending data collection or analysis?

Name of RAS:

Name of RAS:

Name of RAS:

Annex 4 - Mapped RAS

These are the 291 Rapid Assessment Surveys mapped by national researchers. Those highlighted in grey are RAS that were identified as particularly promising by national researchers (see Methodology chapter).

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based Work & Labour Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta I Justice	Human Rights	Other			
AT01	Austria	Love, Intimacy and Sexuality in times of Corona	https://barbararothmueller.net/rothmueller2020zwisehenberichtCOVID19.pdf						x			x	x
AT02	Austria	Multiple burdens under COVID-19: home office and domestic work	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3831914		x				x				
AT03	Austria	Learning and Covid 19 – a challenge for self-regulation	https://lernencovid19.univie.ac.at/en/more-information/									x	x
AT04	Austria	Analysis of domestic violence during Covid Lockdown	https://bmi.gv.at/bmi_documents/2536.pdf	x									
AT05	Austria	Renewable Energy in Austria	https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/at/Documents/energy-resources/at-erneuerbare-energien-2021.pdf						x	x	x		
AT06	Austria	Media Use During the Covid Crisis (of migrants)	https://www.integrationsfonds.at/fileadmin/content/AT/Downloads/Publikationen/OeIF_Forschungsbericht_Mediennutzung_2021.pdf									x	x
AT07	Austria	Women on the labour market before and during the Covid-19 crisis	https://www.wifo.ac.at		x			x					
AT08	Austria	Analyses of the Social Situation in Austria in the COVID-19 Pandemic	https://www.sozialministerium.at/dam/jcr:5f807a53-5dce-4395-8981-682b5f1dc23b/BMSGPK_Analyse-der-sozialen-Lage.pdf		x	x	x	x				x	
AT09	Austria	AKCovid – Effects of the health and labour market crisis on the population	https://inprogress.ihs.ac.at/akcovid		x				x				

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS								
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other
AT10	Austria	Austrian Corona Panel Project (ACPP)	https://viecer.univie.ac.at/coronapanel/austrian-corona-panel-data/method-report/		x	x		x	x			
AT11	Austria	Teaching and learning during the condition of a pandemic	https://irihs.ihs.ac.at/id/eprint/5873/24/ihs-report-2021-steiner-koeppling-leitner-pessl-lassnigg-lehren-und-lernen-unter-pandemiebedingungen.pdf									x
BE01	Belgium	Belgian wages with focus on essential occupations during Covid-19	https://statbel.fgov.be/nl/themas/werk-opleiding/lonen-en-arbeidskosten/gemiddelde-bruto-maandlonen		x		x					
BE02	Belgium	Consequences of the Covid-19 crisis for the Belgian labour market generally remain limited in 2020	https://statbel.fgov.be/nl/nieuws/gevolgen-van-de-covid-19-crisis-voor-de-belgische-arbeidsmarkt-2020-blijven-globaal-genomen		x	x						
BE03	Belgium	Sciensano Covid-19 health survey	https://www.sciensano.be/nl/pershoek/neem-deel-aan-de-nieuwe-covid-19-gezondheidsenquête-0	x	x							x
BE04	Belgium	Impact of corona measures on stress, relationships and intrafamily violence	https://ircp.ugent.be/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Toelichtend-rapport-RSA-studie-Eerste-bevindingen-Mei-2020-1.pdf	x								
BE05	Belgium	Power to Care	https://www.sciensano.be/nl/pershoek/covid-19-crisis-heeft-grote-impact-op-persoonlijk-professioneel-en-lichamelijk-vlak-voor-zorg-en		x							x
BE06	Belgium	Covid and I	https://uclouvain.be/en/research-institutes/irss/covid-et-moi.html									x
BE07	Belgium	Covid-19 Inquiry	https://www.statistiekvlaanderen.be/nl/sv-rapport-%E2%80%98resultaten-covid-19-bevraging-gezondheid-welzijn-en-sociale-contacten%E2%80%99		x		x	x		x	x	
BE08	Belgium	The psychosocial and financial impact of the Covid-19 epidemic in Belgium (L'impact psycho-social et financier de l'épidémie de Covid-19 en Belgique)	https://www.croix-rouge.be/2021/03/11/enquete-9-belges-sur-10-touche-financierement-et-psychologiquement-par-la-crise-sanitaire/		x	x						x
BE09	Belgium	The Big Corona Study (De Grote Coronastudie)	https://www.uantwerpen.be/nl/projecten/coronastudie/		x							x

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta	Justice	Human Rights	Other
BE10	Belgium	Impact of the corona crisis on the process of finding employment and the well-being of people looking for employment.	https://www.ugent.be/nl/actueel/meer-dan-4-op-5-werkzoekenden-bezorgd-over-het-vinden-van-een-job-tijdens-de-coronacrisis.htm		x								
BG01	Bulgaria	Effects of the Coronavirus Crisis on Bulgarian Citizens and Business Entities	https://alpharesearch.bg/post/967-otrajenie-na-krizata-s-koronavirusa-vurhu-bulgarskite-grajdani-i-stopanskite-subekti.html?lang=bg		x	x							
BG02	Bulgaria	COVID-19 in Roma Neighbourhoods in Bulgaria	https://osis.bg/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Covid-19-Romes-ENG_final_web.pdf		x							x	
BG03	Bulgaria	A Year After the Covid-19 Beginning - How Did Our Lives Change?	https://alpharesearch.bg/post/976-godina-sled-nachaloto-na-kovid-pandemiata-kak-se-promeni-ivotut-ni.html		x		x	x				x	
BG04	Bulgaria	The COVID-19 Lockdown Through the Eyes of Teenagers	https://www.unicef.org/bulgaria/en/press-releases/covid-19-lockdown-through-eyes-teenagers									x	
BG05	Bulgaria	Attitudes of Bulgarians Towards the COVID-19 Situation	https://rctrend.bg/project/%d0%bd%d0%b0%d0%b3%d0%bb%d0%b0%d1%81%d0%b8-%d0%bd%d0%b0-%d0%b1%d1%8a%d0%bb%d0%b3%d0%b0%d1%80%d0%b8%d1%82%d0%b5-%d0%b2-%d1%81%d0%b8%d1%82%d1%83%d0%b0%d1%86%d0%b8%d1%8f%d1%82%d0%b0-%d1%81-%d1%80%d0%b0/		x	x						x	
BG06	Bulgaria	Educational Inequalities During the Pandemic	http://ire-bg.org/wpsite/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/%D0%9E%D0%B1%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B7%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%D1%82%D0%B5%D0%BB%D0%BD%D0%B8-%D0%BD%D0%B5%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B2%D0%B5%D0%BD%D1%81%D1%82%D0%B2%D0%B0-%D0%BF%D0%BE-%D0%B2%D1%80%D0%B5%D0%BC%D0%B5-%D0%BD%D0%B0-%D0%BF%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B4%D0%B5%D0%BC%D0%B8%D1%8F.pdf		x							x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
BG07	Bulgaria	Social Community Services During the State of Emergency	https://sapibg.org/download/1589265744-doklad-ot-prouchvane-socialnite-uslugi-v-obshchnosta-v-usloviya-na-izvredno-polozhenie.pdf		x								
BG08	Bulgaria	Distant Learning: an Opportunity for the Development of Education or a Prerequisite for Deepening Educational Inequalities	http://www.amalipe.com/index.php?nav=news&id=3690&lang=2									x	
CY01	Cyprus, Switzerland	COVID-19 IMPACT SURVEY	https://ucy.ac.cy/acthealthy/en/covid-19-impact-survey	x	x				x			x	x
CY03	Cyprus	COVID-19 Isolation and Risk of Death in Elderly People in Cyprus	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340600133_COVID-19_Isolation_and_Risk_of_Death_in_Elderly_People_in_Cyprus_Short_Report_-_National_Gerontology_Centre_Cyprus_April_2020									x	x
CY04	Cyprus	The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Mental Health: Evidence from Cyprus	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350713515_The_Impact_of_the_COVID-19_Pandemic_on_Mental_Health_Evidence_from_Cyprus						x			x	
CY05	Cyprus	Lifestyle habits of adults during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in Cyprus: evidence from a cross-sectional study	https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-021-10863-0						x			x	
CY06	Cyprus	Perceived Stress During the COVID-19-Related Confinement in Cyprus	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352055082_Perceived_Stress_During_the_COVID-19-Related_Confinement_in_Cyprus		x	x			x			x	
CY07	Cyprus	The Psychological Impact of Covid-19 Lockdown Measures on Cypriots' Mental Health and Quality of Life	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/345087894_The_Psychological_Impact_of_Covid-19_Lockdown_Measures_on_Cypriots'_Mental_Health_and_Quality_of_Life_'pdf		x	x			x			x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS										
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta	Justice	Human Rights	Other	
CY08	Cyprus	The Impact of the Covid19 Lockdown Measures on Mental Health and Well-Being and the role of Resilience: A Review of Studies in Cyprus	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350792241_The_Impact_of_the_Covid19_Lockdown_Measures_on_Mental_Health_and_Well-Being_and_the_role_of_Resilience_A_Review_of_Studies_in_Cyprus		x	x							x	
CY09	Cyprus	Psychological Resilience, Hope, and Adaptability as Protective Factors in Times of Crisis: A Study in Greek and Cypriot Society During the Covid-19 Pandemic	https://ojs.wiserpub.com/index.php/SER/article/view/618/372						x				x	
CY10	Cyprus	Examining the relationship between distance learning processes and university students' anxiety in times of Covid19	https://oapub.org/soc/index.php/EJSSS/article/view/1012/1598										x	
CZ01	Czech Republic	Mandatory Home Education During the COVID-19 Lockdown in the Czech Republic: A Rapid Survey of 1st-9th Graders' Parents	https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2020.00103/full										x	x
CZ02	Czech Republic	What are the effects of the pandemic on mental health? (Jaké má pandemie dopady na duševní zdraví?)	https://zivotbehempandemie.cz/dusevni-zdravi					x					x	x
CZ03	Czech Republic	Unemployment during the period of Covid-19, June 2021 (Nezaměstnanost v období COVID-19, červen 2021)	https://idea.cerge-ei.cz/images/COVID/Nezamestnanost_v_obdobi_covid-19_cerven_2021.pdf		x									
CZ04	Czech Republic	Evaluation of State Response to COVID-19 Epidemic (Hodnocení reakce státu na epidemii COVID-19)	https://cvvm.soc.cas.cz/en/press-releases/political/politicians-political-institutions/5384-evaluation-of-state-response-to-covid-19-epidemic-our-society-special-april-2021											x
CZ05	Czech Republic	Financial Situation of Households and Distance Learning (Finanční situace domácností a distanční výuka)	https://cvvm.soc.cas.cz/en/press-releases/other/5378-covid-19-financial-situation-of-households-and-distance-learning-our-society-special-april-2021		x	x								x
CZ06	Czech Republic	How did the pandemic affect working life? (Jak dopadla pandemie na pracovní život?)	https://zivotbehempandemie.cz/destabilizace-prace		x	x								

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
CZ07	Czech Republic	Survey on the situation of single parents in the coronavirus crisis (Výzkum k situaci samoživitelů a samoživitelek v koronavirové krizi)	https://www.stem.cz/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/STEM_Samozivitele_fin-3.pdf	x	x			x					x
CZ08	Czech Republic	What is the interest in getting vaccinated for free? (Jaký je zájem nechat se zdarma naočkovat?)	https://zivotbehempandemie.cz/ockovani										x
CZ09	Czech Republic	Divided by freedom - the effects of the pandemic (Rozdělení svobodou dopady pandemie)	https://plus.rozhlas.cz/sites/default/files/documents/151e94486bb4bf88f4f72e3a8002e122.pdf		x			x					x
CZ10	Czech Republic	Concerns regarding the economic situation and the pandemic are undermining confidence in the EU and Europe (Obavy z ekonomické situace a pandemie snižují důvěru v EU i Evropu)	https://www.stem.cz/obavy-z-ekonomicke-situace-a-pandemie-snizuji-duveru-v-eu-i-evropu-se-zachrannym-balickem-cesi-spise-souhlasil/										x
DK01	Denmark	A population survey of the corona situation 2021	https://www.aeldresagen.dk/presse/viden-om-aeldre/analyser-og-undersogelser/2021-befolkningsundersogelse-coronasituationen										x
DK02	Denmark	HOPE - How Democracies Cope with COVID19. A Data-Driven Approach	https://hope-project.dk/#/about						x			x	x
DK03	Denmark	Corona: Danes with low incomes are more anxious and worried about losing their jobs	https://cevea.dk/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Notat ngstelse og bekymring for arbejdslshed.pdf		x								
DK04	Denmark	The reopening of day care centres after coronavirus	https://www.vive.dk/media/pure/15138/4423870		x								x
DK05	Denmark	Healthcare chauvinism during the COVID-19 pandemic	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1369183X.2020.1860742										x
DK06	Denmark	Non-Western immigrants' level of employment is back to normal (pre-crisis)	https://www.ae.dk/analyse/2021-08-ikke-vestlige-indvandreteres-beskaeftigelse-er-tilbage-paa-foer-krise-niveau		x								
DK07	Denmark	We are testing Denmark	https://www.vitesterdanmark.dk										x

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
DK08	Denmark	Stand together by keeping your distance: The Danes' handling of the corona crisis	https://coronaminds.ku.dk/om/			x						x	
DK09	Denmark	Stand together by keeping your distance: The Danes' handling of the corona crisis	https://coronaminds.ku.dk/resultater/danskernes-mentale-velbefindende-under-coronakrisen									x	
DK10	Denmark	Student attention in the online school	https://coronakrisen.github.io/Om%20os.html									x	
EE01	Estonia	COVID-19 teemaline küsitlus	https://www.sm.ee/sites/default/files/contenteditors/Tervishoid/rahvatervis/2021.05_covid_19_30_kysitlus_yldraport.pdf		x				x				
EE02	Estonia	Covid-19 mõjud projekti „Noorte tervistav ja arendav puhkus“ noorte püsi- ja projektlaagritele“	https://www.hm.ee/sites/default/files/covid_maju_noortelaagritele_2021_raport_euk3.pdf			x			x				x
EE03	Estonia	COVID-19 põhjustatud majanduskriisi mõju töäjou ja oskuste vajaduse muutusele	https://oska.kutsekoda.ee/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/OSKA_COVID-19_eriuring_11.01.2021_loplik.pdf		x	x			x				
EE04	Estonia	Soolise võrdõiguslikkuse hetkeolukord ja parandamise viisid Eesti teaduses	https://www.etag.ee/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Sooline_vordoiguslikkus_Eesti_teaduses.pdf		x		x						
EE05	Estonia	Eesti elanike vaimne tervis ja heaolu	https://www.tlu.ee/sites/default/files/Instituudid/LTI/Dokumendid/Dokumendid/Uuringuraport%201%20laine.pdf		x				x				
EE06	Estonia	Eriolukorrast tingitud distantsõppe kogemused ja mõju Eesti üldharidussüsteemile	No input						x				
EE07	Estonia	Koroonapandeemia mõju laulu- ja tantsupeo kollektiividele	https://sa.laulupidu.ee/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/COVID-19-m%C3%B5juuuringu-aruanne-Saarpollim%C3%A4rts-2021.pdf		x				x				x
EE08	Estonia	Viiruse mõju Eestile	https://www.stat.ee/et/avasta-statistikat/viiruse-moju-estile		x	x			x				
EE09	Estonia	Eesti elanike loodusturismi uuring	https://static.visitestonia.com/docs/3618626_eeesti-elanike-loodusturismi-uuring2020.pdf		x	x			x				

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS								
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other
EE10	Estonia	Kampaania "Puhka Eestis" järeluurung	https://static.visitestonia.com/docs/3618627_eestlaste-sisereisid-2020-easi-siseturismi-kampaania-moju.pdf		x	x			x			
EE11	Estonia	Eesti elanike reisikavatsused lähikuudeks	https://static.visitestonia.com/docs/3658126_eesti-elanike-reisikavatsused-mai2021.pdf		x	x			x			
ES01	Spain	COVID19 impact survey Roma Population 2020	https://www.mscbs.gob.es/profesionales/saludPublica/prevPromocion/promocion/desigualdadSalud/docs/COVID-19_Impacto_PoblacionGitana.pdf									x
ES02	Spain	Questionnaire about the effects of the crisis caused by the Covid-19 on women and men within the business fabric of the province of Albacete	https://www.opialbacete.es/resultados-2020/		x	x		x				
ES03	Spain	DeustoBarómetro Social XVI	https://barometrosocial.deusto.es/		x	x						x
ES04	Spain	Survey on the mental health of Spaniards during the COVID-19 pandemic	http://www.cis.es/cis/export/sites/default/-Archivos/Marginales/3300_3319/3312/cru3312sexo.html									x
ES05	Spain	Inequality Tracker – Real-time Inequality in Spain and the Welfare State in Motion	https://inequality-tracker.caixabankresearch.com/en		x	x	x					
ES06	Spain	The impact of Covid19 on the population looked after through the Red Cross Respond Plan	https://www2.cruzroja.es/documents/5640665/13549052/Boleti%CC%81n_CruzRoja_Vuln_20+Interactivo+%281%29.pdf/b1688d72-c928-c53a-da71-749998342507?t=1616755630307	x	x	x		x				x
ES07	Spain	How the COVID-19 Lockdown Affected Gender Inequality in Paid and Unpaid Work in Spain	https://observatoriosocialcaixa.org/-/las-tareas-domesticas-y-el-cuidado-de-los-hijos-durante-el-confinamiento-una-labor-asumida-principalmente-por-las-mujeres		x			x				

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
ES08	Spain	Violence and Covid-19. Impact on women and LGBTQ+	https://www.aragon.es/documents/20127/2523474/Violencia+y+Covid-19+Impacto+sobre+la+mujer+y+colectivos+LGTBI.pdf/5697c26c-7b6d-1e36-38ac-83f63577bbcd?t=1614678436155	x									
ES09	Spain	The impact of COVID-19 on people of foreign origin in the Basque region	https://www.ikuspegi.eus/documentos/panoramicas/pan80cas.pdf		x	x							
ES10	Spain	Detection of needs of women with disability – Impact of Covid-19	https://www.cocemfe.es/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/informe-deteccion-necesidades-mujeres-discapacidad-covid-19.pdf	x	x	x		x				x	
FI01	Finland	Experiences of service sector workers	https://www.ttl.fi/kokemukset-korona-ajasta-polarisoituivat-palvelualoilla-arvostus-kasvoi-mutta-osa-kaipasi-tukea/		x								
FI02	Finland	Kansalaispulsso [Citizens' Pulse]	https://valtioneuvosto.fi/tietoa-koronaviruksesta/kansalaispulsso		x				x			x	
FI03	Finland	Gender equality in Finland	https://www.stat.fi/tup/julkaisut/tiedostot/julkaisuluettelo/yyti_sts_202100_2021_23460_net.pdf	x	x							x	
FI04	Finland	Well-being of elderly in care institutions and home services	https://thl.fi/fi/tutkimus-ja-kehittaminen/tutkimukset-ja-hankkeet/hyvinvointi-korona-aikana-kysely-vanhuspalvelujen-asiakkaille-vanko-									x	
FI05	Finland	Children's voice	https://www.pelastakaa.fi/ajankohtaista/kampanjat/lapsen-aani/			x						x	x
FI06	Finland	Life in families with children	https://www.lskl.fi/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Lskl_Paikoillaan_pyoriva_arvi.pdf		x	x		x				x	
FI07	Finland	Parents' experiences during the pandemic	https://www.jyu.fi/fi/ajankohtaista/arkisto/2020/05/vanhemmat-kokevat-covid-19-ajan-eri-tavoin-2013-jotkut-haluavat-jaada-poikkeusaikaan		x			x				x	x
FI08	Finland	Distance learning in upper secondary school during the pandemic	https://owalgroupp.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Koronan-vaikutukset-toisen-asteen-koulutukseen_1603.pdf									x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
FR01	France	Coconel/ housing	https://www.ifop.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/117272_COROV12_1_30032020-ENS-1.pdf		x	x		x					x
FR02	France	Survey of women victims of domestic violence during lockdown (Marital Violence - Enquête auprès des femmes victimes de violences conjugales durant le confinement)	https://www.ifop.com/publication/enquete-aupres-des-femmes-victimes-de-violences-conjugales-durant-le-confinement/	x									
FR03	France	EpiCov (Epidémiologie et Conditions de vie)	https://drees.solidarites-sante.gouv.fr/publications/etudes-et-resultats/confinement-du-printemps-2020-une-hausse-des-syndromes-depressifs		x	x					x		
FR04	France	Facing Covid-19. Social distancing, cohesion and inequalities in 2020 France (Faire face au Covid-19. Distanciation sociale, cohésion, et inégalité dans la France de 2020)	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7247999/		x			x					
FR05	France	CoviPrev: a survey to monitor behaviour and mental health during the COVID-19 epidemic (CoviPrev : une enquête pour suivre l'évolution des comportements et de la santé mentale pendant l'épidémie de COVID-19)	https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/etudes-et-enquetes/coviprev-une-enquete-pour-suivre-l-evolution-des-comportements-et-de-la-sante-mentale-pendant-l-epidemie-de-covid-19								x	x	
FR06	France	Survey on students' living conditions during the health crisis (Enquête sur les conditions de vie des étudiants pendant la crise sanitaire)	http://www.ove-national.education.fr/enquete/la-vie-detudiant-confine/		x	x							
FR07	France	Housework	https://harris-interactive.fr/opinion_polls/limpact-du-confinement-sur-les-inegalites-femmes-hommes/					x					
FR08	France	Consultation of people with disabilities on their situation during the Coronavirus crisis (Consultation auprès des personnes en situation de handicap sur leur situation pendant la crise du Coronavirus)	https://www.agefiph.fr/sites/default/files/medias/fichiers/2021-03/Agfiph-Etude_Covid_17%20mars.pdf		x	x							x

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
FR09	France	What impact has the health crisis had on precariousness in France? (Quel impact de la crise sanitaire sur la précarité en France?)	https://www.secourspopulaire.fr/barometre-ipsos-spf-2020-la-precarite-depuis-la-covid-19			x	x					x	
FR10	France	Covid-19 crisis: a setback for gender equality at work? (Crise de la Covid-19 : un retour en arrière pour la parité femmes / hommes au travail ?)	https://www.ipsos.com/fr-fr/crise-de-la-covid-19-un-retour-en-arriere-pour-la-parite-femmes-hommes-au-travail		x								
GER01	Germany	"Mannheimer Corona Studie" MCS	https://www.uni-mannheim.de/gip/corona-studie		x	x	x					x	
GER02	Germany	Corona Online Survey	https://www.boeckler.de/data/Boeckler-Impuls_2020_08_S4-5.pdf		x	x	x	x				x	
GER03	Germany	Daily life during Corona (Corona Alltag)	https://wzb.eu/de/forschung/dynamiken-sozialer-ungleichheiten/arbeit-und-fuersorge/corona-alltag		x	x	x	x					
GER04	Germany	Gender distribution in corona media reporting	https://malisastiftung.org/studie-geschlechterverteilung-corona-berichterstattung/		x	x			x				x
GER05	Germany	Socio-economic factors and implications of the corona virus in Germany (Sozio-ökonomische Faktoren und Folgen der Verbreitung des Corona Virus in Deutschland)	https://soep-cov.de/Berichte		x	x	x						
GER06	Germany	Online survey on the perception of handling the pandemic in Germany	https://pub.uni-bielefeld.de/download/2942930/2942931/Rees%20et%20al.%20Erste%20Ergebnisse%20einer%20Online-Umfrage%20zur%20gesellschaftlichen%20Wahrnehmung%20des%20Ugangs%20mit%20der%20Corona-Pandemie%20in%20Deutschland.pdf		x	x		x				x	x
GER07	Germany	Initial Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Employment and Hours of Self-Employed Coupled and Single Workers by Gender and Parental Status	http://ftp.iza.org/dp13443.pdf		x	x	x	x					

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS								
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environment Justice	Human Rights	Other
GER08	Germany	No specific title - survey on the impacts of the pandemic on families by the Equality office of the district Lüneburg	https://www.landkreis-lueneburg.de/Home-Landkreis-Lueneburg/Bildung-Soziales-und-Gesundheit-Landkreis/Gleichstellungsbeauftragte-Landkreis/umfrage-verursacht-corona-ein-rollback-der-gleichberechtigung-in-die-1950er.aspx	x	x	x					x	x
GER09	Germany	Roles and distribution of responsibilities between women and men in times of corona (Rollen und Aufgabenverteilung bei Frauen und Männern in Corona-Zeiten)	https://www.bertelsmann-stiftung.de/fileadmin/files/user_upload/Spotlight_Rollen_und_Aufgabenverteilung_bei_Frauen_und_Maennern_in_Zeiten_von_Corona.pdf		x			x				
GER10	Germany	The Impact of COVID-19 on Violence against Women and Children in Germany	https://www.hfp.tum.de/globalhealth/forschung/covid-19-and-domestic-violence/	x	x	x					x	
GER11	Germany	No specific title - Corona Survey	https://www.zdf.de/nachrichten/panorama/coronavirus-psyche-belastung-100.html		x	x		x			x	
GR01	Greece	Psychological and Behavioural Responses to the COVID-19 Pandemic in Greece	https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00821/full		x							x
GR02	Greece	OECD Economic Surveys: Greece	https://www.oecd.org/economy/surveys/Greece-2020-OECD-economic-survey-Overview.pdf		x	x		x				
GR03	Greece (plus 29 countries)	COVID-19 impacts on LGBTI communities in Europe and Central Asia: A rapid assessment report	https://ilga-europe.org/sites/default/files/LGBTI%20and%20COVID-19%20rapid%20assessment%20report.pdf									
GR04	Greece	The Cruelty of Containment: the Mental Health Toll of the EU's 'Hotspot' Approach on the Greek Islands	https://eu.rescue.org/sites/default/files/2020-12/IRC_Cruelty_of_Containment_FINAL.pdf								x	
GR05	Greece	Barometer on Working Conditions during COVID-19	https://assets.kpmg/content/dam/kpmg/gr/pdf/2020/07/covid-19-employment-conditions-barometer-3rd-wave-report.pdf		x							
GR06	Greece	Impact of COVID-19 on Urban Everyday Life in Greece. Perceptions, Experiences and Practices of the Active Population	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/22/9410		x					x		

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
HR 01	Croatia	Croatian Women and the Covid-19 pandemic	https://www.worldbank.org/en/search?q=Croatian+Women+and+the+Covid+-19+pandemic		x	x	x	x					x
HR 02	Croatia	Healthcare for pregnant and labouring women and mothers during the COVID-19 pandemic	https://www.roda.hr/udruga/dokumentacijski-centar/rodina-izvjesca-i-analize/dostupnost-skrbi-za-reproduktivno-zdravlje-zena-u-vrijeme-pandemije-covid-19.html					x					
HR 03	Croatia	HEALTHCARE AND SUPPORT TO MOTHERS AND NEWBORNS	https://www.roda.hr/udruga/dokumentacijski-centar/rodina-izvjesca-i-analize/dostupnost-skrbi-za-reproduktivno-zdravlje-zena-u-vrijeme-pandemije-covid-19.html					x				x	x
HR 04	Croatia	HEALTHCARE DURING MEDICALLY ASSISTED REPRODUCTION PROCEDURES	https://www.roda.hr/udruga/dokumentacijski-centar/rodina-izvjesca-i-analize/dostupnost-skrbi-za-reproduktivno-zdravlje-zena-u-vrijeme-pandemije-covid-19.html					x					
HR 06	Croatia	Survey of social exclusion, stigmatization and human rights violations of people with COVID-19 and people in self-isolation in the Osijek-Baranja and Vukovar-Srijem counties	https://acfcroatia.hr/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Analiza-istrazivanja-doživljaja-osoba-obojeelih-od-COVID-19-final.pdf									x	x
HR 07	Croatia	How are we? Life in Croatia in the age of coronavirus	https://web2020.ffzg.unizg.hr/covid19/wp-content/uploads/sites/15/2020/06/Kako-smo-Preliminarni-rezultati_brosura.pdf		x							x	x
HR 08	Croatia	How homeless survive the pandemic	https://www.matica.hr/inkluzija/3/kako-beskucnici-prezivljavaju-u-epidemiji-31035/									x	x
HR 09	Croatia	(Re)building society: A longitudinal study of post-corona social recovery in Croatian general population (ReSPoC)	http://psihologija.ffzg.unizg.hr/projekti/respoc/o-projektu									x	x
HR 10	Croatia	How the pandemic influenced the workers - mental health at the workplace	http://www.sssh.hr/hr/vise/nacionalne-aktivnosti-72/rezultati-istrazivanja-sssh-o-utjecaju-pandemije-na-mentalno-zdravlje-radnika-4767										
HU01	Hungary	Women entrepreneurs during a pandemic	https://hetfa.hu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/noi-vallalkozok-a-jarvany-idejen_HETFA.pdf		x	x		x					

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS										
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta	Justice	Human Rights	Other	
HU02	Hungary	The life situation of families during the time of coronavirus	https://unicef.hu/igy-segitunk/hireink/hazai-felmeres-jelentosen-nottek-az-anyak-terhei-a-karanten-alatt		x			x						
HU03	Hungary	The impact of Covid-19 on the gender division of childcare work in Hungary	https://www.fes-budapest.org/fileadmin/user_upload/dokumente/pdf-dateien/13_COVID_egyenlo_tlense_g_HUN_202_00629.pdf		x	x	x	x						
HU04	Hungary	Coronavirus and crisis management - the experience of Hungarians after a year	https://www.policysolutions.hu/userfiles/Policy_Solutions_Koronavirus_es_valsagkezeles.pdf	x	x	x								
HU05	Hungary	More than half of the woman in Hungary are not planning any vacations this summer	https://bank360.hu/blog/a-nok-tobb-mint-fele-nem-tervez-semilyen-nyaralast-iden-nyaron		x	x	x							
HU06	Hungary	According to Hungarians, gender pay inequality is a real problem	https://www.ipsos.com/hu-hu/nemek-kozti-fizetesbeli-egyenlotlenseg-valodi-problema-magyarok-szerint		x	x	x							
HU07	Hungary	School closures would be a big burden for Hungarian families	https://www.ipsos.com/hu-hu/nagy-terhet-jelentene-az-iskolabezaras-magyar-csaladok-szamara		x									
HU08	Hungary	In the danger of the pandemic and without a home	https://februarharmadika.blog.hu/2021/03/31/vilagjarvany_vezelyeben_lakastalanul		x	x							x	
HU09	Hungary	The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on different areas of life in Hungary (work, private life, health and mental state)	https://www.proquest.com/openview/4cae3369f93581527d9dc025823fd6cd/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=5083790		x	x								
HU10	Hungary	The effect of the pandemic situation on children	https://unicef.hu/mentalis-egeszseg/kutatas											x
IE01	Ireland	National Remote Working Survey April 2021	http://whitakerinstitute.ie/wp-content/uploads/2014/02/Remote-Working-National-Survey-Phase-III-Report-final.pdf		x	x								
IE02	Ireland	Social Impact of COVID-19 Survey February 2021: Well-being	https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-covid19/covid-19informationhub/socialandwellbeing/impactofcovid-19surveyfebruary2021well-being										x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
IE03	Ireland	Tracking the Shadow Pandemic – Lockdown 2: A report on women and children seeking support from Domestic Violence Services September 2020 –December 2020	https://www.safeireland.ie/policy-publications/#dfli-8398/1/	x								x	
IE04	Ireland	The Gender Gap in Income and the COVID-19 Pandemic	https://www.iza.org/en/publications/dp/14360/the-gender-gap-in-income-and-the-covid-19-pandemic		x			x	x				
IE05	Ireland	COVID-19 and Non-Irish Nationals in Ireland	https://www.esri.ie/publications/covid-19-and-non-irish-nationals-in-ireland		x	x		x					
IE06	Ireland	Women’s Experiences of Caring during COVID-19	https://www.nwci.ie/learn/publication/womens_experiences_of_caring_during_covid_19	x	x	x		x	x			x	
IE07	Ireland	LGBTI+ Life in Lockdown: One Year Later	https://www.belongto.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/LGBTI-Life-in-Lockdown-1-Year-Later_BeLoNG-To-Youth-Services.pdf	x								x	
IE08	Ireland	COVID-19 Nursing Homes Expert Panel Examination of Measures to 2021	https://assets.gov.ie/84889/b636c7a7-a553-47c0-88a5-235750b7625e.pdf									x	
IE09	Ireland	“Powerless”: Experiences of Direct Provision During the Covid-19 Pandemic	https://www.irishrefugeecouncil.ie/Handlers/Download.ashx?IDMF=419a9b2f-c405-4cc8-93c7-c27a618beb07		x							x	
IE10	Ireland	The disconnected: COVID-19 and disparities in access to quality broadband for higher education students	https://www.esri.ie/publications/the-disconnected-covid-19-and-disparities-in-access-to-quality-broadband-for-higher									x	
IS01	Iceland	COVID tracking	https://fel.hi.is/is/covid-trackin							x			
IS02	Iceland	Gender (In)equality in Times of COVID-19	https://english.hi.is/news/what_is_the_impact_of_covid_19_on_gender_equality		x			x					
IS03	Iceland (plus 16 countries)	Gallup International Covid-19 research	https://www.gallup.is/frettir/covid-19-rannsokn-samanburdur-milli-landa/							x		x	
IS04	Iceland	COVID-19 NATIONAL RESILIENCE COHORT	https://lidanicovid.is/about-the-study/									x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta l Justice	Human Rights	Other	
IS05	Iceland	Gallup's national pulse	https://www.gallup.is/frettir/covid-19-sottvarnarreglur/										x
IS06	Iceland	Gallup's national pulse	https://www.gallup.is/frettir/nyr-thjodarpuls-gallup-covid-19/			x			x				x
IS07	Iceland	Student's well-being during Covid-10	https://www.stjornarradid.is/efst-a-baugi/frettir/stok-frett/2021/03/30/Konnun-a-lidan-studenta-a-timum-COVID-19/		x								x
IS08	Iceland	Information gathering of the general public because of Covid-10	https://maskina.is/maelabord/upplysingaoreida/						x				x
IS09	Iceland	Health and well-being of Icelanders during Covid-19	https://www.landlaeknir.is/servlet/file/store93/item43190/Talnbrunnur_September_2020.pdf										x
IS10	Iceland	Icelanders' happiness	https://maskina.is/hamingja-islendinga-obreytt-i-midjum-covid-19-faraldrinum/										x
IS11	Iceland	Well-being and position of students at the University of Iceland during covid-19	https://student.backend.ildevelopment.is/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/5-Konnun-9-oktober.pdf										x
IT01	Italy	The COVID-19 pandemic among the migrant and foreign-born population in the provinces of Milan, Bergamo, Brescia and Cremona	https://www.ismu.org/la-pandemia-covid-19-tra-la-popolazione-migrante-e-di-origine-straniera-nelle-province-di-mi-bg-bs-cr/		x			x					x
IT02	Italy	Diary of the Italians (Diario degli italiani)	https://www.istat.it/it/archivio/255684	x		x		x					x
IT03	Italy	Transition phase 1 - phase 2 the work of men and women (Transizione fase 1 – fase 2 il lavoro di uomini e donne)	https://oa.inapp.org/xmlui/bitstream/handle/123456789/835/Inapp_Cardinali_Dalla_Fase_1_alla_Fase_2_quale_transizione_uomini_donne_WP_56_2021.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y		x			x					
IT04	Italy, Turkey	Emotional and psychological impacts of COVID-19 social distancing and gender stereotypes on well-being in Italy and Turkey during the lockdown	https://www.irpps.cnr.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/7155-7163.pdf										x
IT05	Italy	Young people in the time of the coronavirus (I giovani ai tempi del coronavirus)	https://www.savethechildren.it/press/scuola-e-covid-il-28-degli-adolescenti-un-compagno-di-classe-ha-smesso-di-frequentare-la										x

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta l Justice	Human Rights	Other	
IT06	Italy	Children and lockdown: the word from parents (Bambini e lockdown: la parola ai genitori)	https://www.unimib.it/comunicati/bambini-durante-lockdown-vulnerabili-ma-resilienti					x				x	
IT07	Italy	Smartworking: opportunities and risks for women's work (Smartworking: opportunità e rischi per il lavoro femminile)	https://27esimaora.corriere.it/violenza/21_maggio_01/1-maggio-2021-lavoro-retribuito-lavoro-non-retribuito-tre-donne-quattro-vogliono-smart-working-ma-poi-si-sentono-prigioniere-superlavoro-215be5c6-a909-11eb-afd8-e23f23e9f8bf.shtml		x			x					
IT08	Italy	The economic condition of women in the era of Covid-19	https://www.weworld.it/cosa-facciamo/pubblicazioni/la-condizione-economica-delle-donne-in-epoca-covid-19_brief-report		x							x	
IT09	Italy	WOMEN AND WORK: lights and shadows of the impact of Covid-19 on the lives of female workers	https://ondaosservatorio.it/ondauploads/2021/05/Prezentazione-dati-ricerca29042.pdf		x							x	x
IT10	Italy	Women's work, housework and childcare, before and during COVID-19	https://cepr.org/content/covid-economics-vetted-and-real-time-papers-0		x			x				x	
LT01	Lithuania	Social policy responses to the consequences of the COVID-19 crisis: analysis of the unemployment and poverty situation, international experience and recommendations for Lithuania	https://www.fsf.vu.lt/naujienos/fakulteto-ivykiai/3240-socialines-politikos-reakcijos-i-covid-19-krizes-pasekmes-nedarbo-ir-skurdo-padeties-analize-tarptautine-patirtis-ir-rekomendacijos-lietuvai		x	x							
LT02	Lithuania	Social inequality and its risks during a pandemic	https://www.vdu.lt/cris/handle/20.500.12259/128293		x	x						x	
LT03	Lithuania	Implications of COVID-19 for the Human Security: Challenges and New Opportunities	https://spektras.lmt.lt/REZ_santrauka.php?pW5DGivjoCGQA5YGsyN+LcjmhIC71pMpYKGuu5OXw24=		x	x		x	x			x	
LT04	Lithuania	Changes in Employment in the Lithuanian Labour Market and Measures to Overcome Negative Consequences in the Context of the COVID-19 Pandemic	https://spektras.lmt.lt/REZ_santrauka.php?8gPvnMZorTkXlBkO3XtnRLGoGPdH3tgFxmZl3u16iu4=		x	x		x					
LT05	Lithuania	COVID-19 Distress Thermometer	https://spektras.lmt.lt/REZ_santrauka.php?OX+3FUzBrwOXIc5W235DWzFvHh3fFGCCr+8fUFCFHjA=									x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environment & Justice	Human Rights	Other	
LV03	Latvia	The possibilities for reconciling work and private life for different socio-demographic groups during the period of restrictions imposed in order to reduce the spread of COVID-19	https://www.rsu.lv/sites/default/files/imce/Projekti/VP_COVID/29_zinojums_21022021_final_c.pdf		x			x					
LV04	Latvia	The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the mental health of Latvian adolescents and young people	https://www.pusaudzis.lv/p%C4%93t%C4%ABjums					x					
LV05	Latvia	Survey of LCCI members on the impact of COVID-19	https://www.ltrk.lv/sites/default/files/inline-files/COVID_biedru_v%C4%93rt%C4%93jums_apr%C4%ABis_II.pdf			x							
LV06	Latvia	On the problems and their solutions in ensuring the distance education process in the conditions of the state emergency	https://www.lizda.lv/projects_and_studies/petijums-par-problemam-un-risinajumiem-attalinata-izglitiba-procesa-nodrosinasana-valsts-arkartejas-situacijas-apstaklos/		x								
LV07	Latvia	Quality of professional life of pre-school employees in the conditions of the state emergency	https://www.lizda.lv/projects_and_studies/petijuma-pirmsskola-nodarbinato-profesionala-dzives-kvalitate-valsts-arkartejas-situacijas-apstaklos-rezultati/		x								
LV08	Latvia	Study on public attitudes towards COVID-19	https://www.mk.gov.lv/lv/petijumi-0										x
LV09	Latvia	At the end of the school year survey	https://home.edurio.com/izm-gada-nosleguma-aptaujas		x			x					
LV10	Latvia	KANTAR Covid-19 barometer	https://www.kantar.lv/?s=Covid-19+barometrs				x						
LV11	Latvia	Covid-19 effects on job satisfaction	https://www.kantar.lv/84-latvijas-stradajoso-atzist-ka-darbs-ir-svarigs-un-kopuma-ir-viena-no-svarigakajam-jomam-kas-ietekme-vinu-emocionalo-noskanojumu-un-laimes-sajutu/		x								
LV12	Latvia	Feeling of Happiness at Work	https://www.kantar.lv/41-stradajoso-atzist-ka-covid-19-pandemijas-apstakli-ir-ietekmejusi-vinu-emocionalo-labsajutu/		x								

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
NL01	The Netherlands	Global Female Leaders Outlook 2020	https://home.kpmg/xx/en/home/insights/2021/01/global-female-leaders-outlook-2020.html		x		x			x			
NL02	The Netherlands	The Covid19 Gender (IN)equality Survey Netherlands.	https://www.uu.nl/nieuws/zorgen-voor-de-kinderen-tijdens-corona-de-rol-van-de-vader-wordt-weer-kleiner		x			x					
NL03	The Netherlands	If you ask us (Als Je Het Ons Vraagt).	https://www.dekinderombudsman.nl/publicaties									x	
NL04	The Netherlands	Population groups with migration background more severely affected by covid-19.	https://www.coronatijden.nl/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Policy-brief-Etniciteit-en-COVID-19-Coronatijden-in-Nederland.pdf									x	
NL05	The Netherlands	Vulnerable in Amsterdam: Effects Covid-19 and assistance to vulnerable groups (Kwetsbaar in Amsterdam: Effecten Covid-19 en hulpverlening aan kwetsbare groepen)	https://www.coronatijden.nl/kwetsbaar-amsterdam/			x						x	
NL06	The Netherlands	Loneliness and Mental Health During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Study Among Dutch Older Adults	https://www.coronatijden.nl/sociale-isolatie-deelprojecten/									x	
NL07	The Netherlands	Corona hinders adolescents' sexuality	https://www.rutgers.nl/nieuws-opinie/nieuwsarchief/corona-belemmert-de-seksualiteit-van-jongeren									x	x
NL08	The Netherlands	Quarter of healthcare staff suffer financial loss after COVID-19 infection	https://www.fnv.nl/nieuwsbericht/sectornieuws/zorg-welzijn/2021/03/kwart-zorgpersoneel-lijdt-financiële-schade-na-bes			x						x	
NL09	The Netherlands	The COVID-19 outbreak increases maternal stress during pregnancy, but not the risk for postpartum depression	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00737-021-01104-9									x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta l Justice	Human Rights	Other	
NL10	The Netherlands	Inequality in homeschooling during the Corona crisis in the Netherlands. First results from the LISS Panel.	https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/hf32q					x				x	
PL01	Poland	Pandemic and Remote Learning Stories of LGBTQ + Youth. (HISTORIE MŁODZIEŻY LGBTQ+ Z CZASU PANDEMII I NAUCZANIA ZDALNEGO.)	http://emocjonalnebhp.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Raport-badawczy-2.pdf									x	x
PL02	Poland	Women's situation during the pandemic (Sytuacja kobiet w czasie pandemii)	https://sukcespisanyszminka.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Raport-Sytuacja-Polek-w-pandemii.pdf	x	x		x	x					
PL03		Quality of Life of Elderly in Poland during the first year of COVID-19 pandemic (JAKOŚĆ ŻYCIA OSÓB STARSZYCH W POLSCE W PIERWSZYM ROKU PANDEMII COVID-19)	https://seniorhub.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/raport-jakosc-zycia-osob-starszych-09.pdf									x	
PL04	Poland	Everyday life in times of a pandemic (Życie codzienne w czasach pandemii)	http://socjologia.amu.edu.pl/images/pliki/r%c3%b3%c5%bcne_prezentacje_etc/%c5%bbycie_codzienne_w_czasach_pandemii_-_Wydzia%c5%82_Socjologii_UAM_-_WWW.pdf	x	x	x		x				x	
PL05	Poland	Mother from Warsaw. Mother in the labour market. Let's win with COVID. (Mama-Warszawianka. Mama na rynku pracy. Wygrajmy z Covidem)	https://sukcespisanyszminka.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Raport_Mama_Warszawianka.pdf	x	x		x	x				x	
PL06	Poland	Women versus the coronavirus. How has the pandemic changed their lives and work? (Kobiety kontra koronawirus. Jak pandemia zmieniła ich życie i pracę?)	https://static.im-g.pl/im/6/26955/m26955216,NIEUSTRASZONA-W-PRACY-V2.pdf		x	x	x	x				x	
PL07	Poland	The impact of the pandemic on the career development prospects of women in business (Wpływ pandemii na perspektywy rozwoju zawodowego kobiet w biznesie)	https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/pl/Documents/Reports/pl_Raport_Wplyw_pandemii_na_kobiety_w_biznesie_Deloitte.pdf		x		x	x					

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS								
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other
PL08	Poland	Work And Coronavirus: Will Persons with Disabilities Lose Jobs? (PRACA A KORONAWIRUS. CZY OSOBY Z NIEPEŁNOSPRAWNOŚCIAMI STRACĄ PRACĘ?)	https://aktywizacja.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Badanie-pracodawc%C3%B3w-Praca-a-koronawirus.-Co-z-zatrudnieniem-os%C3%B3b-z-niepe%C5%82nosprawno%C5%9Bciami-1.pdf		x	x						
PL09	Poland	Negative experiences of young people during the pandemic (Negatywne doświadczenia młodzieży w trakcie pandemii)	https://fdds.pl/_Resources/Persistent/5/0/0/e/500e0774b0109a6892ce777b0d8595f528adea62/Negatywnie-doswiadczenia-mlodziezy-w-trakcie-pandemii.-Raport-z-badan-ilosciowych-1.pdf	x								
PL10	Poland	Report from survey of foreigners related to Lublin city in the time of COVID-19 (Raport z badań ankietowych cudzoziemców i cudzożemek związanych z Lublinem w dobie COVID-19)	https://www.hf.org.pl/upload/file/Raport%20-%20cudzoziemcy%20a%20COVID-19.pdf		x							x
PL11	Poland	The professional situation of Poles during the coronavirus epidemic (Sytuacja zawodowa Polaków w trakcie epidemii koronawirusa)	https://cbos.pl/PL/szukaj/open_file.php?url=2020/K_126_20.PDF&tytul=Sytuacja+zawodowa+Polak:243:w+w+trakcie+epidemii+koronawirusa		x							
PL12	Poland	Everyday life in times of the epidemic (Życie codzienne w czasach zarazy)	https://cbos.pl/PL/szukaj/open_file.php?url=2020/K_060_20.PDF&tytul=:379:yicie+codzienne+w+czasach+zarazy		x	x				x	x	
PL13	Poland	The situation of Warsaw women during the epidemic (Sytuacja Warszawianek w czasie epidemii)	https://www.um.warszawa.pl/sites/all/files/download_file.php?file=/sites/default/files/attach/aktualnosci/sytuacja_warszawianek_w_czasie_epidemii_-_raport_z_badan.pdf	x				x				x
PT01	Portugal, England and Netherlands	Experience of discreet choice COVID-19 Portugal (Experiência de escolha discreta COVID-19 Portugal)	https://www2.novasbe.unl.pt/en/		x	x			x			x
PT02	Portugal	Social Impact of the Pandemic (O Impacto Social da Pandemia)	https://www.ics.ulisboa.pt/docs/RelatorioInqueritoCISICTE.pdf		x	x	x	x	x			x

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta	Justice	Human Rights	Other
PT04	Portugal	Pandemic diaries (Diários de uma pandemia)	https://www.publico.pt/aovivo/detalhe/adaptaram-cidadaos-pandemia-covid19-diarios-pandemia-239		x	x						x	
PT05	Portugal	PsiQuaren10	https://www.ispa.pt/noticia/fadiga-pandemica-dos-portugueses		x	x						x	
PT06	Portugal, Netherlands	VD@COVID19	https://www.ensp.unl.pt/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/relatorio-publico-vdcovid19-protected-site.pdf	x	x							x	
PT07	Portugal	Social and Psychological Health Support Networks for Young LGBT+ during the Covid-19 Pandemic (Redes de Apoio Social e Saúde Psicológica em Jovens LGBT+ durante a pandemia de Covid-19)	https://www.cig.gov.pt/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Relat%C3%B3rio-final-17-de-maio-de-2020_ESTUDO-LGBT-COVID-19.pdf	x	x							x	x
PT08	Portugal	Mental Health in times of Pandemics (Saúde Mental em Tempos de Pandemia)	http://hdl.handle.net/10400.18/7245		x	x		x				x	
PT10	Portugal, Brazil and 38 other countries	Impacto Psicossocial da COVID-19 em Portugal	https://www.ces.uc.pt/ficheiros2/files/RELATORIO_Resultados%20Preliminares%20sobre%20Impacto%20Psicossocial%20da%20COVID-19%20em%20Portugal.pdf		x	x							
RO01	Romania	Changes in mental health during the COVID-19 crisis in Romania: A repeated cross-section study based on the measurement of subjective perceptions and experiences	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/00368504211025873		x			x					
RO02	Romania	Working From Home (WFH)	https://sites.google.com/site/rqsaro/news/wfh20raport		x			x					
RO03	Romania	Women's experiences during the pandemic: state of affairs and recommendations for gender-sensitive post-crisis measures	https://coronavirus.centruifilia.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Raport_Online.ro-1.pdf	x	x		x	x				x	
RO04	Romania	Main Concerns in Times of COVID-19 in Three Groups of People: Italians, Romanian Immigrants in Italy, and Romanians in Romania	https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/main-concerns-in-times-of-covid-19-in-three-groups-of-people-italians-romanian-immigrants-in-italy-a		x								

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS								
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other
RO05	Romania (also rest of EU27+UK)	Living, working and COVID-19	https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/data/covid-19		x			x			x	
RO06	Romania	The Welfare of Rural Children during the Pandemic	https://worldvision.ro/2020/08/04/studiu-world-vision-romania-viata-copiilor-din-rural-in-pandemie-40-dintre-parinti-nu-au-reusit-sa-asigure-alimentele-si-produsele-de-baza-doar-60-dintre-elevi-au-facut-scoala-online/		x			x			x	
RO07	Romania	Gender and Age-Related Differences in Depression, Anxiety and Stress during the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Cross-Sectional Study	https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=943999								x	
RO08	Romania	Job Stress and Burnout among Social Workers in the VUCA World of COVID-19 Pandemic	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/13/13/7109/html		x						x	
RO09	Romania	The Psychosocial Impact of the Romanian Government Measures on the Population During the COVID-19 Pandemic	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3867440								x	
RO10	Romania	Demographic Factors Related with COVID-19 Anxiety	http://www.swreview.ro/index.pl/demographic_factors_related_with_covid-19_anxiety								x	
SE01	Sweden	Distance learning in high schools - may affect girls and boys differently	https://www.skolinspektionen.se/globalassets/02-beslut-rapporter-stat/granskningsrapporter/ovriga-publikationer/2021/fjarr--och-distansundervisning-i-gymnasieskolan/fjarr--och-distansundervisning-pa-gymnasieskolor-varen-2021-pm-2021_1666.pdf								x	
SE02	Sweden	How do pregnant women and their partners experience the corona pandemic?	https://www.gu.se/som-institutet/resultat-och-publikationer/som-undersokningen-om-coronaviruset								x	
SE03	Sweden	The pandemic hits women and men's working lives differently	https://www.akavia.se/senaste/pressmeddelanden/brister-i-jamstalldhet-tydligare-under-covid-19/		x						x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
SER05	Serbia	Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and measures for its prevention on women entrepreneurs in Serbia	https://www.secons.net/files/publications/128-publication.pdf		x	x		x					
SER06	Serbia	Impact of COVID-19 pandemic and measures for its prevention on the socio-economic position of rural women, with the focus on agriculture	https://www.secons.net/files/publications/130-publication.pdf		x	x		x				x	
SER07	Serbia	Consequences of COVID-19 on women's and men's economic empowerment	https://serbia.unfpa.org/en/publications/consequences-covid-19-womens-and-mens-economic-empowerment		x	x							
SER08	Serbia	Older Persons in the Republic of Serbia and COVID-19 Pandemic	https://serbia.unfpa.org/sites/default/files/pub-pdf/older-persons-and-covid-19-01-12.pdf									x	
SER09	Serbia	COVID-19 Socio-Economic Impact Assessment	https://serbia.un.org/en/92907-covid-19-socio-economic-impact-assessment		x	x		x		x	x		
SER10	Serbia (plus Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Turkey)	Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on specialist services for victims and survivors of violence in the Western Balkans and Turkey	https://eca.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2020/05/impact-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-specialist-services-for-victims-and-survivors-of-violence	x									
SER11	Serbia	Impact of the COVID-19 crisis on employment: Focus on vulnerable categories	http://socijalnoukljucivanje.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Uticaj_COVID-19_krize_na_zaposlenost.pdf		x	x							
SI01	Slovenia	Atmosphere in intimate partnerships and families during quarantine and increased insecurity	http://ipes-si.org/blog/2020/06/08/raziskava-vzdušje-v-intimno-partnerskih-odnosih-in-druzinah-v-casu-karantene-in-povecane-negotovosti/	x									

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS										
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta	Justice	Human Rights	Other	
SI02	Slovenia	Research about remote schooling	https://www.rtv slo.si/slovenija/raziskava-o-posledicah-solanja-na-daljavo-starsi-utrjeni-in-zaskrbljeni-otroci-brez-motivacije/569307						X				X	
SI03	Slovenia	Impacts of COVID-19 on some aspects of quality of life and well-being	https://www.umar.gov.si/fileadmin/user_upload/publikacije/kratke_analize/Vplivi_Covid-19_na_zivljenje_Sodja_Vplivi_Covid-19_na_nekatere_vidike_kakovosti_zivljenja_in_druzbene_blaginje1.pdf	X	X				X					
SI04	Slovenia	Criminology in times of COVID-19	http://inst-krim.si/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Kriminaliteta-v-dobi-covid-19.pdf	X										
SI05	Slovenia	Development report 2021	https://www.umar.gov.si/en/publications/development-report/publication/news/porocilo-o-razvoju-2021/?tx_news_pi1%5Bcontroller%5D=News&tx_news_pi1%5Baction%5D=detail&cHash=63819becc4d1eb31fdd9b60cb1a8c8b	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SI06	Slovenia	Assessment of psychosocial support needs in the second wave of the COVID-19 epidemic	http://www.dps.si/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Ocena-potreb-psihihosocialni-podpori.pdf	X	X			X	X				X	
SI07	Slovenia	Short analysis: Wage gap and gender inequality in Slovenia	https://www.umar.gov.si/fileadmin/user_upload/publikacije/kratke_analize/2020_10_Placna_vrzeli_Gregorc/Placna_vrzeli_in_neenakosti_spolov_v_Sloveniji.pdf		X	X	X	X	X					
SI08	Slovenia	Experimental statistics: Work and education in the time of COVID-19	https://www.stat.si/StatWeb/en/News/Index/9498		X									
SI09	Slovenia	Inequalities in Health: Future Challenges for Intersectional Cooperation	https://www.nijz.si/sites/www.nijz.si/files/uploaded/neeenakosti_povzetek_angleski_e_verzija_23_6_21.pdf									X	X	
SI10	Slovenia	COVID-19 pandemic in Slovenia	https://www.nijz.si/sl/izsledki-panelne-spletne-raziskave-si-panda		X							X	X	
SK01	Slovakia	Survey on life situation during the COVID-19 pandemic	www.totojrovnost.eu/downloads/Prieskum_zivotnej_situacie_pocas_pandemie_COVID19.pdf	X	X	X		X						

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other	
SK02	Slovakia	When the world has changed	www.uesa.sav.sk/?=sk/ked-sa-zmenil-svet-i-vplyv-pandemie-koronavirusu-na-kazdodenny-zivot-na-slovensku					x					
SK03	Slovakia	Values and society during COVID-19 pandemic	www.sociologia.sav.sk/cms/uploaded/3169_attach_Hodnoty_spolocnost_2020_pramenna.pdf			x			x			x	
SK04	Slovakia	How are you Slovakia?	www.sociologia.sav.sk		x	x						x	
SK05	Slovakia	Youth in times of Corona	https://archiv.mladez.sk/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/RmS_OSF_Webinar_Mladi-v-case-korony_FINAL.pdf			x		x					
SK06	Slovakia	Delivery, rights, pandemic	https://zenskekruhy.sk/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/POROD_PRAVA_PANDE_MIA.pdf									x	
SK07	Slovakia	Mapping of needs of women surviving IPV during the quarantine	www.zastavmenasilie.gov.sk/news/data-potvr dili-zenasilie-na-zenach-pocas-koronakrizy-vyrazne-stuplo/	x									
SK08	Slovakia	Survey on distant education in a school year of 2020/21	www.vzdelavacieanalyzy.sk/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Prieskum-distančne-vzdelavanie_final.pdf		x							x	
SK09	Slovakia	Home office	www.go4insight.com/post/home-office-láka-obľúbeným-sa-stáva-striedať-prácu-z-domu-a-kancelárie		x								
SK10	Slovakia	Labour market in quarantine	www.mfsr.sk/files/archiv/4/Trhpracevkarantene.pdf		x								
TR01	Turkey	Violations of the Rights of Women with Disabilities During the Covid-19 Pandemic	http://www.korlerfederasyonu.org.tr/images/3.pdf	x	x	x						x	
TR02	Turkey	Being a Woman During Pandemic	https://kadinininsanhaklari.org/salginda-kadin-olmak-arastirmasi-raporu-yayimlandi/	x	x	x		x				x	
TR03	Turkey	Turkey research report on the impact of the COVID-19 lockdown on women and violence against women and children	https://sahamerkezi.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/kad%C4%B1n-covid-ek.pdf	x				x				x	

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS									
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmenta	Justice	Human Rights	Other
TR04	Turkey	The economic and social impact of COVID-19 on women and men: Rapid gender assessment of COVID-19 implications in Turkey	https://eca.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2020/06/the-impact-of-covid19-on-women-and-men-rapid-gender-assessment-of-covid19-implications-in-turkey	x	x	x		x				x	
TR05	Turkey	Gender Gaps in The Care Economy During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Turkey	https://www.tr.undp.org/content/turkey/tr/home/library/corporatereports/COVID-gender-survey-report.html					x					
TR06	Turkey	Gender Inequality in the Covid-19 Pandemic: Who Did the Housework? Who Took Care of The Kids?	https://ipc.sabanciuniv.edu/Content/Images/CKeditor/Images/20210401-19042321.pdf					x					
TR07	Turkey	How has COVID-19 affected Turkey's labour market?	https://www.tepav.org.tr/en/haberler/s/10170		x	x							
TR08	Turkey	Research Report on LGBTI+ Persons' Access to Social Services During the Pandemic	https://spod.org.tr/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/pandemi-EN-finn-1.pdf	x		x						x	
TR09	Turkey	Turkey Rapid Needs Assessment on the Impact of Covid-19 on Migrant and Refugee Populations	https://turkey.iom.int/reports/iom-turkey-rapid-needs-assessment-impact-covid19-migrant-and-refugee-populations		x	x						x	
TR10	Turkey	The Research on Specialized Needs of Women Health Workers in the COVID-19 Pandemic	https://turkey.unfpa.org/en/news/our-research-needs-women-health-workers-covid-19-pandemic-out https://turkey.unfpa.org/en/publications/research-specialized-needs-women-health-workers-covid-19-pandemic		x			x				x	
UK01	UK	The Coronavirus Crossroads, Equal Pay Day 2020	https://www.fawcettsociety.org.uk/Handlers/Download.ashx?IDMF=dbe15227-4c02-4102-bbf2-dce0b415e729		x		x	x					
UK02	UK	Working@home	https://www.workingathome.org.uk		x			x					
UK03	UK	UCL Virus Watch's Longitudinal Study	https://ucl-virus-watch.net/			x			x			x	
UK04	UK	Household Longitudinal Covid-19 survey	https://www.kcl.ac.uk/giwl/assets/does-furlough-work-for-women.pdf		x		x						

Code	Country	RAS Name	Website or Report	DOMAINS								
				Gender-Based	Work & Labour	Economy	Gender Pay & Pension Gaps	Gender Care Gap	Decision Making	Environmental Justice	Human Rights	Other
UK05	UK	Welfare – At a (Social) Distance	www.distantwelfare.co.uk		x	x						
UK06	UK	UK Covid-19 mental health and wellbeing study	https://suicideresearch.info/tracking-the-impact-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-on-mental-wellbeing-study-covid-mh/									x
UK07	UK	Unequal Britain: Attitudes to inequalities after Covid-19	https://www.kcl.ac.uk/policy-institute/assets/unequal-britain.pdf			x	x				x	x
UK08	UK (England and Wales)	National Police Chiefs' Council data on reported crime and Fixed Penalty Notices (FPNs)	https://news.npcc.police.uk/releases/crime-is-lower-than-a-year-ago-and-more-fines-given-to-the-public-under-coronavirus-regulations	x								
UK09	UK	Baby Steps: The gender division of childcare during the COVID19 pandemic	http://www.bristol.ac.uk/efm/media/workingpapers/working_papers/pdffiles/dp20723.pdf		x			x				
UK10	UK (England and Wales)	Hear Us: The experiences of refugee and asylum-seeking women during the pandemic	https://dfbceaf-7cbc-4bfa-8f79-6a8a879c2c25.filesusr.com/ugd/d37102_3eb3a41885e24e648f049a972e7e3335.pdf	x	x	x					x	

Acknowledgements

This deliverable benefits from empirical material that has been produced by the RESISTIRÉ network of national researchers, including:

Country	Author/s
Austria	Elisabeth Anna Guenther, Celina Beck
Belgium	Alain Denis, Nathalie Wuiame, Igor Zivkovic, Aart Kerremans
Bulgaria	Ralitsa Golemanova
Croatia	Sanja Sarnavka
Cyprus	Maria Kyprianou
Czech Republic	Vanda Maufras Černohorská
Denmark	Stine Thidemann Faber
Estonia	Triin Roosalu
Finland	Inkeri Tanhua
France	Suzanne de Cheveigné
Germany	Merve Yorulmaz
Greece	Nelli Kambouri
Hungary	Agnes Kende
Iceland	Finnborg Salome Steinþórsdóttir
Ireland	Sara Clavero, Mark Ryan
Italy	Claudia Aglietti, Maresa Berliri
Latvia	Marita Zitmane
Lithuania	Vita Kontvaine, Vaida Tretjakova
Luxemburg	Nathalie Wuiame, Alain Denis
Netherlands	Marloes van Engen, Elsbeth Nieuwkamp, Amber Kaziur
Poland	Ewelina Ciaputa
Portugal	Catarina Sales de Oliveira
Romania	Monica Stroe
Serbia	Zorana Antonijevic
Slovakia	Zuzana Ocnasova
Slovenia	Katarina Zupevc
Spain	Elena Ghidoni, Laia Tarragona, María López Belloso, Silvestre Cabrera María, Beloki Usue
Sweden	Fatma Tuncer, Anne-Charlott Callerstig
Turkey	Kristen Biehl, SU Gender team
United Kingdom	Clare Stovell, Charoula Tzanakou, Alexis Still, Anne Laure Humbert

This deliverable also benefits from the review, comments, and suggestions produced by the partners of the RESISTIRÉ project.